

RESPOND

Working Papers

Global Migration: Consequences and Responses

Paper 2020/45, March 2020

Reception Policies, Practices and Responses

Poland Country Report

**Marta Pachocka, Konrad Pędziwiatr,
Karolina Sobczak-Szelc, Justyna Szałańska**

Centre of Migration Research, University of Warsaw

© Marta Pachocka, Konrad Pędziwiatr, Karolina Sobczak-Szelc, Justyna Szalańska

Reference: RESPOND Deliverable 4.1.

This research was conducted under the Horizon 2020 project 'RESPOND Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond' (#770564).

This publication has been produced with the assistance of the European Commission. The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of the RESPOND Project consortium authors and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Union. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to: marta.pachocka@gmail.com, k.pedziwiatr@gmail.com, k.sobczak-szelc@uw.edu.pl, justyna.szalanska@uw.edu.pl.

Suggested citation: Pachocka, M., Pędziwiatr, K., Sobczak-Szelc, K., Szalańska, J. (2020). 'Reception Policies, Practices and Responses. Poland – Country Report', Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project (#770564, Horizon2020) Report Series, Available at: <https://www.respondmigration.com/wp-blog/>.

This document is available for download at: www.respondmigration.com

Horizon 2020
RESPOND: Multilevel
Governance of Mass Migration in
Europe and Beyond (770564)

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union

Contents

Acknowledgements	5
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	7
List of Abbreviations	8
About the Project	9
Executive Summary	10
Introduction	13
Methodology and Sources	15
1. Legal Regulations and Policies of Reception: A Multi-level Perspective	27
1.2. National Legal and Institutional Framework	29
1.3. Housing and Allowances	36
1.4. Healthcare (Medical) Services	46
1.5. Education	49
1.6. Labour Market	54
2. Reception Practices	56
2.1. Housing and Allowances	56
2.1.1. Housing outside the Centres for Foreigners	56
2.1.2. Housing in the Centres for Foreigners	60
2.2. Healthcare (Medical) Services	67
2.3. Early Access to Education	72
2.3.1. Asylum-Seeking Children in Schools	72
2.3.2. Access to Education for Adults	78
2.4. Early Access to the Labour Market	82
2.5. Encounter with Officials, Civil Actors, and the Receiving Society	86
Conclusions: Challenges, Prospects, and Policy Recommendations	91
Appendices	96
References and Sources	101

Acknowledgements

This report includes findings from desk research and qualitative interviews conducted as part of the project *RESPOND—Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond*. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors. However, we are grateful to several people who have provided us with valuable support. We express our very great appreciation to the external reviewers representing various institutions involved in migration and asylum governance: Marta Górczyńska (Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights), Anna Górska (Institute of Public Affairs) and Dominik Wach (Warsaw Family Support Centre and University of Warsaw). We would like to specially thank the Work Package 4 Team from the RESPOND consortium, including Ayhan Kaya from Istanbul Bilgi University and Alexander K. Nagel from the University of Göttingen. We would also like to acknowledge the support in language editing provided by Brien Barnett and Angelica Jaje. To this end, it is important to emphasize that the preparation of this report—strongly based on the qualitative research material from interviews—would not have been possible without the involvement of members of the Polish team of the RESPOND project, who were responsible for reaching respondents, conducting meso- and micro-level interviews, and their translation, transcription, and coding. These were Karolina Sobczak-Szelc, Marta Pachocka, Justyna Szałańska, Monika Szulecka, Konrad Pędziwiatr, Gagik Grigoryan, and Feras Daboul.

List of Figures

Figure 1 Map of border crossings and Border Guard facilities in Poland	20
Figure 2 Location of guarded (detention) centres for foreigners in Poland (<i>ośrodek rodzinny</i> – centre for families, <i>ośrodek męski</i> – centre for men, <i>małoletni bez opieki</i> – unaccompanied minors).....	21
Figure 3 Location of centres for foreigners in Poland in early 2020 (including reception centres, residence centres and detentions centres).....	22
Figure 4 Social assistance provided by the Office for Foreigners to persons seeking international protection in Poland	39

List of Tables

Table 1 Sample of micro-level interviews in Poland	17
Table 2 Sample of meso-level interviews in Poland	23
Table 3 Development of migration and asylum laws and policies – overview	32
Table 4 List of public authorities involved in the migration and asylum governance	34
Table 5 Allowances for asylum seekers living outside the centres for foreigners.....	40
Table 6 Foreigners in the case of whom proceedings for international protection have been initiated and who are entitled to accommodation in the centres for foreigners or who are being paid cash allowance to live outside the centres.....	40
Table 7 The number of asylum seekers covered by medical care provided by the Office for Foreigners and the cost of medical services in 2015-2019.....	48
Table 8 The number of requested certificates and decisions issued in this regard	55
Table 9 Asylum-seeking children (aged 6-17) in schools in Poland.....	73
Table 10 Main legislative acts relevant to asylum procedures, reception conditions and detention in Poland	96
Table 11 Main implementing decrees and administrative guidelines and regulations relevant to asylum procedures, reception conditions and detention in Poland	97
Table 12 Directives and other CEAS measures transposed into national legislation in Poland	98

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full name
AIDA	Asylum Information Database
AMIF	Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund
BG	Border Guard
DSA	Department for Social Assistance (of the Office for Foreigners)
Dz.U.	<i>Dziennik Ustaw</i> (in Polish); Journal of Laws (in English)
EASO	European Asylum Support Office
ECRE	European Council on Refugees and Exiles
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
EDAL	European Database of Asylum Law
EU	European Union
FRONTEX	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
HFHR	Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights
IGOs	Intergovernmental Organisations
IOM	International Organization for Migration
IOs	International Organisations
MFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MFLSP	Ministry of Family, Labour, and Social Policy
MIA	Ministry of the Interior and Administration
MNE	Ministry of National Education
MSs	Member States
NGOs	Non-governmental Organisations
NHF	National Health Fund
OF	Office for Foreigners
Paragraph	Par.
RESPOND	Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond
Supreme Audit Office	SAO
t.j.	<i>Tekst jednolity</i> (in Polish); Consolidated text (in English)
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
WP1/2/3/4/5	Work Package 1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5
z późn. zm.	<i>z późniejszymi zmianami</i> (in Polish); with amendments (in English)

About the Project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of **14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden.** The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an **in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration** at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization. Each thematic field is reflecting a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the findings related to WP4, which focuses specifically on reception policies, practices and humanitarian responses to the current refugee crisis. Despite efforts to achieve harmonization (especially promoted by the 2016 CEAS and by the ENP), relevant differences exist in this field in the countries that are the object of research (Austria, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Sweden, UK, Turkey and Lebanon). WP4 will map the policies and practices of reception and humanitarian responses of the afore-mentioned countries and migrants' perceptions, actions and reactions to policies and practices. The main objectives of WP4 are as follows:

- to develop a mapping of policies and practices of reception in the countries being researched;
- to develop a typology of these policies, practices and responses;
- to assess the coherence of these policies and practices with respect to international and EU standard;
- to study migrants' perceptions, actions and reactions to policies and practices;
- to provide basic information in the area of reception for the development of all subsequent WPs.

The last point will be achieved through an additional comparative report that will be based on the data from individual country reports.

Executive Summary

This country research report, prepared within Work Package 4, is focused on the reception conditions and reception policy in Poland and delivered under the H2020 project *RESPOND—Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond*. The structure of this report includes several key parts, the first of which is the introduction, outlining the aims and framework of the report. It is followed by a section discussing methodology and sources—the strategies used in gathering data (documents, literature, interviews, and other sources) and analysis of the collected material and the limitations encountered. The next part of the report provides a brief overview of the national legal and institutional frameworks in the field of asylum and reception in Poland as of 2018 (and 2019/2020, if justified) and summarises key developments since 2011. Particularly important for the WP4 report is the section on reception practices in specific policy areas, such as housing and allowances, healthcare (medical) services, early access to education, and early access to the labour market in Poland. The aforementioned section presents important insights from meso- and micro-level semi-structured interviews as well as relevant documents and literature to explain, contextualise, and complement. Extended quotations from the interviews are used to flesh out important results from the fieldwork. The conclusions of the WP4 report follow and are supplemented with policy recommendations in this regard.

In Poland, reception in legal and institutional terms means assistance for foreigners applying for international protection. Its basic scope is governed by the national provisions of the Law on Protection and two ordinances regarding the amount of financial assistance for asylum seekers and rules of stay in centres for foreigners. The most important public body responsible for reception policy is the Office for Foreigners (OF, supervised by the Ministry of Interior and Administration, MIA) and its Department for Social Assistance (DSA). The medical services provider for asylum seekers—selected in a public tender run by the Office for Foreigners—also plays an important role. Since 2015, this entity has been the private provider Petra Medica. Key actors in the area of public education for children include the Ministry of National Education, local public schools, and local self-government authorities in the vicinity of the centres for foreigners. To this end, NGOs also provide various forms of support to foreigners both in and outside the centres.

The findings of our research indicate that the OF has relatively adequate infrastructure to receive asylum seekers. Considering the information provided by the Office of the Commissioner for Human Rights and some NGOs supporting migrants about violations of the right to apply for asylum in Poland and, as a result, the decrease in the number of applicants for international protection in recent years, the number of places for foreigners in the centres seems sufficient. This is also linked to the increasing number of asylum seekers who often decide to live outside the centres for foreigners, relying on housing financial benefits paid by the state. The Office applies a mixed approach to manage the centres. In 2019, four centres were operated by the OF and the remaining seven were run by private entities selected through a tender procedure. The OF-run centres are the core of accommodation infrastructure, while the others can be opened or closed depending on the need. This is important in the event that the number of migrants increases in a short period of time. According to some meso-level respondents interviewed within the RESPOND project, the situation in the Office's centres is better because they are being modernised and more money is invested into them. In general, the standard of the centres has changed for the better in terms of cleanliness and equipment. Actions are also taken to provide pre-school care, places for prayer, and food that

includes special dietary requirements. A different issue is the choice of locations of the centres outside urban areas, especially those run by non-OF entities. As mentioned, it is possible to live outside the centres and receive financial benefits for this purpose; however, the funds are so low that they often do not cover even the basic cost of housing and require additional income (e.g., from undocumented work), living with relatives, or sharing an apartment/house with other migrants.

Overall, the staff of the centres for foreigners were assessed rather positively during our micro-level interviews. It should be noted that while living in a centre, the asylum seekers deal with Office employees, not social workers *per se* (there are no legal requirements regarding the education of the staff who work in the centres, e.g., that they have a social work degree or related). What matters in practice is a communicative knowledge of a foreign language, especially Russian (because most of the people who seek protection in Poland are Russian speaking), and ideally both Russian and English. People working in the centres mainly deal with office work, which does not leave them much time for social work with the residents, even if they would like to focus on it. Our meso-level respondents from various institutions/sectors spoke positively about mutual cooperation between NGOs and the Department for Social Assistance of the Office for Foreigners. In recent years, several NGOs have specialised in helping asylum seekers and refugees but their activity has been limited since 2015/2016 by the Ministry of the Interior and Administration, which significantly changed the rules for financing projects from EU money through AMIF. That resulted in limiting the activities of many NGOs. The situation may improve gradually in 2020 because in 2019, the Ministry settled the competition for AMIF funds.

From the point of view of forced migrants, it is important to note that the centres meet their basic living and social needs. However, staying in the centres is not conducive to pre-integration due to their location outside urban areas, the inability to work legally during the first six months of the asylum procedure, and the limited offer of Polish language courses or other activities. The scope of needs that can be met depends on the regulations and the availability of financial resources. Some migrants do not invest in pre-integration themselves. There are some reasons for this. First, they may not engage in Polish language courses because they do not know whether they will receive a positive decision in their case and be allowed to remain in Poland. Second, they often have other duties, like mothers who must care for children, which precludes them from attending courses. It is also difficult to socialise on a daily basis with the host society because the centres for foreigners are often outside a town or city. The situation is different for those living outside the centres; for them, the low financial assistance is the main challenge.

The meso-level actors we interviewed did not observe any special impact of the 2015 migration crisis on the functioning of the reception system in Poland, and especially on the centres, as their everyday operation is governed by specific rules and procedures. However, the change of government in 2015 and the Ministry's policy influenced the conditions for financing NGOs from AMIF funds, which limited the activities and projects implemented in the centres.

Criticism expressed during the micro- and meso-level interviews concerned the provision of medical services by Petra Medica since 2015—the quality of healthcare services (especially access to specialists) was rated as lower compared to the services provided by the Central Clinical Hospital of the Ministry of Interior and Administration up until 2015. In addition, a deficiency was identified in terms of access to psychologists who provide support free of

charge—either as part of guaranteed medical services or NGO assistance. This is connected to the shortage of specialists who know foreign languages and are prepared to work with asylum seekers, who may be affected by various trauma.

Introduction

This country research report, prepared within Work Package 4, is focused on the reception conditions and reception policy in Poland and delivered under the H2020 project *RESPOND—Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond*. The main aims of this report are:

- to analyse the policies and practices in the field of reception implemented by state and non-state actors;
- to analyse the experiences, actions, perceptions, and opinions of state and non-state actors and forced migrants with regard to the functioning of the national reception system and implemented reception policy;
- to provide empirical analysis based on the macro- (WP1 country report), meso- and micro-level (fieldwork) analyses;
- to evaluate the national reception system and provide policy recommendations.

The timeframe of the analysis covers mostly the years 2011-2017; however, where necessary we refer to previous years (e.g., to important political events or legal changes). We also provide an overview of the most recent developments regarding the legal and policy contexts in the field of reception conditions and policy between 2018 and early 2020.

The approaches and definitions applied in this report in general follow those elaborated for the project purposes and included in the *RESPOND* guidelines for WP4 country reports, as well as the national legal framework and context. In the report, we use some terms interchangeably to ensure the fluidity of considerations. Among others, this applies to the following expressions:

- asylum policy, international protection policy,
- asylum procedure, refugee procedure, proceedings for granting international protection, proceedings for granting refugee status,
- asylum application, refugee application, asylum claim, application for (international) protection, application for asylum, application for granting refugee status,
- applicant for international protection, applicant for asylum, applicant for refugee status, asylum seeker,
- reception conditions, reception system, reception.

The structure of this report includes several key parts starting with this introduction, followed by a section discussing the methodology and sources—the strategies used for gathering data (documents, literature, interviews, and other sources) and analysis of the collected material, together with the limitations encountered. The next part of the report provides a brief overview of the national legal and institutional framework in the field of asylum and reception in Poland as of 2018 (and 2019/2020 if justified) and summarises its key developments since 2011. It refers to three previous national reports prepared and published under the *RESPOND* project that cover the legal and policy framework of migration governance in Poland¹, border management and migration control², and refugee protection and asylum policy³. Particularly important for the WP4 report is the section on reception practices in specific policy areas, such as housing and allowances, healthcare (medical) services, early access to education, and

¹ For further information, see (Szulecka, et al., 2018b).

² For further information, see (Szulecka, 2019).

³ For further information, see (Pachocka & Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

early access to the labour market in Poland. This section presents important insights from the meso- and micro-level semi-structured interviews as well as relevant documents and literature to explain, contextualise, and complement. Extended quotations from the interviews are used to flesh out important results from the fieldwork. The conclusions of the WP4 report follow and are supplemented with policy recommendations in this regard.

Methodology and Sources⁴

This section discusses the strategies used to gather data (documents, literature, interviews, and other sources) and analysis of the collected material. The limitations encountered are also mentioned, as well as some reflections on ethical awareness and principles stemming from the consortium's code of ethics, adjusted for the national context.

The methodology applied in this report is compliant with the RESPOND project's guidelines for Work Package 4, focused on the reception regime. Two different methodological approaches were used in this report. The first was a legal and policy analysis. It relied on a brief analysis of the legal and policy framework from 2011 to 2018 (and 2019/2020 if justified). Along with official documents and statements, considering both the macro- and meso-levels, the reports and works published by international organisations and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) were used, as well as academic literature⁵. The second approach is heavily embedded in the qualitative research material collected from individual, in-depth semi-structured interviews conducted within the project at the micro- and meso-levels.

In this report, the meso- and micro-level perspective was included in subsequent sections and then in relation to selected issues, which allows for the smooth and consistent presentation and discussion of various topics concerning the reception regime, showing the approach of respondents at both levels.

In our qualitative research, the selection of meso- and micro-level respondents was purposeful and, additionally, the snowball recruitment method was applied in the case of micro-level interviews to reach forced migrants. The goal was to obtain opinions on the qualitative aspects of the functioning of reception policy in Poland and the asylum procedure, including both law and practice. Due to the non-exhaustive nature of the sample, the presented results of the qualitative research cannot be generalised, but they illustrate some trends and examples in the field.

For the micro-level interviews, the first step was to identify sampling criteria for Poland, having in mind the general guidelines developed in this field within the RESPOND consortium, as well as the national context, including the asylum statistics in Poland for 2011-2017 and the fact that Poland is often perceived as a transit country by forced migrants⁶. Considering the RESPOND guidelines for micro-level sampling criteria (the inclusion of the top two or three refugee/migrant groups within the time span of 2011-2017 in each country) and the Polish context (the structure of the asylum applicant population, as well as the beneficiaries of international protection; the presence of migrants on the territory of Poland), the research team decided to focus on three countries of origin of migrants, namely the Russian Federation, Ukraine, and Syria. The detailed justification for this selection is in the following paragraphs. As far as possible, the sub-samples of the interviewees were differentiated by place of residence (cities and small towns or villages), age (keeping in mind that most probably there would not be many asylum seekers and refugees above the age of 50), and gender (noting

⁴ This section was developed and updated if necessary on the basis of the section 'Methodology and Sources' from (Pachocka & Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

⁵ For further information, see the section 'References and Sources' of this report.

⁶ For further information, see (Szulecka, et al., 2018b) and (Szulecka, 2019).

that the inflow from Russia, and specifically from Chechnya⁷, and Ukraine is dominated by families, whereas it is by men in other national groups) (Szulecka, et al., 2018a).

According to asylum statistics for Poland for 2011-2017, the biggest share of both applicants for international protection and foreigners with granted international protection (refugee status and subsidiary protection) were citizens of the Russian Federation originating from Chechnya. In 2017, they constituted almost 70% of the asylum applicants, whereas in previous years they constituted even 90% of all applicants for international protection. Although less than 11% of asylum applicants obtained positive first-instance decisions annually in the analysed period of 2011-2017⁸, citizens of the Russian Federation originating from Chechnya were still the most numerous among the beneficiaries of international protection in Poland⁹. Poland's experience with the inflow of this group of asylum seekers is also quite extensive, at this point covering more than two decades. This has strongly influenced the reception and integration system for asylum seekers and refugees in Poland. Russian citizens originating from Chechnya are also subject to Dublin procedures and are apprehended at the border for attempts of unlawful border crossing. This fact additionally justified planning the sample with such a high share for Chechens or asylum seekers with Russian passports. Since 2014, Ukrainian citizens have become an important group of asylum seekers in Poland. Although the vast majority of decisions concluding their asylum procedures were either negative or discontinued, Ukrainian citizens were an important group of beneficiaries of subsidiary protection. Interestingly, positive decisions were made in their appeal procedures, which necessitated consideration of this group of asylum seekers and refugees. Ukrainian citizens are also the most numerous among the foreigners granted residence permits on humanitarian grounds during return procedures. Although Syrian citizens do not constitute a significant share of the asylum seekers in Poland, they are one of the biggest groups with granted refugee status by the Polish authorities. Contrary to other groups' applications for asylum in Poland, the rate of positive decisions for Syrians reached more than 90% in recent years. Moreover, Syrian citizens were apprehended for unlawful border crossing or unauthorised stay in Poland, which required that this group be considered for micro-level interviews (Szulecka, et al., 2018a).

The division into early and late arrivals in Poland was not directly linked to the so-called migration and refugee crisis that clearly affected asylum statistics in many European countries in 2015. From Poland's perspective, visible changes in the structure of the population of asylum seekers was influenced by the eruption of the 2014 military conflict between Ukraine and Russia. Nevertheless, the research group attempted to distinguish early arrivals from late ones (Szulecka, et al., 2018a).

⁷ Chechnya is a 'republic in southwestern Russia, situated on the northern flank of the Greater Caucasus range. Chechnya is bordered by Russia proper on the north, Dagestan Republic on the east and southeast, the country of Georgia on the southwest, and Ingushetiya Republic on the west. In the early 21st century, more than a decade of bitter conflict had devastated the republic, forced the mass exodus of refugees, and brought the economy to a standstill' (Encyclopaedia Britannica, n.d.).

⁸ Own elaboration based on data provided by the Office for Foreigners, see (Office for Foreigners, n.d.).

⁹ One should remember that in Poland, most of the first-instance decisions concern the so-called discontinuation (discontinuance) of the refugee procedure or are left unexamined. For more information about this, see (Szulecka, et al., 2018b, pp. 17-19, 48) and (Pachocka & Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, pp. 55-57).

The final material from the micro-level interviews includes 30 interviews carried out between July 2018 and August 2019 in Poland. The details of the micro-level sample are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Sample of micro-level interviews in Poland

No.	Code	Nationality	Gender	Age group	Place of interview**	Time of arrival***
1	PLMICH01	Russian/Chechen*	Female	27-50	C	Early arrival
2	PLMICH02	Russian/Chechen*	Female	27-50	C	Late arrival
3	PLMICH03	Russian/Chechen*	Female	27-50	C	Late arrival
4	PLMICH04	Russian/Chechen*	Female	27-50	C	Late arrival
5	PLMICH05	Russian/Chechen*	Female	27-50	P	Late arrival
6	PLMICH06	Russian/Chechen*	Female	27-50	P	Late arrival
7	PLMICH07	Russian/Chechen*	Female	27-50	C	Late arrival
8	PLMICH08	Russian/Chechen*	Female	27-50	C	Late arrival
9	PLMICH09	Russian/Chechen*	Male	>50	P	Late arrival
10	PLMICH10	Russian/Chechen*	Male	27-50	P	Early arrival
11	PLMICH11	Russian/Chechen*	Male	27-50	P	Early arrival
12	PLMICH12	Russian/Chechen*	Male	18-26	P	Late arrival
13	PLMICH13	Russian/Chechen*	Male	27-50	C	Late arrival
14	PLMICH14	Russian/Chechen*	Male	27-50	C	Late arrival
15	PLMICH15	Russian/Chechen*	Male	27-50	C	Late arrival
16	PLMIUk16	Georgian/ Ossetian	Male	27-50	C	Early arrival
17	PLMIUk17	Ukrainian	Male	18-26	P	Late arrival
18	PLMIUk18	Ukrainian	Male	27-50	C	Early arrival
19	PLMIUk19	Ukrainian	Female	27-50	C	Early arrival
20	PLMIUk20	Ukrainian	Female	27-50	C	Early arrival
21	PLMISy21	Syrian	Male	27-50	C	Early arrival
22	PLMISy22	Syrian	Male	18-26	C	Late arrival

23	PLMISy23	Syrian	Male	27-50	C	Late arrival
24	PLMISy24	Syrian	Male	>50	C	Late arrival
25	PLMISy25	Syrian	Female	18-26	C	Late arrival
26	PLMIr26	Iraqi	Male	27-50	P	Late arrival
27	PLMIr27	Iraqi	Male	27-50	P	Late arrival
28	PLMIr28	Iraqi	Female	>50	C	Early arrival
29	PLMIJe29	Yemeni	Male	27-50	P	Late arrival
30	PLMIKa30	Kazakh	Female	27-50	P	Late arrival
* 'Chechen' means a Russian citizen with Chechen nationality ** C – centre; P – periphery (small town or village outside the city) *** Early arrival – 2011-2014; Late arrival – 2015-2017						

Source: own elaboration by RESPOND team in Poland.

Two comments have to be made at this point. First, the concept of citizenship/nationality was particularly important in the case of the Chechen migrants who, even if they have Russian citizenship and/or lived in Russia, identify themselves as Chechens. This was reflected in the interviews. Second, the interviews were conducted in different languages, allowing the interviewees to feel comfortable. These were Polish, English, Arabic, and Russian. All interviews were translated, transcribed into English, and coded with NVivo software. Also, all micro-data were coded by the Polish team to the needs of the RESPOND Dataset for use in further work within the project.

According to the criteria applied in the RESPOND project, the 27-50 age group definitely dominated the sample. Respondents aged 30 to 39 years old comprised the main group (14 persons). The smallest group consisted of people aged 50 years and over (only 3 persons). In addition, the majority of the respondents (21 out of 30) belonged to the group of late arrivals to Poland (2015-2017) and only 9 could be assigned to the group of early arrivals (2011-2014) (Table 1). While analysing the legal refugee protection status of the respondents, referring to the categories developed by the RESPOND consortium and based on information provided during the interviews, the distribution was as follows (status and corresponding number of respondents): asylum seeker–13 persons, refugee status–4 persons, under subsidiary protection–11 persons, other–2 persons. Out of 30 respondents, 13 were under the asylum procedure and 15 had already received a positive decision—those granted subsidiary protection prevailed—followed by persons with refugee status in Poland. Two respondents did not declare their legal status in Poland.

For the meso-level interviews, the first step was to identify sampling criteria for Poland, keeping in mind the general guidelines developed in this field within the RESPOND consortium. National specificity was also considered. One of the key decisions at the very beginning was finding a common, practical definition of 'stakeholders', in other words 'actors', to be applied among the RESPOND team. For this project, 'stakeholders' are understood as actors with a meaningful institutionalised practice (at the social/economic or political level) in

relation to migration/integration (including border management, protection, and reception). In line with the project aims and objectives, the RESPOND team was particularly interested in local-level practices with the aim of understanding how policies are received and implemented at different localities, how different civic (social) actors fill in the gap where government policies have failed to deliver the needed services and how policymaking is influenced at various levels through diverse governance practices. In general, the following profiles for key informants and stakeholder interviews were deemed possible:

- those who deliver a service in the field of migration/integration (including border management, protection, and reception);
- those within relevant public administration areas (e.g., policy executors/implementers, meso-level administrators such as bureaucrats, governors or prefects, and the local chief of staff for policing);
- elected policymakers (only at the local level) and representatives of local governments;
- practitioners (e.g., immigration lawyers, school directors, teachers, medical staff, social workers);
- independent activists: human-rights activists (who deliver a service or produce collective action), cultural-brokers, representatives of NGOs and faith-based NGOs, immigrants and other relevant community organisations (Nagel, et al., 2018).

Poland's experience with admitting asylum seekers and granting international protection has been strictly determined by the dominant route chosen by the most common category of asylum seekers in Poland, namely foreigners with Russian citizenship. They are mainly from Chechnya or Dagestan and come to Poland from the territory of Belarus by the land-border crossing point in Brest/Terespol. Asylum applications are received by the Border Guard, which also conducts border control on Poland's land, air, and sea borders (Figure 1). The Border Guard also runs and supervises six detention centres for foreigners (located in Lesznowola, Kętrzyn, Białystok, Krosno Odrzańskie, Przemyśl, Biała Podlaska), where sometimes asylum seekers are placed (Figure 2 and Figure 1Figure 3). These competences implied the inclusion of the Border Guard in the sample. The Office for Foreigners, in turn, is responsible for processing the applications and delivering social assistance to asylum seekers. The OF also runs centres for foreigners who have submitted applications for international protection (Szulecka, et al., 2018a). At the beginning of 2019, the Office had 11 centres for foreigners, including four of its own centres in Podkowa Leśna-Dębak, Biała Podlaska, Czerwony Bór near Łomża, and Linin near Góra Kalwaria, and seven centres contracted with external entities through agreements concluded as part of public procurement procedures. In August 2019, one of the contracted centres (in Grotniki) was closed. The centres in Podkowa Leśna-Dębak (near the capital city of Warsaw) and in Biała Podlaska (30 kilometres from the Polish-Belarusian border and the border crossing point in Brest-Terespol) are reception centres from which asylum seekers are transferred to other centres, called residence or stay centres, in which they can decide to live during the asylum procedure (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 4). These centres are mostly located in two voivodships: Mazovian and Lubelskie (Figure 3).

Figure 1 Map of border crossings and Border Guard facilities in Poland

Source: (Polish Border Guard Headquarters, 2019).

Figure 2 Location of guarded (detention) centres for foreigners in Poland (*ośrodek rodzinny* – centre for families, *ośrodek męski* – centre for men, *małoletni bez opieki* – unaccompanied minors)

Source: (Association for Legal Intervention, 2019).

Figure 3 Location of centres for foreigners in Poland in early 2020 (including reception centres, residence centres and detentions centres)

Source: own elaboration by RESPOND team in Poland.

The final material from the meso-level interviews includes 16 interviews (all of which were transcribed into Polish and coded with NVivo software) carried out between July 2018 and March 2019 in Poland. The 16 meso-level interviews (two of which were double interviews involving two representatives of an institution/organisation) included experts from public administration at the central and local levels, NGOs, and other practitioners dealing with immigration issues. This sample is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Sample of meso-level interviews in Poland

No.	Code	Type of stakeholder
1.	PLMZBG1	Border Guard
2.	PLMZOF1	Office for Foreigners
3.	PLMZOF2	Office for Foreigners
4.	PLMZOF3/4	Office for Foreigners (two respondents)
5.	PLMZP1	Practitioner
6.	PLMZP2	Practitioner
7.	PLMZP3	Practitioner
8.	PLMZLG1	Local governor
9.	PLMZLG2	Local governor
10.	PLMZSO1	Social organisation
11.	PLMZSO2	Social organisation
12.	PLMZSO3	Social organisation
13.	PLMZSO4	Social organisation
14.	PLMZSO5/6	Social organisation (two respondents)

Source: own elaboration by RESPOND team in Poland.

In accordance with the policy of personal data management, anonymisation, and the code of ethics adopted by the Polish team, data on gender and specific interview locations are not disclosed.

As far as the geographical distribution of the micro- and meso-level interviews is concerned, taking into account the number of international protection beneficiaries as well as the concentration of assistance services and offices of relevant authorities, two voivodeships (provinces)¹⁰ (Mazovian and Lubelskie) were identified as the general locations for our interviews. The Mazovian voivodeship is the biggest among the 16 in Poland, and the capital city, Warsaw, is located within its administrative boundaries. Warsaw has the largest number of migrant residents of different categories and statuses in Poland.

To this end, it is important to mention that the first roundtable discussion of the RESPOND Migration Governance Network in Poland was held on 10 December 2018 at the Centre of Migration Research of the University of Warsaw. It was transcribed and coded manually (material codes: MGN1, MGN 2, MGN3). The meeting was attended by about 20 experts

¹⁰ According to the Central Statistical Office, on 1 January 2019, Poland was administratively divided into 16 voivodships (*województwo*), 380 poviats (*powiat*), and 2.477 communes (*gmina*). The largest voivodship was Mazovian, where the capital city, Warsaw, is located (Central Statistical Office, n.d.).

representing different institutions and organisations, including the Office of the Polish Commissioner for Human Rights, the Office for Foreigners, the Border Guard, governmental and local institutions involved in integrative programmes for persons granted refugee status or subsidiary protection, non-governmental and international organisations, local authorities, and academia. The second roundtable discussion was held on 16 January 2020 in Warsaw. Like the one before it, this discussion was also transcribed and coded manually (material codes from MGN2R1 to MGN2R18 where 'R' means 'Respondent' and it is followed by his/her ordinal number). The event was attended by more than 20 participants representing different state and non-state actors, especially those dealing with forced migrants during the asylum procedure in and outside the centres for foreigners.

In addition, the Polish team, including the authors of this report, participated as speakers, experts, or audience members in several thematic events (conferences, workshops, seminars, and debates) in Poland and abroad dedicated to migration issues. This allowed for numerous interaction and discussions with other experts in the field, as well as observations and access to additional materials.

The analysis conducted for the purpose of this report has a qualitative character and it was carried out with the assistance of the NVivo software. To conduct the analysis, the common-coding scheme for WP4 was used, making some country-specific revisions and additions. It began with the categories indicated in the WP4 guidelines and then focused on specific aspects of Poland, which are critical to an understanding of the country's reception regime. Then, some new categories and sub-categories were added to adapt the common coding scheme to the national conditions reflected in the collected interview material.

It is worth paying attention to the limitations pertaining to micro- and meso-level interviews and the MGN meetings that were identified by the RESPOND team. They are the following¹¹:

- Unfavourable political climate in Poland for studying forced migration in the European context, especially since the Law and Justice (PiS) party took power in 2015; and, as a result, the government's approach to the issue of migration through the prism of national security and socio-economic interests (important for meso-level interviews);
- Relatively small number of non-governmental (social) organisations working for migrants and refugees, the majority of which operate in Warsaw or in a few other big cities and towns in the vicinity of the reception and stay (residence) centres for foreigners. This sparked the fear of being easily identifiable among the NGOs (important for meso-level interviews);
- Very heavy workload for some NGOs and public institutions (Office for Foreigners and Border Guard), which caused difficulties in arranging an interview (some interview dates were delayed) or some failures to respond to our invitation (important for meso-level interviews);
- Approaching officials from the Office for Foreigners took more time than expected. Communication became effective after the Office's management helped facilitate the interviews by assigning responsible respondents to share their opinions regarding challenges in the asylum procedures and Dublin transfers. This enriched the data gathered through the interviews. The Office for Foreigners also assigned experts to participate in the MGN meetings. Their knowledge and comments about the asylum procedure and the reception system were very helpful (important for meso-level interviews);

¹¹ It has to be noted that this list is not exhaustive.

- The MGN meetings' participant list and the expert interviews lacked representatives from the Ministry of Interior and Administration, despite efforts to involve them. In fact, their opinions could have shed more light on the practices described by the Office for Foreigners and the Border Guard in the interviews and during the MGN meetings (important for meso-level interviews);
- Due to various factors, it was not possible to conduct several interviews with Border Guard representatives operating in various areas. Since at most 1-2 interviews could be conducted with Border Guard representatives, the research team decided that the interviews should be at the central level, rather than border-crossing points, where the law on border controls, asylum, and migration management is implemented. Two representatives responded to the first MGN meeting and interview invitation and in the end only one individual participated. The opinions shared by the Border Guard representative reflected the known stance of the Border Guard, seen in their responses to requests for intervention at the most common border-crossing point for asylum seekers in Poland (important for meso-level interviews);
- One of the problems encountered stemmed from restricted access to the centres for asylum seekers and reception centres in Poland. In order to get permission to enter and conduct research there, one needs to submit an official motion to the Head of the Office for Foreigners. To conduct micro-level interviews, the researchers from the Centre of Migration Research visited three centres for foreigners. Official approval was needed each time and processing the motions took about one week. In addition, the visit to one of them was delayed due to sanitary problems at the centre—also the reason for a previous rejection of entrance (important for micro-level interviews);
- The gender of the interviewer was relevant. In the case of migrants from Chechnya, male respondents were more reluctant to talk to female interviewers (important for micro-level interviews);
- Another challenge was recruiting asylum seekers willing to participate in the interviews. The researchers approached potential participants in the centres' common spaces, such as backyards, corridors, and kitchens. A majority of asylum seekers refused. Only in one centre were the residents given advanced notice by the manager about the researchers' visit and the possibility to talk about their experiences. Given the manager's facilitation and introduction of the project, it was easier to find respondents, and some individuals even approached the team (important for micro-level interviews);
- Another difficulty related to the interviews conducted in the Centres for Foreigners was the possibility of compromised anonymity due to the lack of privacy. A majority of the interviews was conducted in common rooms, which meant they were interrupted from time to time by people passing by, including centre employees. Therefore, the employees knew who had given interviews and could have passed this information on to their superiors. In addition, an employee in Targówek looked through the questionnaire after asking the researcher to show it to him (important for micro-level interviews);
- Finding respondents living outside the centres for foreigners (either asylum seekers or refugees) was particularly difficult. Without hiring gatekeepers (employees of Foundation Ocalenie, an NGO helping asylum seekers and refugees, and Warsaw Family Support Centre), it probably would not have been possible to find respondents from particular groups like Syrian refugees (speaking Arabic) or Chechen male refugees (who usually are not willing to talk openly about their private experiences, especially with unknown women). In order to find respondents from other groups (Chechen women and Ukrainian women

and men), researchers from the Centre of Migration Research used their professional contacts. Owing to the engagement of the gatekeepers, who encouraged the forced migrants to take part in the research and to give consent to contact them, the researchers were able to successfully conduct the interviews. However, some of the migrants refused to participate in the study in the end. There were also instances of constantly postponing the meeting date. Two interviews were conducted in two parts with more than a one-month intermission due to the interviewees' time constraints. This could have disturbed the atmosphere of the interview and the comfort of the respondents, although it did not seem to impact their answers (important for micro-level interviews);

- An additional significant limitation was related to over-exploitation of some micro- and meso-level respondents. For a majority of them, it was not the first interview they'd given for research purposes. They had talked about their experiences for the purposes of academic studies, NGOs' research, and/or journalists' investigations. Re-telling the stories of forced migrants brought back sad and often traumatic memories about their journey and reasons for why they fled their countries. Understandably, some cried at the reminder of their traumatic experiences, which made it difficult to move on with subsequent questions (important for micro- and meso-level interviews).

All research activities were conducted with full awareness of the ethical guidelines common to the RESPOND consortium and were implemented in line with the project's ethical principles. This is visible in the efforts to anonymise personal and sensitive data, among other decisions. Following the consortium requirements, an ethical application was submitted by the Polish team to its institutional ethical board at the Centre of Migration Research of the University of Warsaw and ethical clearance was granted for all components of fieldwork in Poland.

1. Legal Regulations and Policies of Reception: A Multi-level Perspective

In this section of the report we provide an overview of the legal and policy framework regarding the reception system in Poland at the turn of 2019 and 2020. The Polish reception policy is strongly connected with the area of asylum policy. In Poland, there is no separate legal definition of reception as such. The key legal act in this regard is the Law of 13 June 2003 on granting protection to foreigners within the territory of the Republic of Poland, called the Law on Protection¹². It provides the detailed provisions concerning the principles, conditions and procedure for granting protection to foreigners within the territory of the Republic of Poland and the authorities competent in these matters (Article 1). The Law on Protection also contains the stipulations regarding the assistance of foreigners applying for international protection and includes social assistance and medical care (Articles 70-86).

Below, after a general introduction of the national legal and institutional framework in the field of asylum, including reception conditions, we discuss the regulations and policy actions in particular areas, such as housing and allowances, healthcare (medical) services, early access to education, and early access to the labour market. When we elaborate on asylum policy, we also mean assistance (support) for applicants for international protection in Poland, in other words, what can be understood as reception conditions guaranteed by law. Obviously, many reception-related practices and actions have an informal nature and are provided by non-state actors willing to support asylum seekers¹³. These can be NGOs, informal groups, or individuals.

1.1. Background of the National Legal and Institutional Framework¹⁴

As of 2019, 30 years have passed since the beginning of Poland's systemic transformation that affected all dimensions of the state's functioning—political, social, and economic. At the same time, 2019 is the 15th anniversary of Poland's membership in the EU and 12th anniversary of joining the Schengen area. Undoubtedly, these three decades have had a major impact on Polish asylum policy and the context of European integration progress in the Central and Eastern Europe region particularly. The beginning of the 1990s meant the opening of Poland to intensified international migration and international cooperation.

The period of the Polish People's Republic (1952-1989) did not leave the country with solid foundations for national asylum policy. At that time, Poland did not participate in international and regional refugee protection systems as it was neither a party to the Geneva Convention nor part of the ongoing process of European integration in Western Europe and its structures (Florczak, 2003, p. 7). The legal framework of the refugee protection system in Poland gradually became the result of the implementation of international law, EU law, and national law. It was only in 1991 that Poland joined the Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees

¹² Ustawa z dnia 13 czerwca 2003 r. o udzielaniu cudzoziemcom ochrony na terytorium Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej (t.j. Dz.U. z 2019 r. poz. 1666 z późn. zm.).

¹³ For further information, see the section '2. Reception Practices' of this report.

¹⁴ This section was developed and updated if necessary, on the basis of the section '1. Background of the National Legal and Institutional Framework' from (Pachocka & Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

of 28 July 1951 adopted in Geneva¹⁵ and the Protocol on the Status of Refugees, declared in New York on 31 January 1967¹⁶, thereby acknowledging and adopting the *acquis* of international refugee law along with the consequences of its provisions. This was directly influenced by a turnover in 1990 when about a thousand people coming from Sweden to Poland (but not Swedish nationals) wanted to apply for international protection. At that time, Poland did not have adequate legal tools to handle such cases on its own as it was not party to the Geneva Convention (Klaus, 2017a, pp. 9-10) (Florczak, 2003, pp. 97-107) (Weinar, 2006, p. 79). In the following years, migrations, including forced ones, were becoming a regular rather than temporary phenomenon that required the development of permanent legal and institutional solutions. Therefore, international cooperation in this area was necessary to build an institutional framework and a legal regime from scratch (Florczak, 2003, p. 12).

Since late 1980, Poland has experienced some major turning points in the formulation and development of its asylum policy, including Poland's transition from a communist state in the Soviet bloc to a democratic state with a market economy, preparations for the EU accession in 2004 and joining the Schengen zone in 2007, subsequent EU membership, and finally, the migration and refugee crisis in Europe whose peak coincided with the presidential and parliamentary elections in Poland of 2015¹⁷.

Only the second decade of the 21st century contributed to the growing interest in refugee issues in Poland in public and political discourse and media narration. However, this did not result from key changes in the forced-migration situation in the country such as the increased number of people applying for international protection or significant reforms to the asylum system. This was particularly related to the changing migration landscape in Europe and its neighbourhood and the EU's response to these developments. The new decade also brought several serious terrorist attacks in EU Member States, including France (Paris in 2015 and Nice in 2016), Belgium (Brussels in 2016), Germany (Berlin in 2016) and the United Kingdom (London in 2017). At the same time, the inflow of Ukrainians to Poland grew due to the armed conflict in eastern Ukraine with Russian involvement and its unstable political and economic situation. The year 2015 was marked by an important political shift in Poland. As a result of the presidential and parliamentary elections, the Law and Justice party—considered right-wing, conservative and populist—came to power. The new government favoured (or even intentionally provoked) the politicisation of the issue of refugees in public media and strengthened its anti-immigration, anti-refugee, and even anti-European narrative. This, in turn, translated into growth of negative public attitudes towards receiving asylum seekers and refugees in Poland¹⁸. This coincidence of various external and internal factors has led to growing interest in issues concerning migration and state security in Poland. According to some opinions, it can be stated that the noticeable presence of the refugee topic in Polish media and political discourse in recent years was only to a small extent due to a real influx of people seeking protection to Poland (Klaus, 2017a, p. 7).

¹⁵ For further information, see (UN General Assembly, 1951).

¹⁶ For further information, see (UN General Assembly, 1967).

¹⁷ For further information about the key developments after 1989 in the field of immigration to Poland and Polish migration policy, see the section '2.1. A brief history of immigration and migration policy development' in (Szulecka, et al., 2018b).

¹⁸ For further information, see (Górak-Sosnowska & Pachocka, 2019), (Horolets, et al., 2019), (Klaus, 2017b), (Klaus, et al., 2018), (Legut & Pędzwiatr, 2018), (Mołęda-Zdziech, et al., 2020).

1.2. National Legal and Institutional Framework¹⁹

The legal framework in the field of asylum encompasses national, European, and international legislation. The fundamental, national legal act is the Constitution of the Republic of Poland (1997). It states only a general protection of rights and access to international protection (Article 56), indicating that the details are specified in the relevant laws. To be more precise, Paragraph 1 of Article 56 stipulates that: 'Foreigners shall have the right of asylum in the Republic of Poland in accordance with principles specified by statute' (in this provision asylum, in Polish 'azyl', is understood as a national form of protection), and is followed by Paragraph 2 stating that: 'Foreigners who seek protection from persecution in the Republic of Poland, may be granted the status of a refugee in accordance with international agreements to which the Republic of Poland is a party' (Article 56). The Constitution does not discuss the division of competences between ministries and the details of local governance, which means that the institutions involved in managing migration are not mentioned in this act. The execution of this right is regulated in the Law on Protection (Szulecka, et al., 2018b, pp. 29-30).

There are also other general provisions of the Constitution (1997) that are relevant for asylum (and migration) policy and for people of different legal statuses in Poland:

- Article 32: '1. All persons shall be equal before the law. All persons shall have the right to equal treatment by public authorities. 2. No one shall be discriminated against in political, social or economic life for any reason whatsoever'.
- Article 40: 'No one may be subjected to torture or cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment or punishment. The application of corporal punishment shall be prohibited'.
- Article 41. '1. Personal inviolability and security shall be ensured to everyone. Any deprivation or limitation of liberty may be imposed only in accordance with principles and under procedures specified by statute'.
- Article 47: 'Everyone shall have the right to legal protection of his private and family life, of his honour and good reputation and to make decisions about his personal life'.
- Article 68: '1. Everyone shall have the right to have his health protected. (...). 3. Public authorities shall ensure special health care to children, pregnant women, handicapped people and persons of advanced age'.
- Article 70: '1. Everyone shall have the right to education. Education to 18 years of age shall be compulsory. The manner of fulfilment of schooling obligations shall be specified by statute. 2. Education in public schools shall be without payment. Statutes may allow for payments for certain services provided by public institutions of higher education'.

The main legal acts regarding asylum policy and related issues (e.g., reception conditions and detention) in Poland are presented in Table 10²⁰ while the main implementing decrees, administrative guidelines, and regulations are indicated in Table 11²¹. From the point of view of the reception conditions, three legal acts are the most important: Law of 13 June 2003 on granting protection to foreigners within the territory of the Republic of Poland (consolidated text, Journal of Laws 2019, item 1666 with amendments), Ordinance of the Minister of Interior

¹⁹ This section was developed and updated if necessary, on the basis of the sections '1.1. Overview of the National Legal and Institutional Framework' and '1.2. Important Developments since 2011' from (Pachocka & Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

²⁰ See 'Appendices'.

²¹ See 'Appendices'.

and Administration of 19 February 2016 on the amount of assistance for foreigners seeking international protection (Journal of Laws 2016, item 311)²² and Ordinance of the Ministry of Interior of 23 October 2015 on the rules of stay in the centre for foreigners (Journal of Laws 2015, item 1828)²³.

Due to membership in the European Union, Poland participates in the Common European Asylum System (CEAS). Therefore, as an EU Member State, Poland is obliged to transpose directives and other CEAS measures into national legislation. Those regarding the asylum and reception are presented in Table 12²⁴.

In addition, as indicated by the Office for Foreigners (n.d.), Poland is legally bound by the following international legal acts regarding migration and asylum (in chronological order of documents):

- Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, 4 November 1950, Rome,
- Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees, 28 July 1951, Geneva,
- European Agreement on the Abolition of Visas for Refugees, 3 September 1960, Strasbourg,
- Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees, 31 January 1967, New York,
- European Agreement on Transfer of Responsibility for Refugees, 16 October 1980, Strasbourg,
- Protocol No. 7 to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, 22 November 1984, Strasbourg,
- Convention on the Rights of the Child, 20 November 1989, New York,
- Agreement between the Swiss Confederation and the Republic of Austria regarding the establishment and functioning of the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD), 1 June 1993, Vienna,
- Agreement between the Minister of the Interior and Administration of the Republic of Poland and the International Organization for Migration on cooperation in the field of voluntary returns of foreigners leaving the territory of the Republic of Poland, 12 July 2005, Warsaw.

'Since 2015, new intensive debates about possible solutions to the so-called "refugee crisis" have prompted Polish policymakers to introduce reforms to both international protection and immigration law' and 'the direction of changes in law reflects the emphasis placed on internal state security, whereas the practice observed since late 2015 raises concerns about respect for human rights, particularly in cases of arbitrarily denied or restricted access to the asylum procedure and pushback of potential applicants' (Szulecka, et al., 2018b, pp. 65-66). In 2017, a proposal for amending the Law on Protection was announced and followed by its revised version in 2019. The proposed amendment concerned, among others, the introduction of a border procedure and lists of safe countries and safe third countries. The planned changes were criticised by many NGOs in Poland. In recent years, however, it was

²² Rozporządzenie Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych i Administracji z dnia 19 lutego 2016 r. w sprawie wysokości pomocy dla cudzoziemców ubiegających się o udzielenie ochrony międzynarodowej (Dz.U. 2016 poz. 311).

²³ Rozporządzenie Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych z dnia 23 października 2015 r. w sprawie regulaminu pobytu w ośrodku dla cudzoziemców (Dz. U. 2015 poz. 1828).

²⁴ See 'Appendices'.

rather the implementation of the law, government policy, and unofficial practices (e.g., of the Border Guard) that raised more doubts than the changes in the law and planned amendments.

'The year 2015 was of key importance to migration management as well as the development and implementation of migration policy in Poland – not so much due to the migration crisis in Europe, which was not directly experienced in Poland, but rather due to the electoral victory of PiS. The newly established government withdrew from the participation in the temporary relocation scheme, annulled the strategic document adopted by the Council of Ministers in 2012 "Polish Migration Policy – Current State of Play and Proposed Actions" and, at the same time, engaged in closer cooperation with Hungary, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia within the Visegrád Group in order to develop and present a joint stance on the European policy on migration, asylum, and borders (this mainly concerned the objection to the relocation mechanism)' (Pachocka & Szczerba-Zawada, 2019, pp. 80-81). Despite previous announcements, the government had not adopted a new strategic migration policy document. However, 'in June 2019 a draft document titled "Poland's Migration Policy" was made public. but has not been officially published on government websites. This document was heavily criticised by representatives of various communities, including academia (commented in public by both individual researchers and bodies such as the Committee on Migration Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences – KBnM PAN) and non-governmental organisations (e.g. the Association for Legal Intervention – (SIP) and the Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights – HFHR). In its position, KBnM PAN recommended that the draft should be rejected altogether and works started from scratch, pointing out that the published version of the document had not been subjected to open and transparent public consultations with key stakeholders and experts in migration, scientists, representatives of non-governmental organisations and local governments, and that its content had not been based on scientific evidence thus leading to numerous errors and perpetuation of stereotypes and prejudices. The document is focused on the prospect of Poland being endangered by migration and the need to shift the future migration policy towards a broadly understood security, with migrants being instrumentally regarded as foreign labour force. In the opinion of the HFHR, some passages of the document raised concerns as to their compliance with the EU law and international law. What is more, the proposed approach, which the Foundation found to have a xenophobic tone, may result in the violation of fundamental freedoms and human rights' (Pachocka & Szczerba-Zawada, 2019, p. 81). In autumn 2019, the Law and Justice party again won the parliamentary elections. As of the beginning of 2020, the government had not proposed a new strategy in the area of migration.

Important developments in migration and asylum law and policy (including institutional aspects) in Poland since 2011 are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3 Development of migration and asylum laws and policies – overview

Year	Introduction of laws/changes in the law	Institutional and political changes
2011	Amendment to the Law on Protection, including, among others, the possibility of relocation and resettlement of foreigners to Poland; modification of conditions for providing social assistance and medical aid to asylum applicants and providing assistance in voluntary returns; specification of the conditions of apprehension and detention of asylum seekers (Journal of Laws of 2011 no 191, item 1133)	
2012	Introduction of Law on Regularisation of Stay of Particular Foreigners on the Territory of Poland (Journal of Laws of 2011 no 191, item 1133) (passed in 2011, lasted for the first half of 2012) including provisions on the possibility of obtaining a residence permit by failed asylum seekers (who received negative decisions and were ordered to leave before Jan. 1 st , 2010 yet were staying irregularly in Poland) or asylum seekers having applied for international protection several times (being in the course of a subsequent procedure after Jan. 1 st , 2010)	Polish government's acceptance of a strategic document on migration policy ('Polish migration policy—the current state and recommended activities')
2014	Introduction of the new Law on Foreigners of 2013 (Journal of Laws of 2013, item 1650), implementing, among others, the EU directive on single permits, prolonging the maximum period of stay in the territory of Poland based on the temporary residence permit from 2 to 3 years, introducing a permit for stay due to humanitarian reasons and modifying the permit for tolerated stay	Acceptance by the Polish government of the plan of implementation of the strategic document on migration policy accepted in 2012
2014	Introduction of an amendment to the Law on Protection, implementing the Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection and for the content of the protection granted (recast)	
2015	Introduction of amendments to the Law on Protection, including, among others, provisions on the relocation to Poland of persons with international protection granted by other EU countries and the introduction of provisions of	A decision on relocation to Poland of asylum seekers from other countries, withdrawn after the change of government in October 2015

	access to free of charge, legal aid for asylum seekers	
2016	An introduction to an amendment to the Law on Protection including reference to issues linked to state security in the context of the relocation of foreigners	Annulment of the strategic document on migration policy accepted in 2012; the beginning of work on new migration policies responding to changed migration challenges Declaration of Visegrad countries (V4) on the establishment of 'Migratory Crisis Mechanisms' for the coordination of assistance to asylum seekers in regions of origin and improvement of information exchange
2017	Announcement of a proposal for amending the Law on Protection, including the introduction of border procedures, lists of safe countries of origin and safe third countries and a change of the appeal body in asylum procedures	Establishment of Migration Crisis Response Mechanism by V4 countries; initiative aimed at providing support for EU countries experiencing the highest inflow of asylum seekers, addressing root causes in regions of origin and the improvement of information exchange between different countries and institutions
2018	Introduction of an amendment to the Law on Protection and the Law on Foreigners linked to the reform of laws on entrepreneurship and the implementation of EU directives on mobility in the framework of an intra-corporate transfer	
2019	Announcement of a revised proposal for amending the Law on Protection, including the introduction of border procedure, lists of safe countries of origin and safe third countries	A new draft document on 'Poland's Migration Policy' is made public (but not officially published on government websites) and heavily criticised by numerous experts and institutional stakeholders in Poland

Source: (Szulecka, et al., 2018b, pp. 34-37), shortened and updated.

Table 4 indicates the key public authorities involved in migration and asylum governance in Poland. In addition to the above-mentioned actors, other actors involved in the asylum procedure in practice by providing different forms of assistance to migrants during the procedure also play an important role, including international organisations (e.g., UNHCR), NGOs (e.g., providing legal and psychological support or other support in the centres for foreigners such as childcare, language teaching, housing, etc.) and numerous local actors (e.g., neighbours, communities, school teachers, etc.).

Table 4 List of public authorities involved in the migration and asylum governance

Authority (English name and abbreviation, <i>Polish name and abbreviation</i>)	Government level (national, regional, local)	Type of organisation	Area of competence in the fields of migration and asylum
Ministry of the Interior and Administration (MIA) <i>Ministerstwo Spraw Wewnętrznych i Administracji (MSWiA)</i>	National (implementation of laws at the level of the governmental administration in regions—voivodeships)	Government	Supervision of the Border Guard; elaboration of migration policies; proposing laws linked to migration and asylum; supervising voivodeship department offices in the issuance of residence permits and work permits; issuing return orders in specific cases involving a threat to national security due to terrorism and espionage activities
Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA) <i>Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych (MSZ)</i>	National	Government	Elaboration and implementation of visa policies; supervision of Polish consulates
Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Policy (MFLSP) <i>Ministerstwo Rodziny, Pracy i Polityki Społecznej (MRPiPS)</i>	National (implementation of laws at the local level)	Government	Elaboration and implementation of policies concerning the integration of foreigners, social assistance and employment of foreigners; supervision of regional and local labour offices responsible for issuing short-term permits for foreigners to work; coordinating the work of local family-support centres and local centres of social assistance
Office for Foreigners (OF) <i>Urząd do Spraw Cudzoziemców (UdSC)</i>	National with local branches	Governmental administration	Processing applications for international protection in the first instance; processing appeals to decisions on residence permits in the second instance; coordinating social assistance for asylum seekers; processing appeals to decisions on return issued by the Border Guard; processing appeals of decisions on refusals to grant permits for stay due to humanitarian reasons and permits for tolerated stay issued by the Border Guard; running four centres for foreigners

Refugee Board (RF) <i>Rada do spraw Uchodźców (RdsU)</i>	National	Public administration	Processing appeals to decisions on granting international protection in the second instance
Straż Graniczna (SG) <i>Border Guard (BG)</i>	National with regional and local units	Public administration	Protection of state border; border control; control of legality of stay and employment of foreigners; receiving applications for international protection; running detention centres for foreigners; issuing return orders and (if applicable) permits for stay due to humanitarian reasons and permits for tolerated stay

Source: based on (Szulecka, et al., 2018b, pp. 70-71), updated.

The most important state actor with respect to reception is the Office for Foreigners (supervised by the Ministry of Interior and Administration) and, in particular, its Department for Social Assistance (DSA). One of the DSA's main statutory tasks is to coordinate and organise the everyday work of the centres for foreigners who are applying for international protection in Poland (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 3).

As indicated in the organisational regulation of the Office for Foreigners, the scope of activities of the DSA includes, among other things (Szef Urzędu do Spraw Cudzoziemców, 2018):

- providing assistance to: a) foreigners applying for international protection, b) foreigners who withdraw their application for international protection, c) unaccompanied minor foreigners applying for international protection or asylum and placed in foster care exercised in a form other than a care and educational institution, d) foreigners benefiting from temporary protection;
- coordinating the performance of tasks by the Office's organisational units regarding the use of temporary protection by foreigners;
- ensuring the operation of centres for foreigners applying for international protection;
- supervision of the work of security staff in centres belonging to the Office;
- maintenance of proper operation of electronic systems supporting physical security in centres belonging to the Office;
- organisation of funerals in the event of the death of a foreigner who had applied for international protection or reimbursement of funeral expenses to a person who has incurred the funeral costs of such a foreigner;
- cooperation with government and self-government administration bodies and non-governmental organisations in the field of social assistance provided to foreigners;
- providing support to foreigners regarding proceedings for granting international protection and providing information on social assistance;
- cooperation with the competent authorities to ensure safety and order in centres for foreigners;
- performing tasks related to the management of real estate belonging to the Office in the area of operating centres for foreigners;
- performing tasks related to the management of the Office's movable property in the area of operating centres for foreigners;

- providing access to data processed in the national set of registers, records and lists in matters regarding foreigners and in other registers kept by the Head of the Office in matters related to the implementation of the school obligation for minor foreigners and cooperation with educational institutions;
- providing access to data collected in documentation created or processed in matters regarding foreigners led by the Department for Social Assistance;
- keeping the national set of registers, records, and lists in matters regarding foreigners in areas falling within the competences of the Department for Social Assistance.

1.3. Housing and Allowances

Housing or shelter is an important basic need that anyone claiming asylum must be provided with or obtain individually. The quality of the housing or shelter has a crucial influence on the pace of the process of adaptation of foreigners to the new socio-cultural conditions of the host country, as well as on the mental condition of an individual seeking asylum or entire families escaping wars or various types of persecution in their home countries. This section of the report begins with a description of major legislative and policy documents on housing and allowances for people seeking asylum and then provides some statistical information on the provision of accommodation for such persons in existing centres for foreigners in Poland, as well as outside of them.

Article 16(1) of the Law of 12 December 2013 on foreigners (called the Law on Foreigners)²⁵ specifies some key competences of the Head of the Office for Foreigners regarding foreigners seeking international protection, which include granting refugee status, granting subsidiary protection, granting a permit for stay due to humanitarian reasons and a permit for tolerated stay, granting asylum, or granting temporary protection. Detailed provisions concerning people seeking protection, including the reception conditions, can be found in other acts. Among them, the Law on Protection is particularly important. Articles 70 to 86 of this law lay out the elements of assistance that foreigners applying for international protection in Poland are entitled to, including the provision of housing. Following the provisions of Article 71, the Department for Social Assistance (DSA) of the Office for Foreigners in the guidebook on its scope of activities explains that foreigners staying in centres for foreigners are entitled to (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, pp. 4-5):

- accommodation,
- all-day group meals in accordance with the cultural standards of foreigners,
- permanent financial assistance in the form of 'pocket money';
- permanent financial aid for the purchase of personal hygiene products;
- one-time cash assistance for the purchase of clothing and footwear;
- financing of transfers for the following purposes: taking part in the proceedings for international protection, presenting oneself for medical examinations or protective vaccinations, in other justified cases;
- learning the Polish language and basic materials necessary for learning;
- providing foreign minors with access to public schools and covering costs resulting from the tuition, including providing teaching aids, i.e., school supplies or vouchers for their purchase, as well as textbooks for those students who do not receive them at school;

²⁵ Ustawa z dnia 12 grudnia 2013 r. o cudzoziemcach (t.j. Dz.U. z 2018 r. poz. 2094 z późn. zm.).

- providing a cash equivalent in exchange for meals in the centre (this applies to children under 6 years of age and students of primary and lower secondary schools);
- providing preschool children with the opportunity to participate in educational and adaptive activities that take place in all centres for foreigners;
- covering, to the extent possible, the costs of extracurricular and recreational and sports activities for children’.

Importantly, the Law on Protection specifies in Article 71 that a foreigner shall be granted a financial benefit to cover his/her cost of stay in Poland outside the centre for foreigners (excluding the cost of medical care) when it is required by organisational aspects or it is necessary to: 1) ensure the foreigner’s safety (including the special situation of single women), 2) protect the public order; 3) protect and maintain family ties, 4) prepare the foreigner to live independently outside the centres for foreigners after receiving refugee status or subsidiary protection (Law on Protection).

As one of our informants from an NGO pointed out, the requirements to justify staying outside the centre are not followed:

Today, no longer do these conditions need to be fulfilled. Fifteen years ago, it was obligatory to provide medical or security arguments (PLMZSO1)²⁶.

The same respondent explained that:

There was no encouragement and there were these [aforementioned] conditions to be met. I don't remember when ... but surely a few years ago it started to change so now it was only on paper, but nobody looks at it. I don't even know if it is formulated in the regulations now. But in practice, it works in such a way that everyone who submits an application to obtain housing benefit gets it. It is a matter of time, if you submit it before the 20th day of a given month, you can leave the centre and move out from it in the following month. If it is submitted after the 20th, one needs to wait a bit longer. But I understand that these are organisational issues and if the situation is urgent and you get in touch and ask for an exception, it usually works and practically overnight people can sometimes move from the centres (PLMZSO1).

One of the reasons to allow people seeking asylum to live outside the centres for foreigners, and hence the growing popularity of this type of accommodation in the last decade, was revealed by another NGO expert. This respondent mentioned a discussion with one of the employees of the Office for Foreigners, who had said that:

[Paying housing benefits] is a very attractive offer for the state because it costs the state much less. Maintenance of the centre for foreigners costs the state much more, so the state administration would like to have even more people living outside the centres. (...) This is a good option as long as people seeking asylum are also provided with some additional integration instruments (PLMZSO3).

²⁶ In quotes from micro-level interviews, the ‘R’ is the ‘Respondent’ and ‘I’ the ‘Interviewer’. Abbreviations made by the authors of this report in quotations are marked with the symbol ‘(...)’. The information in square brackets ‘[...]’ introduced by the authors means editorial notes intended to facilitate readers’ understanding of the respondents’ statements.

As we are going to show below, based on the most recent statistical data, the option of living outside a centre for foreigners is today the most popular form of housing among those seeking international protection in Poland. The Law on Protection stipulates that accommodation (along with material assistance and medical care) is provided to all asylum seekers during the entire period of the procedure and up to two months after the final decision on their case or until the fulfilment of the obligation to leave Poland (if it occurs earlier than within 2 months)²⁷. If, however, an application is discontinued, assistance is offered for up to 14 days after that decision becomes final. If applicants receive a final negative decision after the appeal procedure (second-instance decision issued by the Refugee Board), they must leave the territory of Poland within 30 days, so they should not need to take advantage of social assistance for more than 30 days. At this stage, the foreigner may appeal against a second-instance decision to the administrative court²⁸. One of the major requirements to be fulfilled by asylum seekers so they could benefit from this assistance is registration at one of the reception centres within two days of submitting the application for international protection (Article 74(1)(1) in conjunction with Article 77 of the Law on Protection). If they do not get to the centres within 48 hours from the moment of filling in the application for international protection, their asylum proceedings are discontinued. As Szulecka, Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc (2018b, p. 42) aptly point out, nonappearance at a reception centre usually stems from the fact that asylum seekers, who are often assisted by members of their families already living in Western European countries, try to travel across Poland to get to other countries where they also apply for international protection.

The Law on Protection and some other more detailed legal acts, in particular the Ordinance of the Minister of Interior and Administration of 19 February 2016 on the amount of assistance for foreigners seeking international protection (Journal of Laws 2016, item 311) and Ordinance of the Ministry of Interior of 23 October 2015 on the rules of stay in the centre for foreigners (Journal of Laws 2015, item 1828), describe in greater details the elements of material assistance to be provided to those seeking international protection, including the provision of housing.

The reception system for asylum applicants is coordinated by the Office for Foreigners, with its head office in Warsaw and branch office in Białą Podlaska, 30 kilometres from the border with Belarus and the border-crossing point with Belarus in Brest-Terespol. The Office is responsible for providing social assistance, including housing, to people seeking international protection. Figure 4 presents the scope and types of social assistance provided by the Office for Foreigners to people seeking international protection in Poland.

As mentioned earlier, foreigners who are seeking international protection are traditionally provided with accommodation in one of the centres for foreigners run by the Office for Foreigners. If they opt-out of the accommodation in the centres managed by the Office, they are granted a financial allowance for accommodation outside the centres. According to the

²⁷ For further details regarding detailed legal provisions, see Article 74(3) of the Law on Protection.

²⁸ Since 2016 the courts have mostly refused to suspend the enforcement of a negative decision on an international protection application for the duration of the applicant's appeal process. Since the negative decision on their application ends the social benefits to which applicants had been entitled while awaiting a decision, those asylum seekers appealing a negative decision are left without support. However, some asylum seekers have reported good practices on the part of the centres, which have allowed them to continue staying there despite no longer being entitled to assistance (Szulecka, et al., 2018b, p. 42) (Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights (HFHR), 2019, pp. 40-41).

guidebook on social assistance published by the Office, this assistance ‘may be provided in the form of a cash payment to cover the costs of stay of foreigners on the territory of the Republic of Poland, if the organisational point of view so requires or if it is necessary for (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 5):

- providing the foreigner with security, with particular emphasis on the situation of single women;
- protection of public order;
- protection and maintenance of family ties;
- preparing a foreigner to lead an independent life outside the centre, after receiving a decision on granting refugee status or a decision on refusal to grant refugee status, in which subsidiary protection was granted.

Figure 4 Social assistance provided by the Office for Foreigners to persons seeking international protection in Poland

Source: (Office for Foreigners, n.d.).

Foreigners eligible for this cash payment receive assistance in the amount specified in the Ordinance of the Minister of the Interior of 19 February 2016 on the amount of assistance for foreigners applying for international protection. The amount of assistance depends on the number of family members in line with information provided in Table 5, that is, from 25 PLN daily amount per person for singles to 12.50 PLN per person for the fourth and next member of the given family (Ordinance of the Minister of Interior and Administration of 19 February 2016, Par. 6(1) and (2)). This level of financial support to asylum seekers living outside the centres has remained unchanged for over 15 years in spite of the growing cost of living. These payments are supposed to be sufficient to cover all living expenses of a foreigner in Poland, including housing and food. In addition, what is important in this context is that people seeking asylum are not allowed to work in Poland in the first six months of the examination of their applications for international protection. The additional allowance that those living outside the centres can receive is the one for school utensils and didactic materials for children (Chrzanowska & Czerniejewska, 2015, p. 7) as well as, help in learning the Polish language and basic educational materials, financial assistance to cover the costs of extra-curricular activities and recreational and sports activities for children; to cover the cost of public transport in order to participate in the procedure for granting international protection, to undergo medical treatment or protective vaccinations, or in other particularly justified cases (Law on Protection, Article 71(4)).

The asylum seekers during the procedure are not eligible for any social benefits available for citizens, including the child benefit called '500+', introduced by the Polish government in 2015²⁹. It means that, in light of the law, all the needs of the asylum seeker are to be met by the Office for Foreigners. However, as we show below, everyday practice significantly differs from these legal provisions.

Table 5 Allowances for asylum seekers living outside the centres for foreigners

Number of people in a family	Daily amount per person	Monthly amount per person
1 person	25 PLN (around 6.25 EUR)	750 PLN (ok. 187.5 EUR)
2 people	20 PLN (around 5 EUR)	600 PLN (ok. 150 EUR)
3 people	15 PLN (around 3.75 EUR)	450 PLN (ok. 112.5 EUR)
4 people	12.50 PLN (around 3 EUR)	375 PLN (ok. 93.75 EUR)

Source: (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 6).

According to the latest statistical data published by the Office for Foreigners at the end of June 2019, there were 2,963 foreigners whose proceedings for international protection had been initiated and who were looked after by the Office. Of them, 44% lived in one of 11 centres for foreigners and the remaining 56% were being paid cash benefits to cover the cost of living outside the centres supervised by the Office. Of the foreigners entitled to receive social assistance from the Office for Foreigners, 62% were Russian citizens, 18% came from Ukraine and 5% from Tajikistan (to mention only the largest groups). As shown in Table 6, there has been a constant flow of people who arrive at the centres and then leave them during the month of June. At the same time, the number of people accommodated in the centres in June 2019 remained relatively stable at around 1,300 people. It means that there were on average 118 people accommodated in each centre (Office for Foreigners, 2019a).

Table 6 Foreigners in the case of whom proceedings for international protection have been initiated and who are entitled to accommodation in the centres for foreigners or who are being paid cash allowance to live outside the centres

Time frame	27.05-02.06.2019	03-09.06.2019	10-16.06.2019	17-23.06.2019	24-30.06.2019
Foreigners					
In the centres	1 306	1 299	1 283	1 283	1 295
Outside the centres	1 663	1 664	1 661	1 667	1 666
Who left the centres	35	55	52	50	13
Newly arrived at the centres	68	47	33	51	32
Minors without parents in the centres	2	2	2	2	2
Total	2 971	2 965	2 946	2 952	2 963

Source: own elaboration by RESPOND team in Poland based on (Office for Foreigners, 2019a).

In past years, the Office for Foreigners was looking after a higher number of people seeking asylum. For example, two years earlier, in June 2017, the Head of the Office for Foreigners

²⁹ '500+' is a government programme introduced in 2016 under which parents received 500 PLN a month for each child after the first, and since 2019, they receive the benefit for every child, regardless of income.

had an average of 3,920 people under his protection. The number of people seeking asylum who were looked after by the Office decreased from an average of 4,200 at the beginning of 2017 to 3,900 in mid-2017. This number further decreased to an average of 3,376 people under Office protection in January 2018. At the same time, one may observe a slight increase in the number of foreigners who decide to stay outside of the centres for foreigners. In June 2017, on average 55% of the beneficiaries were arranging their housing independently of the Office for Foreigners (Office for Foreigners, 2019a).

As far as accommodation in the centres for foreigners is concerned, all of them are open-type facilities, so foreigners are free to leave them any time. However, while staying in the centres, foreigners have to follow some rules specified in Ordinance of the Ministry of Interior of 23 October 2015 on the rules of stay in the centre for foreigners. They are obliged to, among others, show particular care for the safety of minor children remaining under their care, respect quiet hours from 10.00 p.m. to 6.00 a.m., return to the centre before 11.00 p.m., possess and present at the request of the Office's employee or a security guard of the centre, a temporary certificate of identity of a foreigner and a resident ID, and leave a resident ID to the centre's security guard each time he/she leaves the centre³⁰ (Par. 12). In addition, foreigners are not allowed to (Par. 13):

- possess weapons or ammunition, as well as explosives or other items whose use may threaten the order in the centre;
- possess or use narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances or substitute drugs;
- own or consume alcoholic beverages;
- disturb the order in the centre, in particular by shouting, noise, alarm or other behaviour that disturbs quiet, order, rest or causes scandal at the centre (is inappropriate);
- invite unauthorised persons to stay for the night;
- arbitrarily move the equipment of the residential premises of the centre;
- use additional heating devices that are not the centre's equipment;
- take meals from the canteen;
- record conversations or photograph or film foreigners staying at the centre without their consent;
- destroy the property of the centre and the property of other foreigners staying in the centre;
- conduct business for profit;
- use the premises of the centre not in accordance with its intended use;
- smoke tobacco products outside designated areas.

The residents are accommodated in double, four and multi-person rooms depending on the situation of a particular person or family. In 2019, the Office ran 11 centres for foreigners, including four centres that belonged to the Office and seven were leased. With the exception of the centre in Czerwony Bór, where foreigners receive a per diem instead of prepared

³⁰ To this end, the Office for Foreigners in its guidebook 'First steps in Poland' informs foreigners applying for international protection that: 'You are thus allowed to leave the facility between 6:00 a.m. and 11:00 p.m. You need to be back at the facility before 11:00 p.m. In case of leaving the facility for more than two days, you will be crossed off the list of facility residents and you will lose the social benefits and medical care. If, after this lapse of time, you request to return to the facility, you will not be admitted but referred to the refugee facility in Dębak in Podkowa Leśna where you will have to submit an application for resumed social assistance' (Office for Foreigners, 2015, p. 29).

meals³¹, in the other centres, a full-board canteen is offered to asylum seekers. Apart from meals, in all the centres the foreigners are provided with so-called 'pocket money' (50 PLN per month)³², financial aid for the purchase of personal hygiene products (20 PLN per month), one-time cash assistance for the purchase of clothing and footwear (140 PLN), and financial aid to cover the cost of transportation for strictly specified purposes (taking part in proceedings for international protection; presenting oneself for medical examinations or protective vaccinations; other justified cases). The centres also offer the possibility to learn Polish and basic materials necessary for learning, access of foreign minors to public schools and covering the costs of tuition (providing teaching aids, i.e., school supplies or vouchers for their purchase, as well as textbooks for students who do not receive them at school) and a cash equivalent for meals (this applies to children under 6 years of age and students of primary and lower secondary schools); the possibility for preschool children to participate in educational and adaptive activities, which take place in all centres for foreigners; and the possibility of having the costs of extracurricular and recreational and sports activities for children covered (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, pp. 4-5) and Ordinance of the Minister of Interior and Administration of 19 February 2016 on the amount of assistance for foreigners seeking international protection, Par. 2.1 – 6.1).

All residents of the centres are obliged to comply with the legal norms in force on the territory of the Republic of Poland and the regulations on their stay at the centres for foreigners—implemented by way of the aforementioned Ordinance of the Minister of the Interior of 23 October 2015. At the same time, the Office for Foreigners claims to pay a lot of attention to the issue of respect for the religious and cultural identity of people applying for international protection, and—in cooperation with other bodies—to try to ensure security and compliance with public order at the centres and in their immediate vicinity (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 5).

The state-owned centres are located in Podkowa Leśna-Dębak, Biała Podlaska, Czerwonny Bór near Łomża, and Linin. The remaining six facilities are leased from external entities on the basis of agreements concluded as part of public procurement procedures³³. They are located in Białystok, Warszawa-Targówek, Kolonia Horbów, Bezwola, Łuków, and Grupa near Grudziądz. Apart from the aforementioned centres, the Office runs Foreigner Service Centres (mostly for persons using services outside the centres for foreigners) at the main Office on Taborowa Street in Warsaw and on Lubomelska Street in Lublin (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 4).

As one may see on Figure 3, almost all the centres are located in the eastern part of Poland. Six centres are located very close to the Polish eastern border, either in Lublin Voivodeship (in Biała Podlaska, Bezwola, Kolonia Horbów, and Łuków) or in the Podlaskie Voivodeship (in Białystok or Czerowny Bór). Three centres are situated in Masovian Voivodeship, either in the capital city (Warszawa-Targówek) or in the relative vicinity of Warsaw (Linin and Podkowa

³¹ This equivalent is provided to children up to the age of six and elementary school students or students of lower secondary schools, in accordance with the provisions of the Law on Protection.

³² If a foreigner performs cleaning works in the centre for foreigners, translations facilitating communication between the centre's employees and foreigners, or conducts cultural and educational classes for other foreigners staying in the centre, the amount of his/her pocket money may increase to 100 PLN (Ordinance of the Minister of Interior and Administration of 19 February 2016 on the amount of assistance for foreigners seeking international protection (Journal of Laws 2016, item 311), Par. 4.2).

³³ For further details concerning addresses and contact information, see (Office for Foreigners, n.d.).

Leśna-Dębak). One centre is located Kuyavian-Pomeranian Voivodeship (Grupa). Out of the 10 centres run by the Office in early 2020 only two were located in big cities over 250,000 inhabitants (Warszawa-Targówek and Białystok) whereas the majority were located in small cities (e.g., Biała Podlaska) or rural areas.

The centres in Biała Podlaska, 30 kilometres from the border-crossing point in Brest-Terespol, and in Podkowa Leśna-Dębak, in the suburbs of the capital city of Warsaw, perform the functions of reception centres. In other words, they serve as the first contact places where asylum seekers are accommodated and registered before they are moved to other centres for foreigners in different parts of Poland. The reception centre in Biała Podlaska is for first-time asylum applicants, whereas the centre in Podkowa Leśna-Debak serves mostly as a reception centre for asylum seekers transferred to Poland within the framework of the Dublin III Regulation. As one of the employees of the Office (PLMZOF3/4) informed us during the interview, the location of these reception centres is closely linked to how the migrants applying for international protection in Poland arrive in the country, with most usually arriving in Poland from Belarus or Ukraine, and other migrants transferred back to Poland (in line with the Dublin III Regulation), usually from Western European countries. Asylum seekers can request to be transferred to a particular centre, for example, to reunite with some members of the family or join friends and such requests are usually accepted. Also, those centres located in either bigger or smaller cities tend to be more popular than those in rural areas.

As one may read in the latest Office for Foreigners brochures, the Office pays special attention in the tender procedures to criteria aimed at increasing the standard of the stay of foreigners in leased facilities. In 2019, criteria for the evaluation of offers in the tender proceedings were the following: 35% price, 20% housing conditions, 5% additional housing conditions, 10% distance from the reception centre in Biała Podlaska, 5% location of the facility (administrative location and unemployment rate), 5% flexibility of accommodation (the possibility of increasing it), and 20% the contractor's experience in running a centre for foreigners applying for some form of protection on the territory of the Republic of Poland. The criterion of housing conditions has been supplemented with a number of elements that all facilities must meet (including dayrooms for women and men, kindergarten, room for maintaining religious practices, recreation areas, classrooms, meeting rooms, the right number of refrigerators, washing machines and vacuum cleaners for use by foreigners) and elements receiving extra scores (including facilities for the disabled, bathrooms in rooms, good condition of the building's facade, additional equipment on the playground, equipping recreational areas with equipment allowing for team sports) (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 4).

In the past, the main and almost only criterion considered during the decision process on the choice of a new centre for foreigners was the price. So, this has significantly changed and today even members of social organisations acknowledge the improvement in the conditions in which asylum seekers live. One of our interviewees from the NGO sector observed, for example:

In recent years, the Office for Foreigners has introduced a lot of good changes in terms of conditions in the centres for foreigners. They were so filthy, dirty and unpleasant some years ago that now I see significant progress here (PLMZSO1).

Another NGO expert in the same spirit pointed out that:

In 2016, the quality of the rooms in the centres, their equipment and security were very bad. It is much better now (PLMZSO2).

At the same time, our interviewee argued that:

The very philosophy of running the centres for foreigners continues to be imperfect. The main criterion of their choice is still the price and there are very limited activities for the inhabitants of the centres (PLMZSO2).

The same meso-level respondent observed also that the quality of housing has been diversifying in recent years. Those centres run by the state have undergone substantial renovations and tend to provide better quality housing:

All the investments in the infrastructure and the quality of the rooms are made, also with support from the European Union, in the state-owned centres. In the private ones, their owners are responsible for any changes. Moreover, in these government centres, there is no additional private administration. The private administration in the non-government centres also overlooks the order to make sure there is no damage to infrastructure. In this way, private administration frequently introduces various additional elements of disciplining people (PLMZSO2).

As far as the special provision of housing for vulnerable persons and groups is concerned, the legal basis for it can be found in the Law on Protection in Article 68. In legal terms, vulnerable people that may require special treatment take into account the following groups of migrants: minors, the disabled, the elderly, pregnant women, single parents, victims of human trafficking, the seriously ill, mentally disordered people, victims of torture, victims of psychological, physical and sexual violence, as well as violence due to gender, sexual orientation, and gender identity. As stipulated in Article 68(2) the applicant or the person on behalf of which the applicant is acting shall be considered as a person requiring special treatment in the field of social assistance, where there may be a need of:

- accommodation in the centre for foreigners:
 - adapted to the needs of the disabled,
 - providing a single room,
 - intended exclusively for women or women with children;
- placing them in a treatment institution, a nursing care institution or hospice;
- placing them in foster care corresponding to their psychophysical condition;
- adapting their diet to their health.

The vulnerable groups that the Office seems to take into account are single women and women with children. In order to improve their safety, the Office for Foreigners identified one centre solely for this group of people. In 2010, the centre for foreigners applying for international protection located in Targówek in Warsaw was allocated for the accommodation of single women and women with children. According to the Office, from the very beginning, the centre is fully occupied (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 9).

Representatives of NGOs during interviews pointed to numerous issues linked with this particular centre for vulnerable persons. The most significant criticism concerned the fact that there is only one such centre in Poland and it can be easy to track down a given woman with children. This is crucial from the point of view of safety of vulnerable persons: 'This is the only centre in Poland for women bringing up children on their own. What protection are we talking about?' (PLMZSO5/6). Apart from that, the same interviewee mentioned several other problems concerning this centre for foreigners:

Living conditions there are terrible. There are bed bugs and sick children. Children sleep on the floor because it is not possible to sleep in beds because of the danger of being bitten by bed bugs. You can't get rid of them (PLMZSO5/6).

Apart from setting up the centre for single women and mothers with children, in recent years the Office for Foreigners adopted and implemented the action 'Policy of protection of children against abuse in centres for foreigners' in cooperation with the 'We give children the strength' Foundation. This policy was a result of the project 'We protect children in refugee centres—a comprehensive system to protect children from violence and abuse', co-financed from the national programme under the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) and from the state budget (project number 16/2-2015/FAMI). The introduction of this policy in November 2016 obliged all employees, both of the DSA of the Office for Foreigners and employees of companies and organisations that act on behalf of the head of the Office in the centres or run projects targeted at the residents of the centres, to take measures to ensure the security of all minor foreigners. Its key goals are (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 9):

- raising awareness of the importance of protecting children against all forms of abuse;
- providing guidance and determining the course of action and the scope of responsibility in all activities related to the safety of children;
- providing children with safety through preventive actions aimed at education in the field of protection of children's rights and minimising the risk of child abuse, and intervention actions aimed at taking appropriate steps in case of suspected or established child abuse.

As part of the project, all employees and co-workers of the Office undergo periodic training in the field of child protection, including training in the area of the policy of protection of children against abuse in force at the centres. The Office also has educational materials (leaflets, brochures, books, audio-visual materials) for parents concerning children's rights, upbringing without violence, protection of children against violence and abuse, protection of children against peer violence and, if possible, educational activities for parents from the above-mentioned range are conducted (Office for Foreigners, 2019b, p. 9).

Here, it is also worth recalling that in the midst of the migration crisis in 2015, the Polish authorities reluctantly agreed (under PM Ewa Kopacz) to participate in the emergency relocation and resettlement schemes but then later (under PM Beata Szydło) withdrew from it (Pachocka & Velez, 2019) (Legut & Pędziwiatr, 2018). While preparing for the increased influx of forced migrants in need of protection within the abovementioned EU mechanisms, the public authorities carried out a survey that was supposed to assess the capacities of the national asylum and reception system on how many asylum seekers each region, sub-region, or locality could accept. One of our meso-level interviewees recalled a discussion with the mayor of a small city who declared to the central authorities that their community would be able to accept one refugee family. The consequences of this declaration were shocking to the mayor. He said that he had almost lost his position as a result of it. He became the target of a hate campaign. Almost everyone in his city, including local priests and other persons of high social esteem, criticised him (PLMZSO4).

In the provision of housing, the Office is often assisted by various non-governmental and international organisations. Some of the NGOs that have cooperated in the recent years with the Office for Foreigners and, for instance, conducted activities in the centres for foreigners or assisted asylum seekers outside of the centres are: the Other Space Foundation (Fundacja Inna Przestrzeń), the Dialogue Foundation (Fundacja Dialog), the Foundation for Freedom (Fundacja dla Wolności), the Halina Nieć Legal Aid Centre (Centrum Pomocy Prawnej im.

Haliny Nieć), Caritas Poland (Caritas Polska), the Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights (Helsińska Fundacja Praw Człowieka, HFHR), the Association for Legal Intervention (Stowarzyszenie Interwencji Prawnej), the Ocalenie Foundation (Fundacja Ocalenie), the We Give Children Strength Foundation (Fundacja Dajemy Dzieciom Siłę), Refugee.pl, the Polish Hospitality Foundation (Fundacja Polska Gościnność), and With Bread and Salt (Chlebem i Solą). Some of these organisations have been providing, for example, people seeking international protection with substantial assistance in finding adequate accommodation outside the centres. While providing a wide range of social services to migrants, the Office also has been cooperating closely with such international organisations as the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees in Poland (UNCHR Poland).

1.4. Healthcare (Medical) Services

The legal basis for access to health care for persons living in Poland is to be found in Article 68 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997. It stipulates that everybody has the right to healthcare – supposedly citizens of Poland and foreigners alike. It also states that: ‘Public authorities shall ensure special health care to children, pregnant women, handicapped people and persons of advanced age’. However, it also states that equal access to public healthcare services is restricted to Polish citizens. According to the Law on Healthcare Services financed from public funds, the access itself is based upon one’s status as an ‘insurance holder’ – i.e. a person insured with the National Health Fund. Apart from Polish citizens, EU/EFTA countries citizens and certain groups of third-country nationals (e.g. work visa holders, temporary and permanent residents, recognised refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection) can also be considered ‘insurance holders’ (Law on Healthcare Services).

As far as persons seeking asylum in Poland are concerned, their access to healthcare is regulated by the Law on Protection. It describes the conditions for admitting asylum seekers, granting international protection and for executing asylum procedures. Article 70(1) generally states that persons seeking asylum in Poland are entitled to social assistance and healthcare, while Article 71(1) lists the various elements of assistance that foreigners applying for the international protection are entitled to. Foreigners placed in the centres for foreigners are provided with, among other things, tickets for transport in order to attend medical examinations or prophylactic vaccinations or in other particularly justified cases. More detailed information about the healthcare provision to applicants for international protection is to be found in Articles 73 and 74 of the Law on Protection. The first states that healthcare provided to the asylum seekers includes medical care within the scope of which the persons covered by compulsory or voluntary insurance are entitled to on the basis of the Law of 27 September 2004 on health care services financed from public funds. The only elements that are not part of the medical coverage are sanatorium treatment and sanatorium rehabilitation. It also provides information on the organisation of the healthcare provision. It states that medical care is provided on the basis of civil law contracts concluded between the Head of the Office for Foreigners and selected in the public tender medical service providers (Law on Protection, Article 73).

Article 74 provides more detailed information about the commencement and termination of the healthcare coverage for asylum seekers. It states that medical care—similar to social

assistance for asylum seekers—is provided when an application for international protection is being processed, starting from the day the asylum seeker arrives at the centre for foreigners, except in special situations related to threat to the life or health of the foreigner. In the latter situation, medical care is available from the day the foreigner submits the application for international protection. The termination of the healthcare provision is supposed to take place up to two months from the date of delivery of the final decision on granting (or refusing to grant) international protection or for a period of 14 days from the date of delivery of the final decision to discontinue the proceeding, if the procedure has been discontinued. It also states that medical care (and social assistance for asylum seekers) is not to be granted after 14 days from the date of delivery of the final decision to discontinue the procedure, if the procedure for granting international protection has been discontinued. Medical care is also not provided after the execution of the obligation to leave the territory of the Republic of Poland by an asylum seeker whose application for international protection was turned down and who received the decision of refusal to grant refugee status or subsidiary protection.

Up until 2015, asylum seekers were provided with healthcare services by the Central Clinical Hospital of the Ministry of Interior and Administration on Wološka Street in Warsaw. One of our interviewees from the NGO sector described this old arrangement in the following way:

(...) the beginnings were difficult. But I remember that in the last years it significantly improved and, as for the Polish medical care conditions, it worked like a well-oiled mechanism. Of course, it was incomparable to what people have in Germany or Sweden, where the sickest asylum seekers go. But for Polish conditions it worked really well and the asylum seekers were looked after very well (PLMZSO1).

In mid-2015, the contract between the Office for Foreigners and the Central Clinical Hospital ended and the new public tender was won by the private company, established in 1996 – Petra Medica³⁴. This company also won public tender in 2019 and its contract was renewed for the next four years. As one of the employees of the Office for Foreigners informed us, the main reason why the relatively small private company had won against the large clinical hospital is that the public procurement law favoured ‘a better offer’ (PLMZOF3/4), which most probably was also the cheapest offer. Petra Medica provides healthcare services in the centres for foreigners (basic treatment and diagnostics) as well as in the specialist medical units outside the centres. In addition, asylum seekers receive psychological consultations and dental treatment (Office for Foreigners, n.d.). As we will show below, the quality of the latter services are particularly strongly criticised for not being adequate (e.g. no psychotherapy offered and dental treatment in practice limited to the possibility of teeth removals) by the actors from the NGO and some practitioners (MGN2).

Basic healthcare is organised in medical offices within each of the centres for foreigners. The Office confirmed in the communication with Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights that in 2018, the medical doctor in the centres had ten duty hours per 120 asylum seekers, while the nurse had 20 hours for the same number of potential patients. Both had three hours a week more for every additional 50 asylum seekers. As already mentioned, the provision of medical care for asylum seekers also includes treatment for persons suffering from mental health

³⁴ For further information about the Petra Medica, see the company’s website (Petra Medica, n.d.).

problems. In 2018, psychologists worked in all the centres for at least four hours a week for every 120 asylum seekers. This was extended for one hour for every additional 50 asylum seekers. This assistance was limited to basic consultations, however, asylum seekers could also be directed to a psychiatrist or a psychiatric hospital (Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d.).

According to information the Polish RESPOND team received from the Office for Foreigners, the Office spent on average 4165 PLN for medical care for each foreigner applying for international protection in 2019. Four years earlier, when Petra Medica started to provide healthcare services to asylum seekers, the Office spent on average 2813 PLN for each person. Although the number of foreigners applying for refugee status in Poland in recent years has decreased, the cost of medical coverage provided in and outside of the centres for foreigners to asylum seekers has not fallen but fluctuated over the last year. In other words, as shown in Table 7, between 2015 and 2019, the highest total cost of medical care provided to asylum seekers in a given year was in 2017. In that year, the Office spent 12.65 million PLN for this purpose. However, when the average cost of medical care provision per foreigner is taken into account, one may clearly see that the healthcare services offered to asylum seekers were most expensive in 2019. This may, inter alia, have to do with the general rise in cost of medical services in the country. In the last 5 years, over 18 thousand asylum seekers were eligible for the medical care offered by the Office. Its expenses on healthcare services in and outside the centres for foreigners amounted to 57 million PLN. In the last five years, the annual average spent by the Office for the provision of medical services per person was 3150 PLN.

Table 7 The number of asylum seekers covered by medical care provided by the Office for Foreigners and the cost of medical services in 2015-2019

Year	Foreigners applying for refugee status and eligible for the medical care provided by the Office for Foreigners	The total cost of the medical care provided by the Office for Foreigners (in PLN)	Average cost of medical care per foreigner (in PLN)
2015	4 011	11 284 142	2 813
2016	4 171	10 307 245	2 471
2017	3 882	12 654 251	3 259
2018	3 117	10 537 122	3 380
2019	2 979	12 409 887	4 165

Source: own elaboration by RESPOND team in Poland based on data received from the Office for Foreigners.

Neither the Office nor Petra Medica provided the RESPOND team with detailed information about the structure of expenses for providing medical services to asylum seekers. However, one of the officials from the Office informed us that the Office is paying Petra Medica a monthly fee for each foreigner. The interviewee argued that, 'The given foreigner may not use the medical services but he or she is covered by our services anyway [and] we transfer a monthly fee for him or her' (PLMZOF3/4).

It is important to mention that, in 2015, an amendment was introduced to the Law on Protection, placing on the asylum authority, the Office for Foreigners, the responsibility for due examination if an asylum seeker is a person that requires special treatment and can be considered a vulnerable person. Article 68(1) of the Law on Protection lists the following vulnerable groups: minors, disabled persons, elderly persons, pregnant women, single

parents, victims of human trafficking, seriously ill persons, mentally disordered persons, victims of torture, victims of psychological, physical and sexual violence as well as violence due to gender, sexual orientation and gender identity. In the course of the asylum procedure, the Office for Foreigners is now obliged to examine if the applicant should be considered vulnerable on one or more grounds and thus entitled to special treatment. As experts point out, this is an important change as prior to the amendment, the process of identification of vulnerable groups was based solely on ineffective self-identification mechanisms (Szczepanik, 2017).

Medical and psychological treatment are some of the services that, according to the Law on Protection, should be provided to vulnerable asylum seekers (Article 68). Vulnerable asylum seekers should also be granted special procedural guarantees in the course of the refugee status procedure, including conditions adapted to their mental and physical state, the presence of a psychologist or doctor during the interview or the possibility to be interviewed at one's place of residence (Law on Protection, Article 69).

On their website in April 2017, the Office for Foreigners informed about the opening of the so-called second 'epidemiological filter' facility (Office for Foreigners, 2018). One of the employees from the Office said during the interview:

We have two points of epidemiological filters in Dębak and in Biała Podlaska, where all the asylum seekers need to be examined through one of these filters (PLMZOF3/4).

These facilities are located near Warsaw (Podkowa Leśna-Dębak) and the Belarusian border (Biała Podlaska), where most asylum seekers cross the Polish land border. They are aimed at providing medical assistance exclusively to foreigners who have just applied for protection in Poland and to reduce epidemiological risks for the whole of Poland by prompt diagnosis of potential infectious diseases (Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d.).

1.5. Education

In Poland, reception policy with regard to education is based on the following legal acts:

- the Constitution of Poland (already discussed),
- the Law on Protection (already discussed),
- the Law on School Education of 14 December 2016 (called Education Law)³⁵,
- the Ordinance of the Minister of National Education of 23 August 2017 on the education of persons who are not Polish citizens and persons who are Polish citizens and received education at schools functioning in the education systems of other countries (called Ordinance of the Minister of National Education of 23 August 2017)³⁶,
- the Higher Education Law of 20 July 2018³⁷.

³⁵ Ustawa z dnia 14 grudnia 2016 r. - Prawo oświatowe (t.j. Dz.U. z 2017 r. poz. 59 z późn. zm.).

³⁶ Rozporządzenie Ministra Edukacji Narodowej z dnia 28 marca 2019 r. zmieniające rozporządzenie w sprawie kształcenia osób niebędących obywatelami polskimi oraz osób będących obywatelami polskimi, które pobierały naukę w szkołach funkcjonujących w systemach oświaty innych państw (Dz.U. z 2019 r. poz. 666).

³⁷ Ustawa z dnia 20 lipca 2018 r. - Prawo o szkolnictwie wyższym i nauce (Dz.U. z 2018 r. poz. 1668 z późn. zm.).

According to the Polish Constitution, everyone has a right to education and education is compulsory until the age 18 (Article 70(1)). In fact, the right to education is guaranteed not only to Polish citizens but to all children in Poland, including asylum seekers, who have free and unlimited access to education in public schools until the age of 18 or the completion of higher school. According to Article 71(1) of the Law on Protection, asylum seekers are entitled to social assistance, which with reference to education comprises:

- classes of Polish and basic supplies for learning the language,
- didactic materials for children benefitting from education and care in public institutions, primary schools or secondary schools,
- covering, if possible, the costs of extra-curricular activities and sports and recreational classes for children.

The obligation of education is regulated in detail by the Law on School Education (in short: Education Law). This Law determines compulsory education for all children until 18 years old (Article 35(1)) and compulsory schooling for all children from 7 years old until the completion of primary school, but no longer than the age of 18 (Article 35 (2)). Furthermore, it introduces the obligatory one-year pre-school preparation for all 6-year-old children (Article 31(4)). The latter can be carried out either in primary schools or kindergarten or other form of pre-school education. With regard to pre-school education, it applies to children from 3 to 7 years old, although it is not obligatory, except for the one-year pre-school preparation for 6-year-old children (Articles 31(1)(4)).

In Poland, as of September 2019, full-time compulsory education lasts for 9 years. It comprises the last year of pre-school education and 8 years of primary school education. In the Polish educational system, full-time compulsory education and part-time compulsory education are defined as follows:

- Full-time compulsory education (obligation to attend 8-year primary school) applies, in general, to pupils aged 7-15 years.
- Part-time compulsory education (obligation to be in education) concerns pupils aged 15-18 and it may take place either in school settings (a pupil attends upper secondary school) or in non-school settings (e.g., a pupil follows vocational training offered by employers).

Reform of the Polish school system has been underway since 1 September 2017. In December 2016, two key acts were passed by parliament, specifically the Law on School Education and the Provisions introducing the Law on School Education³⁸, which have largely replaced the School Education Law of September 1991. The main change involves replacing the previously existing 6-year primary school and lower secondary school (6+3), leading to upper secondary education in 3- or 4-year schools, with the single 8-year primary school and extending the duration of education in (upper) secondary schools to 4-5 years. This will partly re-establish the model that was in place in Poland before the school system reform of 1999/2000 (European Commission (EC) - Eurydice, 2019).

Children applying for international protection and subject to compulsory schooling who do not know Polish or whose level of Polish is not sufficient to benefit from education are entitled to additional, unpaid Polish language learning in the form of additional lessons. These classes are conducted individually or in groups, for at least two hours up to a maximum of 5 hours (in

³⁸ Ustawa z dnia 14 grudnia 2016 – Przepisy wprowadzające ustawę – Prawo oświatowe (Dz.U. z 2017 r. poz. 60 z późn. zm).

a situation in which a child does not participate in the compensatory classes described below) a week. Learning Polish continues until the student masters the language to a degree enabling learning and is not time-limited (Ordinance of the Minister of National Education of 23 August 2017, Par. 17).

Asylum seeking children can also benefit from additional compensatory classes organised by the school if a teacher conducting educational classes in a given subject finds the need to supplement the curriculum differences in that subject. Such additional compensatory classes in a given subject are conducted individually or in groups in the form of additional lessons in this subject for one lesson per week for a period of 12 months. However, there is a limit of five hours of additional language and compensatory classes per pupil (Ordinance of the Minister of National Education of 23 August 2017, Par. 18 and 19). Although the period of compensatory classes for foreign children is limited to 12 months, after this time these children can attend didactic and compensatory classes organised for students with learning difficulties, in particular in meeting the educational requirements resulting from the general education core curriculum for a given educational stage (Ordinance of the Minister of National Education of 9 August 2017 on the principles of organisation and providing psychological and pedagogical assistance in public kindergartens, schools and institutions, Par. 15)³⁹.

In response to the increasing number of pupils with migration experience in Polish schools and communications problems stemming from it, the Education Law of 2016 introduced the possibility to create a preparatory class (also called 'a welcome class'⁴⁰), a new organisational form of education for children who do not know Polish well enough to learn in this language or who have adaptation problems after arriving in Poland. The departments can be created in public and non-public schools by a school's governing body, either at the beginning or during the school year. In principle, education in a preparatory department lasts one school year, but it may be shortened or extended by a maximum one school year (Education Law, Article 165(11)). The Ordinance of the Minister of National Education of 23 August 2017 specifies the organisation of the work of the preparatory department, in particular the maximum number of students (15 people), which aims to ensure an individual approach to each pupil. Teaching in the preparatory class should be conducted according to school curricula, with methods and forms being adapted to individual development and educational needs as well as psychophysical abilities of students. Compulsory teaching of Polish as a foreign language is carried out for pupils not less than three hours a week. A pupil of the preparatory class also has the right to take additional Polish language classes as mentioned above (Ordinance of the Minister of National Education of 23 August 2017, Par. 16 and 17).

Children also have a right to the assistance of a person who knows the language of their country of origin, which can be employed as a teacher's assistant (also called 'a intercultural assistant') by a director of the school. This assistance is limited to a maximum of 12 months for a student (Education Law, Article 165(8)). The tasks of the teacher's assistant usually include supporting foreign students in learning, supporting teachers in teaching foreigners, controlling attendance, and also mediating, also as translators, in contacts between school and parents of students (Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights (HFHR), 2019). It is worth

³⁹ Rozporządzenie Ministra Edukacji Narodowej z dnia 9 sierpnia 2017 r. w sprawie warunków organizowania kształcenia, wychowania i opieki dla dzieci i młodzieży niepełnosprawnych, niedostosowanych społecznie i zagrożonych niedostosowaniem społecznym Dz.U. z 2017 r. poz. 1578 z późn. zm.).

⁴⁰ For further information, see (Sołtan-Kościelecka, 2018).

mentioning that this solution is not easy to implement, since the final decision about hiring a teacher's assistant rests with the local government responsible for administering a particular school.

In 2018, the Ministry of Interior and Administration proposed an amendment to the Ordinance on the rules of staying in centres for foreigners enabling teaching asylum-seeking children in the centres instead of public schools. The Ombudsman (Commissioner) for Children's Rights and social organisations criticised the proposal, arguing it would violate children's rights and lead to discrimination and separation of asylum-seeking children from Polish society (Rzeczpospolita, 2018). After the Ministry's vague explanations that the main aim of the proposal was to provide the possibility to react in case of a massive influx of foreigners, the criticism did not abate and the Ministry backed off the idea (Dziennik Gazeta Prawna, 2018).

Asylum seekers do not have a guarantee that they could send their children to a nursery or a kindergarten, since there are not enough places in pre-school learning facilities in Poland. However, in all centres for foreigners some form of kindergarten is provided, often with a support of NGOs. Day care is provided a minimum of five times a week for five hours a day. In addition, since 2018, the additional play and educational classes for children have been organised in the centres on Saturdays (Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights (HFHR), 2019).

The Education Law stipulates that asylum seekers have access to education in public schools for adults, public post-secondary schools, public art schools, public institutions and colleges of social service employees and vocational qualification courses under the conditions applicable to Polish citizens (Education Law, Article 165(3)). In practice, vocational training courses are organised in some centres by NGOs but their range is limited due to insufficient funding⁴¹ (Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights (HFHR), 2019).

With respect to higher education, asylum seekers do not have right to free access to it, since the latter is reserved only for Polish citizens and particular categories of foreigners, including refugees and subsidiary or temporary protection beneficiaries (Higher Education Law, Article 324(2)). However, the law also gives the right to study without tuition to fluent Polish speakers, which has to be confirmed by a Polish language certificate with at least a C1 level (Higher Education Law, Article 324(2)(5)). Although theoretically it can also apply to asylum seekers, in practice the probability of such a combination is almost none. Therefore, if asylum seekers want to begin or continue studies, they have to pay tuition. Access to Polish language classes for adults and basic language-learning materials are guaranteed by the Law on Protection (Article 71(1)). Polish language courses in centres for asylum seekers are organised by the Office for Foreigners as a pre-integration action. The language classes are conducted by private entities selected in public procurement for the 'provision of educational services for the needs of the Office for Foreigners'. According to the conditions of the latest procurement announced in 2019, the entity responsible for organisation of the courses has to provide Polish classes in every centre three times weekly (two hours each) for adults and five times weekly (one hour each) for children (Office for Foreigners, 2019c). The number of hours of Polish classes was increased from four to six weekly after control of the Supreme Audit Office (SAO, in Polish *Najwyższa Izba Kontroli*, NIK) in 2015. The SAO stated that four hours of Polish classes is not enough to learn the language to a level for functioning in the local community (Baczyński-Sielaczek, 2016).

⁴¹ For further information regarding the implementation of the Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund (AMIF) in Poland since 2015, see (Pachocka & Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, pp. 35-38).

The responsibilities in the realm of reception in education are divided between central and local governments. Coordination of educational policy rests with the Ministry of National Education (MNE, in Polish *Minister Edukacji Narodowej*, MEN), whereas the management of education and the administration of schools, nursery schools and other educational institutions is decentralised. The responsibility for the administration of nursery schools (*przedszkole*) and primary schools (*szkoła podstawowa*) (and, as of 1999/2000, lower secondary schools, *gimnazjum*, which are being phased out since 2017) has been delegated to the communes (*gmina*). Statutory responsibility for the management of post-primary schools (above the lower-secondary level until 31 August 2017), art schools, and special schools has been delegated to districts (*powiat*). The self-governing provinces (regions), called voivodships (*województwo*), administer only schools operating at the regional and supra-regional levels. The responsibility for pedagogical supervision rests with the heads of the regional education authorities (superintendents) in the 16 voivodships.

In addition, some competences in the mentioned area are vested in the Office for Foreigners, an institution subordinate to the Ministry of Interior and Administration. The Office for Foreigners is responsible for the social assistance provided to asylum seekers, including assistance in education stemming from the Law on Protection.

Local government units are entitled to the educational part of the general subsidy for tasks related to the education of children from abroad. The algorithm for the division of educational subsidies includes additional weights covering pupils benefitting from additional Polish language classes. According to the Ordinance of the Ministry of National Education on the distribution of part of the general educational subsidy for local government units in 2019⁴², the weighting was $P44=1.5$. Furthermore, there is an additional weighting for children attending the preparatory class, which is $P45 = 0.3$ ⁴³. However, the actual sum of the additional subsidy depends on the number of children attending the mentioned additional classes (Ministerstwo Edukacji Narodowej (MEN), 2019). If a child starts school after the reporting date, then funds in the form of the increased educational subsidy to cover additional costs related to his/her education cannot be granted to the school at all (Commissioner for Human Rights, 2016: 24).

It is possible to request additional support due to an increase in unexpected school and non-school tasks which is allocated to schools from the reserve. However, even a significant increase in the number of foreign students at school, which is often experienced by schools close to the centres for foreigners, does not imply an automatic increase in funds allocated to the school. In addition, the funds granted to the school for foreign children's education do not have to be spent on their direct support. The subsidy is non-returnable aid granted to the commune (*gmina*) and does not have to be spent on a specific, predetermined purpose. Moreover, the Ministry of National Education cannot control how local governments manage their own budgets (Commissioner for Human Rights, 2016). The practice shows that the money is spent on supporting the education of foreign children, but the subsidy is not sufficient to cover all tasks and needs related to it.

⁴² Rozporządzenie Ministra Edukacji Narodowej z dnia 18 grudnia 2018 r. w sprawie sposobu podziału części oświatowej subwencji ogólnej dla jednostek samorządu terytorialnego w roku 2019 (Dz.U. z 2018 r. poz. 2446).

⁴³ The weightings (symbols from P1 to P58) are used for calculation of a statistical number of pupils in a particular school on basis of what the overall education subsidy given to the local governments is calculated. The subsidy is calculated as a total sum of subsidies per one conversion pupil.

1.6. Labour Market

According to the rules specified in the Law on Protection, the issuance of a decision on granting international protection to a foreigner should be completed within six months⁴⁴ (following the day when the application was lodged (Article 34(1)). However, this time limit may be extended to 15 months when the case is particularly complicated; applications for international protection are made in short intervals by a large number of foreigners and this makes it impossible to examine the application for international protection within six months; or, the applicant does not fulfil the obligations arising from the Law and asylum procedure (Article 34(2)). As stipulated in Article 35(1) of the Law of Protection, if a decision has not been issued within the time limit of six months from the date of submission of an application, and the proceedings extended for a reason beyond the applicant's control, the Head of the Office for Foreigners, upon an applicant's request, may issue a certificate (statement), which, accompanied by the temporary certificate of identity of a foreigner, entitles a given person to work within the territory of the Republic of Poland according to the Law on the promotion of employment and labour market institutions⁴⁵. Foreigners who apply for international protection are exempt from the obligation to have a work permit, provided they have the aforementioned certificate. Asylum seekers, even if receive the abovementioned certificate, are not permitted to run their own business. The certificate is valid until the date by which the decision on granting international protection becomes final, that is, until the moment when the decision is upheld or overturned by the Refugee Board (second-instance decision) (based on the Law on Protection) or earlier if the asylum seeker decides not to appeal to Refugee Board. The temporary ID document is valid for 90 days and can be prolonged for renewable periods of six months (Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d.). During the appeal in court and/or repeated application, the foreigners are not allowed to work—their certificate becomes invalid—unless the court decides to suspend the enforceability of the Refugee Board's decision, which used to be a rare situation, or the repeated procedure lasts longer than six months. Therefore, in a situation when someone receives a final decision within the first six months and then appeals against this decision in the court and submits a new application, sometimes even a couple of times, he/she may be not allowed to work for even a few years. Hence, many asylum seekers are in a form of limbo in this regard.

According to the statements of the participants of the II MGN Roundtable Discussion held in January 2020, there was a change in practice in the abovementioned area regarding both the moment within the procedure when asylum seekers are allowed to apply for the certificate, as well as juridical practice regarding its validation. In the first case, a couple of years ago the Office for Foreigners started to issued certificates not only for those whose procedure had been prolonged in the first instance but also for those whose whole asylum procedure within both bodies (Office for Foreigner and Refugee Board) exceeded the six-month period. In addition, during the last months of 2019, the courts started to suspend the implementation of the Refugee Board's decisions more often, which means that people who file complaints to courts may legally perform work and use the certificate. This interpretation and action are in

⁴⁴ With the exception of cases specified in Article 39(1) of the Law on Protection regarding the so-called accelerated asylum procedure.

⁴⁵ Ustawa z dnia 20 kwietnia 2004 r. o promocji zatrudnienia i instytucjach rynku pracy (t.j. Dz.U. z 2019 r. poz. 1482, 1622, 1818, 2473 z późn. zm.).

line with Directive 2013/33/EU⁴⁶ whose Article 15(3) stipulates: ‘Access to the labour market shall not be withdrawn during appeals procedures, where an appeal against a negative decision in a regular procedure has suspensive effect, until such time as a negative decision on the appeal is notified’.

The Polish RESPOND team received the data from the Office for Foreigners on the number of requested certificates since 2017. As shown in Table 8 there is a relatively high percentage of refusals concerning requests for issuing a certificate submitted by asylum seekers (even 49% in 2018). As we were informed by a representative of the Office for Foreigners, this situation can be explained by the fact that the requests are submitted too early (that is, before the end of the time limit of six months when the Office is supposed to issue a decision on asylum application) and/or the decision on granting international protection becomes final before the request is examined.

Table 8 The number of requested certificates and decisions issued in this regard in 2017-2020 (January)

	2017	2018	2019	30.01.2020
Number of asylum applications	5104	4165	4093	404
Number of requests for the certificate	689	588	686	59
Number of issued certificates	459	301	486	32
Number of refusals	230	287	200	7*
Percentage of refusals	33%	49%	29%	12%
*20 applications have not yet been considered or their results have not yet been registered				

Source: own elaboration by RESPOND team in Poland based on data received from the Office for Foreigners.

In absolute terms, the number of requests lodged for certificate is not high. In relative terms, if we compare this number to the total number of asylum application, we observe that it amounts to 13-17% of asylum applications. This was also confirmed during interviews with practitioners. This situation was partially explained by one of the MGN II participants who stated that, on average, asylum seekers receive a first-instance decision on their application for international protection within five months, which means that they are not entitled to apply for a certificate to work. Other possible explanations come from micro-level and meso-level interviews. According to them, many asylum seekers have no knowledge of the legal conditions regarding their access to the labour market and job opportunities. Another important fact in the revocation figures is the high number of asylum seekers leaving Poland after having submitted their application for international protection, as evidenced by the large number of discontinued proceedings.

⁴⁶ Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (OJ L 180, 29.6.2013).

2. Reception Practices

In this section of the WP4 report, we focus on the practices, experiences, and perceptions regarding the reception system in Poland. This part provides important insight from the meso- and micro-level semi-structured interviews, as well as from relevant documents and literature to explain, contextualise, and complement these practices and experiences. Extended quotations from the interviews are used, as agreed within the RESPOND consortium, to flesh out relevant results from our fieldwork. We discuss the following aspects of reception conditions: housing and allowances, healthcare (medical) services, early access to education and early access to the labour market.

2.1. Housing and Allowances

As the growing majority of asylum seekers in Poland live outside the centres for foreigners operated by the Office for Foreigners, we begin with an assessment of this type of housing provision and allowances linked with it. After a critical evaluation pointing out numerous issues linked with these provisions, we shed light on the practices, experiences, and perceptions of housing and allowances in the centres for foreigners. In both parts, as far as possible and relevant, we strive to juxtapose the opinions of the asylum seekers, and hence, data from the micro-level interviews with those from the state administration, practitioners, and NGO actors, so meso-level data.

2.1.1. Housing outside the Centres for Foreigners

One of the major problems with housing provision, as mentioned frequently by both meso-level actors as well as those seeking international protection in Poland, is the insufficient level of financial support provided by the state to cover the cost of living outside of the centres for foreigners. As mentioned above, a single person receives a monthly benefit of 750 PLN to cover all the costs of life outside the centres while a four-person family receives 1500 PLN. Technically, as one of our interviewees from the state agency dealing with migrants explained, in the past these benefits used to be paid to the migrants only in the centres, so they were forced to collect their benefits in cash there. In 2019, the situation changed and at the moment the benefits are paid to migrants by postal transfers. This means that every month the postal carrier delivers the benefits to people accommodated outside the centres at their place of residence. The Office only monitors whether the benefits have been collected. Polish postal law also allows close relatives of the people to whom the postal financial transfer is addressed to collect these benefits. If it is not collected, then the Office is informed about it by the postal system and the agency knows that the migrant probably has changed address or left the country (PLMZOF3/4).

One of the interviewed practitioners argued that the extent to which housing needs are satisfied for people seeking international protection

(...) depends on their personal expectations because everyone is different. For some people, one room with a kitchen will be enough, and for someone else who used to live in a large house, it will degrade his/her dignity and comfort. (...) I can't say it is tragic, because these are just the conditions in this country. One cannot turn a blind eye to the fact that in this country sometimes families of two generations live in a 37 square metre flat. It is just a fact. If someone thinks that

he/she will live in 65 square metres, it is not always [the case] in our region (PLMZP2).

This interviewee also claimed that in one medium-size Polish city, 1200PLN is sufficient to pay for all the costs of the rental of a fully-furnished two-room or three-room flat. 'If someone rents a room in a single-family house, it is 400-450PLN. It is true that people may prefer to be more independent, but these prices can still be found' (PLMZP2). The respondent also suggested that the cash benefits to self-cover the costs of one's stay in Poland are adequate.

However, the vast majority of actors from the NGO sector as well as some asylum seekers interviewed in the course of the research complained about the level of the financial support provided by the Office to cover the cost of living outside the centres for foreigners. For instance, one of the asylum seekers argued that to rent a flat:

I would need to have a permanent job. I receive 1500 PLN when I work, and I would need to pay for everything for the flat. But I also need the money for food and for the children's clothes. I certainly would like to rent a flat. We go to bed at 8 p.m. and sometimes it is noisy here (PLMICH02).

She is unable to leave the Office-run facility despite its numerous drawbacks because she does not earn enough money and would not receive sufficient financial support from the Office.

Some of the representatives of the social organisations were even more vocal in their criticism of the level of support provided by the state to the asylum seekers who decide to live outside the centres for foreigners. One of them pointed out that, for example:

the level of financial support can be sufficient to maximally rent a room, because one cannot even dream about renting an apartment for this money and yet [still have] some resources to buy food. A couple with a child gets 1350 PLN for three persons. This amount is not sufficient to survive even in small towns in Poland (PLMZSO2).

A similar opinion was expressed by another respondent from the NGO sector, who argued that 750 PLN:

certainly does not allow one to rent an apartment. Sometimes a room. In Warsaw, room prices are even higher. So, to find a room for 400 PLN borders on a miracle. This has a direct impact on the housing conditions (...) They are sometimes literally substandard—people live in basements or in attics without heating, or a lot of people live in a very small space and this is done without the consent of the owner. So, they rent a flat as a family of five [persons], and then they also take in a cousin with his/her children (PLMZS01).

These opinions are supported by numerous research reports. In one of them, from 2017, one may read that the amount of so-called benefits outside the centre has not been raised since they were introduced in 2003. In the same period, the costs of living have significantly risen. In 2016, for example, the subsistence level, that is, the minimal amount of financial resources below which there is a biological threat to human life, according to calculations by the Institute of Labour and Social Affairs, amounted to 555 PLN for a one-person household and 472 PLN per person in a four-person household (Klaus, 2017a, p. 22). Hence, if a four-person family in 2019 is paid 1500 PLN cash benefit to live outside the centre, then it is almost 100 PLN per person less than the subsistence level in 2016.

A report by the Association of Legal Intervention based on monitoring of the housing conditions of refugees describes the situation of persons seeking international protection in Poland. It points out that asylum seekers 'in order to support themselves have to earn some extra money, most commonly by working illegally'⁴⁷. And even then, they usually rent apartments of substandard quality or rent them together with two or three families'. At the same time, the authors of the report argue that foreigners who are in the refugee procedure are never threatened with extreme homelessness. If they are unable to make a living by renting an apartment on the free market, they can at any time opt-out of the 'out-of-centre' benefits and return to one of the Office-run centres for foreigners (Chrzanowska & Czerniejewska, 2015, p. 8).

Here, it is worth mentioning that this opinion is not shared among all of the researchers analysing the situation of people seeking asylum in Poland. Kinga Wysieńska, for example, in her report on various dimensions of homelessness among refugees and people seeking international protection in Poland, argues that not only foreigners living in the centres run by the Office for Foreigners but also those who are recipients of the benefits living outside the centres experience homelessness, or they are exposed to it. The first group of foreigners (those living in the centres) are exposed to it because they are staying in collective accommodation, whereas those receiving the benefit, due to its minimal amount, cannot adequately cover the cost of rented premises on the free market (Wysieńska, 2014, pp. 5-6).

Poor housing conditions due to insufficient financial support was also mentioned in the project interviews by employees of the Office for Foreigners. One interviewee said openly that 'the out-of-centre benefit is too low and it is difficult to survive with it' and that the agency's control visits regularly show that 'migrants are renting flats or houses that are lived in by a higher number of people than they should be' (PLMZOF3/4). These situations are also confirmed by numerous accounts of people seeking international protection in Poland. For instance, one of our micro-level respondents said:

The thing I would like to change in the first place is an apartment. Here, an accommodation issue is very hard, not like in other countries. I lived for almost one year in my sister's apartment because it was hard to rent a flat. In the one apartment, we lived almost 15 people (PLMICH11).

The process of monitoring the housing conditions of asylum seekers living outside of the centres by employees of the Office for Foreigners is also not very consistent and there are no serious consequences. It is clear from the following account provided by one of them:

Until now, we organised such teams of employees who visited foreigners twice a year. We call these people earlier and inform them about our visit. If they do not agree, then we do not enter their houses and we give up. But if they agree, then we meet, talk about their problems and whether the children go to school. Also, we check the conditions in which they live, whether these conditions are appropriate, especially for children. There were different situations. Sometimes they were living in really quite dangerous flats, maybe not so much the flats as the houses (PLMZOF3/4).

At the same time, this employee admitted that

⁴⁷ As mentioned earlier, they can be granted a work permit only six months after filing the application for international protection.

We [the Office for Foreigners] don't have the tools to bring them back to the centres; however, we always offer this. The foreigners, though, who live outside for some time do not want to return to the centres. We suggest they look for another flat, or as employees, we also get involved and try to help them look for something else. We follow rental advertisements, call the owners and try to arrange appointments for the asylum seekers (PLMZOF3/4).

Yet another problem with the 'monitoring visits' by Office employees to migrants' homes was mentioned by one of NGO sector respondents, who pointed out that these visits are 'half-control and half-care', and described the following interesting case from the organisation's activity:

(...) There was a lady, whom we knew that she had these difficult housing conditions. Objectively, she did not live in terrible conditions, but she had to work hard to earn money to have these conditions. She said that when someone from the Office came to her, then they said that she had a clean house, a TV set and everything was fine. However, they were not aware of the fact that she paid twice as much for this apartment than what she got from them. And she couldn't afford another standard—she preferred to live separately with her daughter because she was afraid of leaving her daughter in the apartment with other people (PLMZSO1).

The research data show also that not only Office employees but also other practitioners and members of social organisations try to provide assistance to foreigners in the search for housing. The practitioner from one medium-size Polish city pointed out, for example:

If someone is looking for a flat somewhere, we talk about it and we are also looking for such a flat. We call people who rent flats or provide these addresses where we know people have been renting flats for many years. It is hard to call them hotels—let's call them workers' hotels. We provide asylum seekers information about where someone is renting an apartment at a decent price and in good conditions (PLMZP2).

This help is very important since foreigners seeking protection have to tackle not only the issue of very limited funding for accommodation but also problems related to discrimination in the housing market. This problem and some interesting ideas of addressing it were mentioned by an interviewee in the NGO sector, who said:

There is high resistance on the part of flat owners, apart from the financial barrier. Even if there is no resistance from the owners, the flats for rent are too expensive for the asylum seeker. However, an interesting grassroots initiative has been launched by 'With Bread and Salt'⁴⁸ over a year ago. They search for flats for both asylum seekers or refugees without separating the two groups and they have achieved huge success in this field. They work through Facebook, through various social media and such networks. They found several dozen nice apartments, just under 100—in the last year or so. It's a lot (PLMZSO1).

The aforementioned type of help would be particularly appreciated by the following asylum seeker (like many others) interviewed in the course of this research, who said:

⁴⁸ For further information about the initiative, see its social media page (Facebook, n.d.).

I want to rent a flat, but I haven't found a proper flat yet. It would be great to live in peace and quiet, which is impossible here (in the centre for foreigners). It is noisy here. You have to share the kitchen, the bathroom with other people. I am already tired of living in a camp. I want to have my own place, to be able to take a bath, to cook when I want (PLMICH03).

It is also important to mention the problem of vulnerable people who live outside the centres and rely on the benefit that is supposed to cover the cost of life in Poland. Again, here also the key barrier for vulnerable people to move out of the centres is a financial one. Its key elements were aptly noted in this observation by a civil society actor:

Certainly, for everyone, in the long run, the best is accommodation outside of the centres for foreigners (...) A three or six-month stay in the centre is not a drama, but if these procedures are prolonged, it would be good for everyone to live outside the centres. But it is such that this financial support is so low that a lot of people who would want to move out of the centres cannot afford it because they know that they have no 'extra money', because they are single mothers or people with disabilities. It is certainly the case that the financial support is not diversified in any way depending on the specific needs of a given person or family. If a family has a disabled person requiring intensive care or no such persons to look after, they will both receive the same amount of money as the non-centre benefits. (...) It would be worth diversifying this amount of help depending on the needs of people with special needs (PLMZSO1).

As will be shown below, some vulnerable asylum seekers prefer to live in the centres for foreigners to have easier access to the medical services provided there or that can be arranged easier with the help of the centre's staff.

2.1.2. Housing in the Centres for Foreigners

When it comes to accommodation in the centres for foreigners, there was almost general agreement among the meso-level interviewees that the housing conditions in these centres have over the last years significantly improved. This transformation has been pointed out both by practitioners and members of the NGO sector. These improved conditions, according to some of the interviewed employees of the Office for Foreigners, can be matched with conditions provided to asylum seekers in Western European countries. One of these interviewees argued that:

I have not been to many study visits, but from the stories, reports and what I saw myself, we really have nothing to be ashamed of. Our conditions may be modest, but they are really very good. Especially in comparison to the situation in some countries where foreigners live in some barracks, in large halls, where it is not possible to keep the intimacy of the family. (...) We have at least comparable conditions, if not better. I know this also based on the opinions of foreign delegations that visit our centres. I have not heard any criticism yet. On the contrary, everyone is surprised that foreigners are in such good conditions (PLMZOF3/4).

These descriptions of good standards in the centres are worth juxtaposing with the opinions of some of the interviewed asylum seekers as they do not necessarily create a cohesive

picture. One of them described the reception conditions in the centre in Dębak in the following way:

Conditions in the refugee camp were very poor. In terms of hygiene standards, it was dirty. There were bedbugs in the blankets. It was a horror. It seemed as they somehow drove the people into the barn, where everything smelled. People were complaining a lot. I thought, how long can I handle it? That's why I had to leave camp as soon as possible' (PLMICH09).

This opinion clearly diverges from the perspective painted by the employee of the Office for Foreigners quoted above.

Other people seeking international protection in Poland had a less critical perception of the conditions in the centres. Before describing some of the other main criticisms raised, it is worth mentioning a couple of positive points that were made. One of the most important ones had to do with security. Several interviewees from the micro-level pointed out that the centres have provided them with something very important—security. One of them, when asked if she liked the centre in which she was staying, answered:

The main thing for me is that I am safe here, that nobody will come and kill me. I am alive, my child is with me. We are not starving. We have a room. Of course, it could be better, but for the moment, that will do for me. The main thing is, that I feel protected. Nobody knows, where I am (PLMICH03).

Another element of the housing provision in the Office-run centres appreciated by their inhabitants was the possibility of interaction with other people and social life. An inhabitant of one of the centres said:

It looks like a hotel to me. Yes, we share the kitchen and the bathroom with other families. It is not convenient, but on the other hand, we have a social life. Women talk in the kitchen. (...) I can go out to the garden, rake leaves, like at home. I can't say I feel completely at home. We have been living here for some time, so we made our room cosy (PLMICH05).

As is evident from the excerpt of the interview with the asylum seeker, this person is fully aware of the fact that the centre is not her home and yet she tries to make it a little bit like home. Similarly, a few other interviewees talked about the importance of socialising and spending time together with other inhabitants of the centres in their 'kitchen' (e.g., PLMICH06 and PLMIIR26). One of the major reasons that prevented them from enjoying it more was the lack of money to buy items to cook—an issue which will be discussed later. Yet, one more feature of the centres that was considered positive and mentioned by a few current or past inhabitants was the quite easy access to medical care in the centres⁴⁹.

One of the major critical remarks concerning the provision of housing in the centres for foreigners was linked with their location. Both our interviewees involved in providing assistance to foreigners as well as asylum seekers saw the location of the centres in the countryside and sometimes (when applicable) within cities as very problematic. The first issue was well captured by one of the practitioners, who pointed out that:

⁴⁹ This dimension of social services provision to asylum seekers will be explored in detail in the section '2.2. Healthcare (Medical) Services' of this report.

When it comes to the centres for people in the procedure, I have the impression that they select them only on the basis of price. Whoever offers the lowest then wins. Nobody thinks whether there are refugees or not. Łódź Grotniki, for example, or Czerwony Bór near Łomża. I apologise for the expression, but you can't find bigger shitholes. The conditions for integration are zero. They have empty buildings so let the foreigners live there. Nobody takes into account how close these places are to cities, about the possibility of interaction with people and entering the labour market. This is completely out of the picture. Only the price criterion—98% and 2% I do not know what—whether there is a nice forest around. Dębak, for example, is a former missile defence unit in Warsaw. What [integration] are we talking about? (PLMZP1).

This is how one of the people in the asylum procedure talked about her life in Podkowa Leśna-Dębak:

I lived there for four months and it was very difficult. I had to be in the office in Taborowa street in Warsaw every Wednesday and I had to go to the bus stop through 3 km of forest together with the children. Sometimes, my friends who had cars gave me a lift. I also had a job. I cleaned in the kindergarten. It was difficult to get there from Dębak (PLMICH02).

Later, this person talked about the relief she felt when she managed to secure a transfer to a centre in a big city where she lives close to people, shops, school, and her temporary job.

The location of the centres far from big cities is particularly problematic to vulnerable persons such as those with a disability. One such person interviewed in the course of the research pointed out:

The location of the centre is very problematic—it's a big problem for me. How can I go anywhere? You can't go anywhere except by car. I've been here in the camp for two months and 10 days and I did not go out at all. If I need anything, my friends will bring it to me here. Anything I eat or drink or smoke, it comes to me here. I do not go out because once it was cold and another time there was no track for the wheelchair (PLMIIR26).

The fact that many centres are far from cities not only limits the scope of interaction and integration of foreigners with the host society but also the actions of the NGO sector. As one of its representatives aptly pointed out:

Because the centres are far away from some large urban agglomerations and often off the beaten track, it makes it difficult for NGOs to reach them. If we want, for example, to do some activities for people in Linin, we will find volunteers, but we would need to arrange transportation for them to take them there and back (PLMZSO1).

An interesting problem linked with the location of the centres away from big cities was noticed by one of the interviewed representatives of the local authorities. He claimed that one of the centres:

(...) was located in the wrong place. It became a very visible—dominant element there. If it functioned within a larger environment, it wouldn't be so noticeable, it would be lost in the crowd of people. This is a sparsely populated area because we know that these are small villages and a school with 150 pupils. Every element

of behaviour that we cannot agree with is quickly noticed. Maybe it has good sides because there is a signal and there is a faster response. In the city, it could be more camouflaged, classified, because in urban society not all such things are noticed (PLMZLG1).

In his own way, the quoted respondent referred to the issue of the visibility of minorities that in a small rural or urban settings become clearer. However, moving the centres for people seeking asylum to big cities will not resolve all the problems linked with this type of phenomenon and frequent discriminatory perceptions and treatment of visible minorities, especially during the significant securitisation of the figure of a refugee and more generally the processes of forced migration (Legut & Pędziwiatr, 2018) (Łodziński, 2019) (Molęda-Zdziech, et al., 2020) (Pędziwiatr, 2019).

Another issue indicated was the location of some of the centres within cities, but on their outskirts or in some poor or problematic parts. One NGO expert pointed out the centre for foreigners located in Targówek in Warsaw as one located 'in the unfriendly part of the city, with the factories and where the concrete mixers drive every now and then' (PLMZSO1). Another NGO expert added:

The buildings are close to the warehouses and storage for construction material. There is plenty of dust in the air during the whole warm period. Children go to school along the road for trucks. It is in the outskirts (PLMZSO2).

Yet, a different problem with the housing provision in the centres mentioned by some of our interviewees was overcrowding. One asylum seeker with whom we talked to recounted the following about the conditions in the centre:

(...) in the past, it was not good. (...) Before, there were 14 people in a room. All the countries, Iraq, Yemen ... Now in the new room, it is me and three other guys, two Kurds, and one Yemeni (PLMIIR27).

On the other hand, another asylum seeker described his living conditions in the centre for foreigners as:

Maybe we were lucky, or maybe the management decided like that, but they gave us a very spacious room. There were four big rooms in the centre, and one of them was ours. We fitted in. On the one side, there were children, on the other—us. We separated the sides with the wardrobes (PLMIUK19).

People seeking international protection who lived in the centres for foreigners also complained about conflicts with other inhabitants of the centres. One of our Ukrainian interviewees claimed that ethno-religious tensions were the major reasons why she decided to move out of the centre. She argued that:

It was hard to stay together with Chechens and their different attitudes to women and to people relations. (...) It was one of the reasons I wanted to live in my own flat, not to depend on anyone. I wanted to be a host in my own house. So, when we were accommodated together with this Chechen family, I decided to look for a private house. Before, I wrote motions to be moved to another room, but the management of the centre rejected them (PLMIUK20).

Instances of conflict and even violence in the centres were also mentioned by some of the interviewees from the civil society organisations and local governments. One NGO expert

(PLMZSO2) claimed that the scale of violence is particularly high in the centre in Targówek in Warsaw, where there are only women and children. These conflicts were 'between residents, between children, between residents and children' and even the police were unable to control them. Our interviewee put most of the blame for this situation on the authorities who had created such a large centre for women with children. The number of people staying in the centre at the time of the interview was around 150. According to the respondent, this crowding was the main reason for the high level of tension and violence in the centre.

Conflicts rooted in cultural and religious differences in other centres for foreigners were also pointed out by one of the interviewed representatives of the local authorities (PLMZLG1). According to this interviewee, these differences were the major reason why asylum seekers, in spite of the very modest housing benefits, preferred to live outside the centres. In this regard, one of the employees of the Office for Foreigners informed us that in order to prevent conflicts, 'there is a bit of a tendency not to mix nationalities too much, and some know-how about how to locate the people in the centres so as to avoid tensions [related to] different backgrounds' (PLMZOF2). At the same time, another person that we interviewed from the Office said that in one of the centres they needed to intervene to prevent strong ethnic homogenisation. This interviewee pointed out that:

We try to avoid situations in which the centre was typically Chechen, that persons of no other nationality stay there, only Chechens. We had such a situation in one of the centres. The case was quite mediatised. In one of the schools attended by the children from our centre, there was some nasty incident. One of its consequences was the decision to try to change slightly the nationality structure in this centre and reduce the number of Chechens in favour of persons with other nationalities. (...) We succeeded in achieving this (PLMZOF3/4).

The amount of 'pocket money' given to asylum seekers while living in the Office-run centres was yet another frequently reoccurring point of criticism among the micro-level respondents and NGO representatives. One of those who had applied for international protection in Poland (PLMICH06) pointed out that she would like to cook for her children more often instead of receiving food from the canteen, but for 70 PLN pocket money per month, it was not possible. The very low amount of pocket money given to those who stay in the centres for foreigners also has an impact on their daily functioning outside the centres. An interesting observation about this was made by a social organisation respondent, who stressed:

The pocket money they get is terribly low, it is not enough for anything, for example, to travel by public transport. It forces people to travel without a ticket and exposes them to fines, penalties, etc. (PLMZSO1).

One important criticism from the NGO experts working with asylum seekers was that apart from food and shelter, the centres for foreigners offer very limited activities for their inhabitants. According to some of our interviewees from the meso level, this is linked not only with the legal and financial aspects of the functioning of these centres but also with the qualifications of their personnel. Some actors from the NGO sector complained that many employees of the centres do not have adequate qualifications to work at such premises. One of them argued, for instance:

people who are said to be social workers in the centres are not social workers. They are state officials who do not have social work tasks in their job descriptions. Their task is to run the centres and manage the resource, determine the number

of persons in each of them, forward official letters to and from asylum seekers. They are an intermediary between the Office and the persons living in the centres—they assess applications for the food equivalent for children and clothes and help to enrol children in schools, but they are officials. They are not social workers. They do not need to have a degree in social work. There is no career path at all for a social worker working with people seeking international protection (PLMZSO5/6).

As far as vulnerable people are concerned, as mentioned above, there is a fairly good legal basis for providing services for them (including housing) in the Law on Protection. The interviewed employees of the Office for Foreigners tend to hold an opinion similar to the following, which suggests that the special needs of vulnerable persons are addressed adequately. Our interviewee argued that:

There are not many persons of that kind (vulnerable). But there are special cases, for example, a [bedridden] person without a family. In such cases, we place them in healthcare facilities. For a disabled person, we also adjust the conditions. We look at which centre is appropriate. For example, for a person requiring dialysis, a hospital must be close because they must have dialysis every other day. And there is transportation arranged for such persons. (...) In every centre, we have a medical point—there is a doctor, a nurse—so I think that there is good care here (PLMZOF3/4).

The employee of the Office talked as well about other facilities for disabled persons that have been installed in recent years in the state-owned centres and how the Office tries to take various special needs of vulnerable persons into account when selecting new centres or prolonging the contracts with current ones (PLMZOF3/4).

Our interviewees from the NGO did not share the optimism of the employees of the Office in this respect. As emphasized by one of our respondents from a social organisation, despite the various categories of vulnerable people indicated by the Law on Protection and some positive actions such as the one described above, '[the vulnerable asylum seekers] are thrown into one bag. It's not the case that they are offered some kind of individual solution depending on the specific need they have (PLMZSO1).

The Helsinki Foundation, which monitors the asylum situation in Poland, also reports on the practices of dealing with vulnerable groups during the asylum procedure at various stages. In recent years, one of the problems frequently highlighted by the HFHR is a generally malfunctioning identification mechanism, as well as the issue of placing vulnerable groups in detention centres⁵⁰.

Before moving on to the next part of the report, it is important to mention a crucial role played by various NGOs in the assistance of asylum seekers and the perception of this help by some of our interviewees from the micro-level. From a wide range of NGOs involved in the help of asylum seekers in the centres or outside them⁵¹ some of the most frequently mentioned by

⁵⁰ For further information about this issue, see (Białas, et al., 2014) and (Pachocka & Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

⁵¹ These are, inter alia: Volunteer Centre in Lublin (Centrum Wolontariatu w Lublinie), Other Space Foundation (Fundacja Inna Przestrzeń), Dialogue Foundation (Fundacja Dialog), Foundation for Freedom (Fundacja dla Wolności), Halina Nieć Legal Aid Centre (Centrum Pomocy Prawnej im. Haliny

our interviewees were Ocalenie Foundation and the initiative With Bread and Salt. One of our micro-level respondents said:

After arriving in Poland, I was staying in Debak for seven months and meanwhile, I got a work permit. I was working officially, but to live in one room in the camp among those different nationalities it was very hard. It was not hygienic, not clean, not cultural, not that pleasing. Thank God that there exists such an organisation like the Ocalenie Foundation. (...) Those open and kind people trying to help us as much as possible. Thanks to this organisation (...) my children take additional exercises [and] I'm getting moral, psychological, legal support. Everything that is going on positive in my life now [is] thanks to the Ocalenie Foundation. I am saying it honestly because they gave me a house, household appliances, cleaning supplies. They help how they can, me and my family. I'm thankful to them (PLMICH13).

Another interviewee acknowledged the aid of the initiative With Bread and Salt (Chlebem i Solą):

We live in one of the districts of Warsaw. We live there to now. Why there? Because we didn't have any alternative. The foundation Chlebem i Solą posted an advertisement on the internet and then some people answered these ads. (...) There were two rooms with a kitchen, an old house, after renovation. So, we went there (PLMIUK20).

It is important to emphasize that not only secular but also religious organisations or faith-based organisations provide assistance to asylum seekers with housing or housing-related issues. For example, numerous Catholic organisations or those faith-based and indirectly linked with the Catholic Church have been actively helping people who have applied for international protection frequently, regardless of their religious affiliation, for many years. One other organisation worth mentioning, which has been providing such help to people coming from Chechnya who are seeking asylum, as well from other parts of the world, is the Volunteer Centre in Lublin (Centrum Wolontariatu w Lublinie). It was established in 1999 by young people and priests working in the Centre for the Youth Chaplaincy of the Lublin Archdiocese, set up by Archbishop Józef Życiński. The Volunteer Centre has cooperated with various local and national organisations providing various forms of support to people seeking asylum entering Poland through the so-called 'Polish Lampedusa' (as Father Puzewicz calls the border crossing in Brześć-Terespol between Belarus and Poland). This aid includes, among other things, accompaniment, integration activities and support in communication between foreigners and Polish institutions and local communities, as well as in solving specific problems (e.g., finding a flat, learning the city, and identifying destination points) to translation services and psychological support. The Volunteer Centre closely cooperates with the city and regional authorities in the implementation of these activities as well as with numerous current and past centres for foreigners (e.g., Biała Podlaska, Kolonia Chrubieszów, Bezwola, Łuków) in the region (Centrum Wolontariatu w Lublinie, n.d.)(MGN2).

Nieć), Caritas Poland (Caritas Polska), Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights (Helsińska Fundacja Praw Człowieka), Association for Legal Intervention (Stowarzyszenie Interwencji Prawnej), Ocalenie Foundation (Fundacja Ocalenie), Refugee.pl, Polish Hospitality Foundation (Fundacja Polska Gościnność), and With Bread and Salt (Chlebem i Solą).

As far as the Muslim organisations in Poland are concerned, they have not developed long-term assistance projects for asylum seekers and refugees but engaged in helping them on an ad hoc basis. The Tatar-led Muslim Religious Union has been actively helping Crimean Tatars who escaped Crimea in 2014 and sought asylum in Poland. Around 30 families who settled in the city of Białystok and nearby have received from the local Tatar community not only significant legal help, which facilitated their path to receiving some form of international protection, but also material and spiritual help.

The Muslim Religious Union also has been closely cooperating with Chechen imams in different parts of Poland (e.g., in Warsaw in the Chechen mosques on Budrycha and Skalnicka streets) providing religious education to Chechen children (Nalborczyk & Pędziwiatr, 2018).

The second-largest Muslim organisation in Poland, the Muslim League (LM), which runs the first purpose-built mosque in Warsaw, has been mainly helping asylum seekers and refugees as an important meeting place and institution that very often directs asylum seekers to the various civil society actors mentioned above (e.g., Ocalenie Foundation, Association for Legal Intervention) dealing with the support and integration of people under an international protection procedure. One of the groups of refugees for whom the mosque serves as an important meeting and conversation place about their own problems and life in Poland are Tajik women linked with the banned an-Nahda Party in Tajikistan.

2.2. Healthcare (Medical) Services

This section of the report focuses on the practices, experiences and perceptions of medical care provided to asylum seekers in Poland. It elaborates on sometimes divergent views about the provision of healthcare among our interviewees from the meso- and micro-levels.

Before we flesh out relevant results from our fieldwork, it is worth mentioning some general points concerning persons seeking asylum and healthcare provision. Medical care is a provision particularly important to persons who are frequently victims of all kinds of violence, which they have endured either in the countries of origin or while fleeing in search of security and safety. As such, they often require specialised medical treatment not only in regard to their physical health but also mental. Easier access to such treatment may sometimes be the reason why persons in reception with family members requiring constant medical assistance decide to stay in the centres for foreigners or live in their vicinity. Sometimes, though, they may decide to leave such centres and be closer to more specialised medical care facilities outside of them.

Here it is also important to mention that prolonged uncertainty about the result of the asylum procedure may also negatively influence the given asylum seeker's health condition. As one of our interviewees from Chechnya pointed out:

The only problem is that you live under constant pressure. If you receive a negative decision, a refusal, you can be deported back to Chechnya. So, people live in fear all the time. This is the worst thing. It can happen to you any time. I get up in the morning and I don't know what will happen today. I am always under pressure. I am afraid of being deported. This is how I feel. I went to see the psychologist. He sent me to a psychiatrist. I have problems with memory. I started to forget some events from my past. All the problems with my health are caused by constant stress that I have (PLMICH06).

Two other RESPOND, micro-level interviewees from Ukraine complained about the effect of the prolonged uncertainty on their health condition. One of them claimed that she had been in good mental condition before being placed in the detention centre for foreigners. She said: 'My depression started when I was detained in the detention centre in Biała Podlaska' (PLMIUK20). One of our male interviewees described the impact of the stress, related to awaiting the decision on refugee status, on the health of his partner in the following way: 'Whenever she's stressed, her skin gets red and, so to speak, she cannot get stressed' (PLMIUK16).

From the perspective of the Office for Foreigners' employees dealing with persons in reception, the healthcare provisions in Poland are sometimes of better quality than similar provisions in other countries of the European Union. One of them argued for instance:

When it comes to medical care, we are probably at one of the highest levels. We have the same care as for citizens. In similar centres in Finland, they have ladies who are between a nurse and a lifeguard. They only prescribe paracetamol to all the symptoms. If someone comes with toothache, then [they] get paracetamol for 2 weeks. If it does not help, then eventually [they] might be sent to the specialists but this is rare. Maybe for children healthcare is not limited, but for adults for sure (PLMZOF3/4).

The only problem mentioned in the interviews with the state officials dealing with migration issues was that sometimes it is necessary to wait for an extended period of time before one sees a specialist. As this issue concerns all persons living in Poland who have access to medical care through the National Health Fund (NHF, in Polish *Narodowy Fundusz Zdrowia – NFZ*), it was in a way taken for granted. Although, one of our meso-level interviewees stated: 'I think that our foreigners [asylum seekers], as a result of having their medical appointments booked commercially, have shorter waiting periods' (PLMZOF3/4). The issue of difficult access to specialists was, however, not mentioned by the employees of the Office for Foreigners.

It was clearly seen though by the studied beneficiaries of the medical services, that is persons seeking asylum in Poland. For example, one of our interviewees from the micro-level had the following observation about healthcare provision:

I had a problem with my nasal septum and they told me the wait is around two years. I decided not to do it and will probably go to a paid one. (...) If we are talking about paid private clinics – it's very fast and efficient. If we are talking about the free, state medical system, it is good but you have to wait a long time (PLMICH15).

In this context, another asylum seeker said:

The only problem in Poland is medicine. (...) I went to hospital in Brest in order to have an appointment with the endocrinologist because you have to wait for too long for such an appointment in Warsaw (PLMICH04).

This interviewee also claimed that, for such a visit with the specialist, she had to pay about 80 PLN and the amount was not reimbursed to her.

One of our interviewees was even not aware of the fact that persons in reception have access to specialised medical care. She claimed that:

They were not referring us to specialists. We were maybe not entitled to such services in this period before the refugee decision. We started seeing doctors only when we obtained refugee status (PLMIr28).

On the whole, however, our micro-level respondents who were direct beneficiaries of the healthcare provision spoke positively about it. One of the interviewees who lived in the centre for foreigners pointed out that:

The medical doctor was available every day. It was possible to come every day. There were no problems with drugs. When there was no possibility to do everything in the Centre, she gave us a referral to the hospital in Biała Podlaska. Once there was a situation when the kids got pneumonia, with fever and so on... So, we went to the hospital with them (...) and after a week everything was OK (PLMIUk16).

Among the interviewees who spoke highly of the healthcare provision were two asylum seekers from Syria accommodated in the initial phase of their reception in one of the centres for foreigners. One of them said:

In the camp there was an excellent doctor with great morals and his behaviour was very nice. He used to receive us very comfortably and provided us with the proper medication in the camp (PLMISy24).

The only issue which they pointed out were the inadequate linguistic skills of the doctors treating patients in the centre for foreigners:

(...) my wife knows English, she used to speak to the doctor in English, but he was the only person who used to speak English in the camp (PLMISy24).

Another interviewee accounted for the specialised medical assistance he received from the ophthalmologist in the following way:

You are sick. For example, you have a problem with your eye. The doctor sees it, tries to treat it...Then she told me that next month she will come and see the eye, if it's not good then I would have to have an operation. Then I go, God helps (PLMIr27).

Some of our interviewees from the micro-level who expressed appreciation for the medical care provision spoke highly of not only the assistance with physical health but also mental health. One of the asylum seekers from the Middle East with whom we spoke in the course of the research pointed out that:

At the beginning, when I arrived, I was in a very bad psychological state and then they brought me a doctor, and thank God, now I am under treatment of some psychiatrist (PLMIJe29).

The most critical assessment of healthcare provision to asylum seekers was collected during our meso-level interviews with actors from the NGO sector. In the remaining part of this section of the report, we will shed light on some of the most frequently mentioned issues by these interviewees. One of the positive elements of the healthcare provision that they could see was slightly easier access to the general practitioners as compared to the same access among wider Polish society. They also believed that access to the basic type of medical assistance was assured for asylum seekers adequately. One of these interviewees, for example, pointed out:

It is true that sometimes it is easier for asylum seekers to get to general practitioners, in the sense that there are shorter queues, because it goes through a different path, or that they receive medications free of charge. On the other hand, it's hard to expect that people who have no right to work will be able to pay for them (PLMZSO1).

As mentioned above, the most frequently raised criticism of limited access to specialised medical care could also be discerned among our interviewees from the micro-level. According to our interviewees from social organisations, this access has been increasingly restricted since the contract for medical services for persons in reception shifted from the Central Clinical Hospital to the private company Petra Medica. One of our interviewees pointed out:

Since then [moment when the contract was signed with the private company], we have been observing a deterioration of these medical services. People complain about lower availability, that they are often sent to semi-specialists who are not specialists in a given field (PLMZSO1).

According to our interlocutors from the NGO sector, who remain in constant contact with asylum seekers in Poland and who assist them in various aspects of life including healthcare, when medical services were provided to persons in refugee procedures by the Clinical Hospital – that is up to 2015 – they had better access to specialists and specialised treatments. Our interviewee from one of the organisations assisting asylum seekers in accessing medical care claimed that:

Another issue is the reluctance of performing medical operations that are not related to saving lives. We had the example of a child who had an eyesight defect. When this child came to Poland, probably 5 years ago, a medical diagnosis suggested that this eyesight defect could be operated and that the surgery gave a 70% chance that the child would regain 100% vision. After 5 years, there would be a 30% or less chance of success because these defects become worse and develop. In the end, the parents left the country with the child (PLMZSO2).

Our interviewees from the social organizations also complained about deteriorating access to specialised therapies. One of them, for example, pointed out that:

Now it works much worse on many levels but especially when it comes to providing such often life-saving treatment of a very specialised type of HIV or treatment of hepatitis C (...). We have patients who have been refused these treatments for some years. They are sent, but not to these specialised institutions, but to some others. Such mock steps are implemented (...). And the Office is also starting to force Petra Medica to comply with the contract (PLMZSO1).

One group of vulnerable asylum seekers who face particular difficulties with adequate medical care in Poland are persons with disabilities. An interviewee from the NGO sector observed that:

As for people with disabilities – I often saw people from the Office for Foreigners who were doing their best to provide for such persons. For example, there is no clear path for how a person who is moving on a wheelchair or who needs crutches should be treated. How these crutches or wheelchairs should be arranged. In general, the system of rehabilitation and support for people with disabilities in Poland is weak and in the reception system is even weaker (PLMZSO5/6).

For the aforementioned reason, the Office informed, on its website at the end of November 2019, that it is currently implementing a project of additional support for asylum seekers in Poland. It includes, among others, elements of material support. With the intention of distributing it among asylum seekers, the Office purchased equipment such as: 10 crutches and 10 wheelchairs, an assortment for removing barriers for disabled people, 225 prams, 225 vouchers for baby items (e.g. diapers, clothes, cosmetics, hygiene items), 2,100 vouchers for school supplies (including stationery, backpacks, sportswear) and 100 packages of medical and hygienic articles (Office for Foreigners, 2019d).

Our interviewees from the NGO sector also pointed out several weaknesses in the current medical care provided to asylum seekers in regard to mental health. One of the basic problems linked with this provision has to do with the fact that psychologists, who may play an important role in the refugee procedure, are not necessarily viewed as neutral when they are being employed by the Office for Foreigners. This issue was mentioned, for instance, by the following interviewee who argued that:

In theory, there are psychologists in all centres for foreigners but in practice it is usually one person who works in several centres. These psychologists travel between the centres. Let's say they are, on average, in the given centre once a week. They are employed by the Office for Foreigners, which means that not everyone in the centres will perceive them as neutral and independent persons (PLMZSO1).

Another issue frequently mentioned in the meso-level interviews concerned the scope and frequency of psychological assistance⁵². One said: 'This psychological help, especially such that is adequate to the needs of people with post-traumatic stress disorder, was always totally insufficient' (PLMZSO1).

The NGO sector has been playing a crucial role in supporting the Office for Foreigners in providing such specialised psychological care to asylum seekers. The social organisations help the OF address not only the challenge of frequency of psychological assistance but also its quality (PLMZSO5/6). One of the initiatives that was mentioned in this regard by our meso-level respondents was the project 'Alter Camp'. As part of it, one of the NGOs working with asylum seekers brought additional psychologists to one of the centres for foreigners (Czerwony Bór) three times a week plus some volunteers, interpreters and mentors. This project significantly improved this form of medical assistance in one of the centres for a short period of time (PLMZSO2).

Yet, another problem linked to the provision of physical and mental health assistance for asylum seekers mentioned by one of our interviewees had to do with the lack of interpreters. One of NGO interviews described it in the following way:

There is no access to translations. If they are available, then one needs to wait for them for very long time and they are provided for 1, 2, 3 psychological consultations. I also refer to physical medical assistance because (...). There are no translations where they are crucial. Asylum seekers are often put out of the door. They come to a medical examination but because of lack of communication, the person who was waiting for his/her appointment with the doctor is asked to leave the medical office because there is no translation provided to the doctor.

⁵² For further information, see (Pachocka & Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

The doctor says that there is no way to communicate, so he/she will not carry out the examination (PLMZSO5/6).

Our meso-level respondents also mentioned educational and professional issues linked with the work of persons providing healthcare assistance to asylum seekers. One of them interestingly pointed out that:

Most of these people work on junk contracts, they have no job stability. There is no specialised educational path for medical staff or for psychological staff – whether as part of formal education, studies or vocational courses, which would then translate into some promotion to specialise in working with such people. In the hospitals, we can specialise as a nurse or instrumentalist in neonatology, surgery, etc. In psychology, we can specialise in addiction psychology, we have a career path, in a psychiatric hospital, as a school psychologist. There are career paths. When it comes to working with asylum seekers, because there are no permanent positions for this medical staff – there is no career path. There is no career path, so people have no competence. They have no competence, so they get frustrated (PLMZSO5/6).

As far as vulnerable persons are concerned, experts point out that in spite of some improvements, including the elaboration of screening questionnaires to be used by psychologists in reception centres, even the identification of vulnerable persons remains a challenge. Specialised treatment for victims of torture or traumatised asylum seekers is not available in practice in Poland because of the lack of qualified psychologists and therapists specialising in treating trauma, especially in an intercultural context. At the same time, the assistance provided by specialists working for non-governmental organisations is not sufficient to fill the systemic gaps, such as the lack of psychotherapy available under general healthcare provisions (Szczepanik, 2017) (Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d.).

2.3. Early Access to Education

This section of the report examines the actual practice of the access of asylum seekers to education in Poland. It aims to present findings of the analysis of the micro- and meso-level data with relation to early access of asylum seeking children to school and language education and educational offer (in practice, limited to Polish language courses) provided to adult asylum seekers. First, the results of the micro- and meso-level interviews analysis are presented with regard to children and then adult asylum seekers. In addition, we focus particularly on both, shortcomings and good practices of the reception system in the area of education.

2.3.1. Asylum-Seeking Children in Schools

In September 2019, about 850 asylum-seeking children attended 110 public schools in Poland (see Table 9). Most of them (490) stayed in centres for foreigners (reception and accommodation centres), predominantly in Łuków, Czerwony Bór, and Linin. With regard to nationality, the majority of them were citizens of Russia (72%) followed by Ukraine (10%) and Tajikistan (6%) (Office for Foreigners, 2019e).

Based on their year of birth, 600 asylum-seeking children (70%) were entitled to primary education, 150 could attend secondary schools (18%), and 90 qualified for pre-school education, or so called 'zero-class' (10%). However, it needs to be mentioned that the year of

birth is not always the only criterion considered when assigning an asylum-seeking child to a specific class or type of school ('zero-class', primary or secondary school). In each case, the individual's history of education is examined and issues such as gaps in education or other relevant factors are taken into consideration (Office for Foreigners, 2019e).

Table 9 Asylum-seeking children (aged 6-17) in schools in Poland

Country of origin	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Russia	460	496	702	449	354	579	656	579	613
Ukraine	1	2	5	252	392	323	182	93	83
Tajikistan	0	0	0	0	0	59	64	40	50
Other	98	160	185	143	141	111	116	111	104
Total	559	658	892	844	887	1072	1018	823	850

Source: own elaboration by RESPOND team in Poland based on data received from the Office for Foreigners.

The number of children in subsequent years beginning from 2011 reflects the general trend of the increase in the number of asylum seekers until 2016 and then, since 2016, a slight decrease. The countries of origin with the most numerous asylum seekers are similar for both groups of adults and children. What is significant is that the biggest group of asylum-seeking children are Chechens who have been raised, in majority, in the Muslim religion and in a non-Slavic language (Chechen).

Despite the obligation to send children to school, it is not clearly stated how much time parents have in order to fulfil this obligation after arriving in Poland. According to a brochure from the Office for Foreigners given to asylum seekers, the accommodation centre helps with signing up children to attend the nearest school. Children are provided with school books and accessories. A child who attends school receives a cash equivalent of 9 PLN (2.15 EUR) per day for food. The Office recommends parents order food for their children in the school cafeteria (Office for Foreigners, 2015).

An asylum-seeking woman told us she had a problem with her children's enrolment to school:

I went to the office here and asked about that, but they told me that the teacher would come to the camp and teach my children. She has to determine whether my children can go to school. She told me that they could go to school. The only problem is with the language, but she told me she would help them with Polish. I have already written two letters on this issue. Now we are waiting (PLMIC06).

According to a social organisation employee, the registration of asylum-seeking children to school has been deliberately delayed recently:

There is such an attempt to push the education of foreign children to the [reception and accommodation] centres. Specific people who come to us report this to me. But at the same time, they ask me not to do anything about it because they are, for example, people who live in Dębak, which is a reception centre, so in theory they should quickly be moved to another centre. [...] So I have my hands tied a bit because someone comes to me and says that the child is not going to school for the third month. I ask if there are classes in Dębak and I hear 'yes, there is Polish every day'. I am asking about other subjects and I hear that there is only Polish. At the beginning of this school year, I called the Department of Social Assistance [at the Office of Foreigners] and asked why these children are not sent to school,

they said 'the regulation has not yet been issued, but it will come soon, we do not know yet what the basis is, but now something will be announced, it's for the good of these children, that it won't be such a shock that they don't know the language'. In short, the idea was that during these three months these children would have school program implemented in the centres. And if they learn a language a little, they go to school. I understand it in situations when someone arrives in April or June and then all July and August should be mashed in the centres. However, I do not understand it when someone arrives in September when the school year begins and then it is really better for such a child to join in December when the class is playing, especially when we are talking about children who would go to the first grade and who would learn very quickly. Especially if all people tell me 'yes, children attend Polish in Dębak, but not other subjects, it is only Polish' (PLMZSO1).

Another respondent from Chechnya admitted that sending children to school was presented to her as a condition for receiving a financial allowance:

I: Did you send your children to school? R: Yes, there was a school outside the camp. I sent my son there, when he was 4 and I sent my daughter there. There was a Chechen woman there who took care of them. The teacher said that they were very good and obedient children. I: How did you find out where to send children to school? R: The social worker told me that I should have sent children to school, otherwise I wouldn't have received the money for them (PLMICH01).

However, from the perspective of a school practitioner, asylum-seeking children should have some time for acclimatisation after arriving:

I think it is important for the education system that these children who come to the centre have time to acclimatise, to adapt to a place where they are, adapt to the Polish language and culture. Before you go to school, you should know that you have to have shoes, that you need to behave well during lessons, you need to have a sports outfit, pencils, etc. Now, it's easier with textbooks, because there are textbooks at school. You have to make an effort to get them, but they are available (PLMZP3).

The above opinion is shared by a practitioner from an NGO active in the field of reception:

[Asylum seeking] kids should not follow the normal course of education. First you should prepare them for this, teach Polish. Now, we have a programme that supports refugee children with such a tutor. If a child does not speak Polish well, he/she is behind other children in all subjects. This is normal (PLMZSO2).

A local governor who we talked to openly admitted that the local government had lobbied for changes in the school obligation for asylum-seeking children so they would have time to adapt and learn Polish:

We requested, with the support of the Head of the Office for Foreigners and the Ministry of the Interior and Administration for the introduction of an adaptation period so that the child does not go to school directly. Unless he/she knows Polish and it will be good for him/her. We thought of an adaptation period that would last from several weeks to half a year, during which time the child could learn the basics of the language, our culture, even history, and rules of behaviour. This

would allow her/him to enter the school community in a very flexible and beneficial way. But unfortunately, the Ministry [of National Education] did not accept this (PLMZLG1).

In the initial period of stay in a reception or accommodation centre, if a child has adaptation problems, a psychologist, a Polish language teacher, or a centre employee will work with the child. If necessary, the assistance is supported by specialised organisations or institutions (also NGOs). Employees of the DSA of the Office for Foreigners, both working in the centres and delegated from the Office headquarters, regularly meet with the management and employees of schools attended by children residing in centres for foreigners. The purpose of these meetings is to identify the most important areas of cooperation between the school and the centre and to eliminate possible conflicts or disputes (Hajduk, 2018).

However, the school practitioner expressed objections to the practice of cooperation between the school and the Office for Foreigners. The practitioner complained especially about the lack of information transfer between institutions:

I think it would be good if those institutions examining [asylum] applications took into account what people living close to them [asylum seekers] think about these people here. So, that such an opinion from a school saying whether these children integrate, if their parents want anything, whether they are completely apathetic or whether they hate Poles, because sometimes it happens, or if they promise to stay in Poland at all weighs more than it weighs now. Maybe such greater cooperation. Now, GDPR [General Data Protection Regulation] has entered into force. We once had a problem with getting any data about those pupils, where they were born. They sometimes don't know where they were born, what the place is. Parents did not have any documents. This transfer of documentation or information—we only get the child's name and parents' names, and we must get the rest by ourselves. Now, these parents will bring TZTC, a temporary foreigner's identity certificate. Sometimes a parent has a child's birth certificate. But once these children came without parents and we registered them by ourselves, we talked to them by ourselves (PLMZP3).

Schools located near reception centres often deal with a high concentration of foreign children in one class. According to the principle of regionalisation, a school headmaster is obliged to accept all children residing in the area of its responsibility, namely the area surrounding the school. The mentioned challenge was faced by the school in Coniew, which in principle should accept all children residing in the accommodation centre in nearby Linin. However, in order to prevent too many foreign children in just this one school, the local government in Góra Kalwaria decided to divide this group across various schools located in the commune. As a result, the children went to schools in Coniew, Dobiesz, Czaplonek, Czachówek, and Cendrowice. This solution was possible thanks to an agreement with the other schools, which, understanding the difficult situation of Coniew, decided to take in some of the children. It was also necessary to obtain the consent of the parents of asylum-seeking children, who so far have not opposed the use of such a solution, especially since the commune provided access to all facilities. However, if one of the parents opposes such a system and demands that the child be placed in a circuit school, he/she must be accepted (Commissioner for Human Rights, 2016, p. 30).

One of our respondents, a local government representative, explained to us the reasons for implementing the solution described above:

We have adopted the principle that there should be no more than two foreign children in one class. I had situations, for example, in which our village schools, which are small establishments, and in one peripheral school in [place name] there was a situation that there were more foreign children than Polish children in one class. This spurred public protest, parental protests. Therefore, we have now adopted the standard that, depending on the number of children who meet the school obligation, we send them to different schools. At the moment, there are probably five schools where these children fulfil their school duty (PLMZLG1).

As further explained by a school practitioner, the action was coordinated by the local government and the schools and the two institutions have lobbied for country-wide regulations in this matter:

Participating in various conferences, in the Ministry or at the Ombudsman where I was invited, or the mayor, we always raised the issue of the possibility of dividing the children into different schools. Until 2016, it was accepted that children from the [reception or accommodation] centre should go to the school closest to the centre, i.e., within the perimeter of where the centre is located. Sometimes it happened that 50 or 100 [asylum-seeking] children went to one school. Most of the children were here because this is our school circuit. The commune started to do it almost from the beginning—since 2005 they have started to split up the children. They stated that if our school had been under the burden of such a large group of foreigners, it would have practically ceased to exist (PLMZP3).

The solution described above seems to be a rather exceptional practice, which is confirmed by the following practitioner from an NGO:

They have the school duty—they must send the child to school. This is not always enforced. But attendance is rather good. But they often have no choice of which school to send their children. It happens that children from one centre go to one school and it is not always good (PLMZSO2).

The problem is seen not only by the communes and school administrations but also by the asylum seekers themselves. One woman from Chechnya decided to send her children to a distant school so they could have more contact with Polish kids and the language:

My children have been attending school for one year. They also got used to life in Poland. When we came to Poland, they were very nervous. Now they are not. They go to school [number] close to [name] railway station. (...) My children go to a different school than all of the refugee children. I transferred them there this year and they learn Polish. They communicate with Polish children. They have small classes. There are 11 students in the class. I have to get up at 6.00 a.m. to go to school with them and later I have to bring them back from school, but it is important for them to study well. The school, where all the refugees' children go is close to here but there is no discipline there and there are a lot of children (PLMICH02).

According to our meso- and micro-level data, language and cultural barriers seem to be the biggest challenge in the reception of asylum-seeking children in the education system. An additional hampering factor is the educational gaps stemming from the conflict situation in the countries of origin and the long journey to the host country.

A Chechen woman told us about her 7-year-old daughter who was attending the local pre-school and for whom the biggest barrier was language:

She is at pre-school. She is doing quite well. Her Polish is not good enough but she speaks a little. Her teacher says that if she learns Polish a little better, she won't have any problems. She likes music, she likes drawing. She is doing well. If she learns Polish a little better, they will transfer her to first grade, because now she is at pre-school (PLMICH03).

Our respondent from Kazakhstan complained about the lack of care for children with special needs, as her son has problems with articulation:

R: My son has problems with speaking. He needs a speech therapist and my daughter attends kindergarten. I: Is there an opportunity to have an appointment with a speech therapist? R: Not yet. Maybe later (PLMIKa30).

In addition to communication problems, asylum-seeking children often face cultural differences to which they are expected to adapt. The burden of adaptation is put not only on these children but also on their teachers, who have to explain to them the new social rules:

These children from Grozny or from larger cities knew civilisation. But those children who grew up in the Caucasus mountains, in small villages—and we also had children who were hidden somewhere in the mountains in some houses or somewhere in the attics for fear of gangs, that they would not be killed or that children would not be kidnapped—they were at risk as someone who had long developmental delays because of it. Such a child comes to school and here suddenly hears a buzzer, some rules he/she does not understand. We have developed special rules in Russian for these pupils on how to behave at school: 'You sit on the bench. You answer when the teacher asks you. You can ask questions to the teacher. Don't bring sharp objects to school. Bring shoes to change into. You change your clothes for physical exercise. You don't hit your friends. You don't kick them. You settle things through the tutor, not by yourself.' It was not an extract from the statute. These were simple, short sentences to make these children understand. That was at the beginning; later, of course, these children adapted (PLMZP3).

In order to overcome these barriers, the Office for Foreigners provides Polish language lessons for children in the reception and accommodation centres, which include help with homework and compensatory classes, as well as classes preparing newcomers to study in Polish schools. The teacher conducting the classes stays in touch with the schools attended by the children, which allows for the exchange of information on their progress and problems in learning and gives the opportunity to adapt the conducted classes to the needs of the children. In addition, the Office provides the pupils with textbooks and accessories (so-called school layettes) if they do not receive them in schools (Hajduk, 2018).

As part of the project 'Polish for a good beginning' (*Polski na dobry start*) carried out by the Office in cooperation with the foundation Linguae Mundi, a curriculum of Polish as a foreign language was developed for asylum-seeking children who have just enrolled in schools in Poland. As part of it, a teacher's handbook containing lesson plans and educational materials for pupils was prepared. As the Office for Foreigners explained, the programme takes into account the specific communication needs of children applying for international protection,

including realistic and socio-cultural content. It also includes the acquisition of basic skills, as well as simulations of communication situations at school (Office for Foreigners, 2017).

Despite the social assistance in education provided by the Office for Foreigners, the education of asylum-seeking children poses a challenge to the institutions, as was admitted by an employee of the Office:

These children come from different environments, from different cultures and do not know Polish at all, so it is quite difficult to put them into the Polish education system. After arriving here, of course, they have classes in Polish at the centres. They have to attend school, so they must go to school. Here, too, there is the problem with classifying children into the appropriate class, because, apart from the fact that it is a different culture, a different system, etc., and the lack of language, there is also the fact that in their own countries of origin these children also had received a different education or they hadn't attended school at all. It also happens here that children of very different ages go to one class, which seems to me to be a very difficult situation (PLMZOF2).

At this point, it needs to be added that new solutions have been implemented since 2010 in Poland aiming at the integration of foreign children into the Polish education system, namely teacher's assistants (cultural assistants), introduced in 2010, and preparatory classes (welcome classes), introduced in 2017. Since both are instruments related to the integration of migrant children, including asylum-seeking and refugee children, they will be analysed in the forthcoming RESPOND Poland country report on integration.

2.3.2. Access to Education for Adults

As mentioned earlier, asylum seekers living in the centres for foreigners are provided with Polish language classes organised by the Office for Foreigners. Participation in the language classes in the accommodation centres is not obligatory. Despite the introduction of some incentives in 2015, i.e., prizes⁵³ for the highest attendance and/or the best results in the group, attendance has remained low. According to a survey by the Institute of Public Affairs, in 2016 only 45% of accommodation centre residents attended the Polish classes and of them, only half were attending classes always or very often (Baczyński-Sielaczek, 2016).

The reasons for the low attendance of the language classes varied. Among the individual reasons were traumatic experiences that precluded a Chechen woman from focusing on learning:

Sometimes, I attend these classes. I don't have patience for that, that's why I started to see a psychologist to calm down a little bit. I can't concentrate on what the teacher is saying. I am thinking about my situation all the time (PLMICH03).

Another Chechen woman could not attend the language classes regularly because she had to take care of her baby:

I speak a little Polish. I attended the course, when I was in the camp, but I had a little baby, which was very much connected with me and I couldn't attend the

⁵³ These are material prizes of a didactic value of 100 PLN for an adult with the highest attendance and at the same time the best learning results in a given semester in each centre or for two people with the same results of prizes worth 50 PLN each.

course all the time. Then I studied for one month and a half and I started to speak and to understand. Now, I will start the course again from the 18th of February (PLMIC08).

In fact, lack of childcare is a serious impediment to mothers of young children in participation in the classes. It is worth adding that providing childcare is not included in the conditions of tenders for the organisation of language classes announced by the Office for Foreigners.

The words of another respondent shed more light on other reasons for the low attendance of Chechen women:

'There were a lot of women from Chechnya, they didn't attend the classes at all because they always have a lot of kids, and they didn't have time. They spent all the time in the kitchen. Because there was no in-house [food service], they gave money for food, so one had to cook by himself/herself' (PLMIUK19).

To some of our respondents, the Polish course seemed to be focused too much on theory than on practice. One Ukrainian woman attended classes in the accommodation centre but practice was more important to her:

R: You know, it is important to talk a lot, to listen. And when I started learning Polish I didn't talk. So, after a couple of months I started using Polish words. And before, when you only listen to some grammatical rules, it is not very good. I: So you needed practice, right? The classes alone were not enough. R: Yes, yes. I: And did you find an opportunity to practice? To talk with people? R: Yes, yes. We talked with the guards at the centre. I: And when you walked out to the grocery? R: Yes, we were going, yes, also. For example: 'Kupuję' ['I'm buying'] or '20 dg kielbasy' ['20 decagram of sausage']. I spoke using very short sentences. But for longer talks in Polish, there were opportunities in the centre with guards, with people in the office. Although in the office they spoke Russian, since there were a lot of Chechens. Chechens don't speak other languages, they start speaking Polish after some time. So, the girls in the office spoke Polish (PLMIUK19).

According to our respondent from the Office for Foreigners, the Office enforced some adjustment measures in order to attract more people to the Polish classes, but the results were far from expectations:

At that time, we had recommendations to take some action to increase this turnout. We have again increased the conditions of conduct and attractiveness. But, unfortunately, it didn't work because we increased the number of hours there. It appeared to us new people can join a language group formed three months before, so we divided groups into some levels so that there were more groups. But this also did not bring any results (PLMZOF3/4).

The latter respondent guessed that the motivation for learning/non-learning the language is directly related to the working plans of asylum seekers:

It seems to me that maybe the Ukrainians are starting a job right now. After six months, if they do not have a decision issued, they can apply for a certificate that they can take up a job. Later, these language skills are needed (PLMZOF3/4).

Another respondent, a practitioner, expressed his/her opinion that the classes of Polish language for asylum seekers should be mandatory:

They are provided with Polish language classes, but almost nobody attends them. This is unattractive and they are not obliged to do so, but in my opinion they should be. If someone applies for refugee status, wants to integrate and wants to stay in Poland, he/she should be forced, however, during the procedure—especially since it is very long—to learn the Polish language. But not that someone comes three times during the first two months and then abandons the classes completely (PLMZP1).

On the other hand, according to a representative of a social organisation, it is the central government that bears the responsibility for the lack of motivation among asylum seekers to learn the language:

My impression is that nothing is done systematically when it comes to the operation of the state when it comes to adult language education because children have school duty and they can learn and they actually learn if their parents watch over them. (...) As for adults, we leave it to the adults themselves and they have no incentive to learn. Their future in Poland does not depend on whether they know the language or not, unless this procedure lasts long enough that someone would say far-sightedly, that in four years when I would speak good Polish, and someone would like to expel me, I will say that there are humanitarian reasons, that I have integrated myself and I know the language. But people don't think about it right now. If they are not asked to learn, the system of learning incentives was not created, then they lose a year, two years. The language is especially important (PLMZSO3).

The micro-level interviews confirmed that one of the factors hindering participation in the language classes is residing in a private accommodation, outside the centre for foreigners. Since language learning is not obligatory during the asylum procedure, asylum seekers do not have the motivation to look for opportunities to learn Polish on their own:

I: And you didn't have any lessons in the centre for foreigners? R: Well, at the centre ... I used to go to at the beginning, there was an alphabet, but then we went to this private apartment, and then to Warsaw. I: And here in Warsaw? R: I don't remember, maybe I didn't get the information, there was the course for money (PLMIUk18).

Out of our 30 respondents, only one said that Polish classes were unavailable in the accommodation centre where she had stayed. However, she managed to find a free language course organised by an NGO:

You know when I've been in [name of the city], I asked the director about language classes and she told me they didn't have it in the camp. After I arrived to Warsaw, I asked a friend about classes. She told me, there are language classes at the Foundation, and I signed up there. Then, I couldn't attend the classes because I was working (PLMICH14).

A significant finding from the micro-level interviews was that asylum seekers who regularly attend Polish language classes in the centre for foreigners were satisfied with the results:

I already write in Polish and read in Polish because a Polish language teacher came to the centre for foreigners and I attended the classes. I was in an advanced

group. So, five people in the beginners group and 1-2 people in the advanced group (PLMIUk19).

R: I am now studying the language here in the camp, in Dębak, and there is a slight improvement. I: But are there teachers who are supervising you in a course?

R: Yes, here, there is one teacher, but she is, I mean, she comes on Mondays, Tuesdays, and Thursdays... (PLMIJe29).

I attended Polish lessons in spring and I am attending them now. I am doing well. Yes, I am trying to speak Polish. My daughter speaks Polish in the kindergarten. I asked them in the kindergarten to speak only Polish to her (PLMIKa30).

The above quotes by three respondents whose native languages (Ukrainian, Arabic, and Kazakh) belong to different language families (Slavic, Semitic, and Turkic) prove that language proximity is not the only motivation or de-motivation factor behind attending the Polish classes.

The micro- and meso-level material proved that there is no institutionally organised vocational education provided for adult asylum seekers. A respondent from the Office for Foreigners told us that vocational courses used to be organised in the past but they were stopped after the projects were finished: 'There were vocational courses in Linin. To this day, there are rooms left over from the project. (...) the project ended, the rooms were left. Nobody conducts any classes' (PLMZOF3/4).

Another employee of the Office for Foreigners argued that vocational courses are not considered to be reception practice, rather a pre-integration activity, which is the main reason why the vocational courses are not offered to asylum seekers:

(...) vocational courses would rather be a part of integration activities, and by assumption, those activities that are provided in the centres are pre-integration activities. In fact, there were periods when funds were obtained and vocational courses conducted in cooperation with NGOs. However, in fact, the Office takes a stance that these are integration activities that are implemented after obtaining a final positive decision [of receiving international protection] and they are more on the side of regional Family Assistance Centres, which take care of foreigners after they have obtained protection. There were such activities, but in fact we do not interpret them as a basic scope of care and social assistance (MGN2R9).

A representative of a social organisation stated that vocational education should be provided for youth aged 16-17, since after granting international protection they will face the biggest difficulties in finding a job:

What is definitely lacking is vocational education for young people who fell out a bit due to various turbulence related to the reason for leaving their country of origin, who sometimes fell out of the education system and have large gaps. There are 16-17-year-olds who have not finished primary school yet. And now the question is whether to force them to register in the primary school with much younger children or what else? And here there is a lack of such programmes targeted specifically at such people, perhaps directing them to some vocational education, and in any case a different individual rhythm so that they can make up for it. Because if a 16-year-old has completed the 2nd or 3rd grade of primary school, he/she will not go to this junior high school or high school because he will only be sitting like at a Turkish sermon for linguistic reasons. They are often children who

fall out altogether—they don't attend classes, nobody checks them, they are forced into primary schools and this is then a huge problem when it comes to their later presence on the labour market (PLMZSO1).

In general, the lack of vocational education and professional trainings for asylum seekers seems to be one of the biggest shortcomings of the reception system in the area of education. The differentiation made by the Office for Foreigners between the stages of reception and pre-integration, which is not confirmed by the literature, seems to be artificial and an excuse for not implementing such solutions.

2.4. Early Access to the Labour Market

This section of the report examines early access of asylum seekers to the labour market in Poland, that is, from the submission of an application for international protection to the moment of receiving the final decision. For this purpose, we analysed legal acts, official documents, and the literature as well micro- and meso-level interviews. Among the 30 interviewed respondents, only six confirmed their working experience during the asylum procedure in Poland and only four of them worked legally (three Chechens and one Ukrainian). In addition, the other two received money from small jobs performed in the reception centre to increase their 'pocket money' or undocumented jobs working in agriculture. From the meso-level in-depth interviews, most crucial for issues related to early access to the labour market were those conducted with representatives from the Office for Foreigners, practitioners, and NGOs.

While discussing job-related issues in Poland during the interviews, our micro-level respondents usually used the expression 'work permit', even if a work permit *per se* does not apply to them according to the Polish law. Often, they had in mind the certificate allowing them to work within the territory of the Republic of Poland. This can be illustrated by the statement of one interviewee from Kazakhstan: 'I could work in a beauty salon. I found a place where they would give me a job, but I need to have a work permit and a residence permit' (PLMIKa30). There was also the case of a Ukrainian migrant who, despite having this certificate, still referred to it as a work permit: 'And then, after half a year, there was information that we could apply for a work permit. (...) I found [a job] in a bistro towards downtown. I started working there' (PLMIUk18).

This misunderstanding of Polish law has further consequences. One of the practitioners (PLMZOF1) pointed out that asylum seekers try to receive a work permit from voivodes⁵⁴, although they are not supposed to, as this legal body is responsible for issuing work permits only for regular migrants. Further, the practitioner described this situation in the following words: '(...) these certificates are issued by us, but partly they [the asylum seekers] turn to voivodes, not to the Office' (PLMZOF1). In addition, another official from the Office pointed out that 'not all asylum seekers are aware that they can apply for this certificate' (PLMZOF2).

This issue of the awareness of legal conditions influences not only asylum seekers' job opportunities but the relation between asylum seekers and potential employers as well. From the point of view of employers what is of key importance is the lack of information regarding the validation deadline of the certificate of one of their employees. According to Polish law, the 'certificate' is valid until the decision on the asylum application is final. However, only asylum seekers are informed about this decision and they do not have to hand it over to the

⁵⁴ A governor of a voivodship (province, region) in Poland.

employer. Therefore, the employers do not know the details concerning the possible duration of employment of a person who is 'in the asylum procedure'. This problem was raised by one official from the Office for Foreigners:

These (...) employers do not know, and very often we have phone calls with a request to specify what it means and when the decision will be final. In fact, the foreigner has a certificate but if he [or she] does not go to the employer and does not tell him [or her] that 'Excuse me, but I just got the decision and it became final on that and that day', the employer does not really know if he [she] employs the foreigner legally or illegally, as there is no such information. These employers call from time to time and ask. We cannot provide such information to outsiders, so it is only a matter of whether the foreigner will tell them or not (PLMZOF2).

In this regard, some researchers underline that many employers do not know that the certificate with a temporary ID document gives asylum seekers the right to work or do not want to employ them for only a short time (i.e., up to six months, as the employers are unaware that the procedure will take longer than the validity of a temporary ID document). In that case, the certificates lose their practical significance (Klaus, 2017a). Further, as stressed by Abdoulvakchabova (2012) some employers are not willing to get into the legal issues and prefer to employ foreigners without a contract. This exposes employees to the risk of non-compliance with any employee rights and is also related to the deception of foreigners, non-payment of remuneration for work performed, and fictitious contracts.

The asylum seekers develop different strategies concerning their access to the labour market. Some are simply passive and do not react in a special way. They stay in the centre for foreigners and rely on allowances, especially those that have difficulties in finding a job due to age, sex, lack of Polish language fluency, and/or need to provide care for children. In the case of women, what often matters is the lack of care for their children. As stated by one NGO expert: 'if the mother is alone, (...) she is with the children, so she can't go to work' (PLMZSO5/6). Cultural factors play an important role as Chechen female asylum seekers are traditionally responsible for taking care of children and family life' (PLMZLG1).

It has to be underlined that the majority of micro-level interviewees, regardless of their region/country of origin, declared a willingness to find a job in Poland. This is confirmed by the statement of one of the officials from the Office for Foreigners who said: 'We have a lot of telephone calls (...) where foreigners ask about the possibility of taking up a job in Poland' (PLMZOF2).

Finding a job is crucial for many applicants for international protection as the amount of the allowance provided by the Office for asylum seekers is rather low and they have to look for additional income⁵⁵. In addition, the amount of the allowance has not changed for many years. In this context, one NGO expert said: '[it] has not been raised for X years, since I can remember, I do not know if it has been at least a dozen years or so—in a situation where people have no right to work' (PLMZOS1).

⁵⁵ For further information about allowances and housing, see the section '2.1. Housing and Allowances' of this report.

As already discussed in this report⁵⁶, asylum seekers that decide to stay in the centres for foreigners receive per month 50 PLN (12 EUR) of so-called pocket money and 20 PLN (5 EURO) for the purchase of personal care products. It may not be enough to cover the costs of the phone calls or to use the internet, not to mention any additional products. A Chechen woman said: 'I and my husband would like to work. We need some clothes, some things and 70 PLN per month is not enough' (PLMICH06).

The NGO expert (PLMZOS1) highlighted that the low amount of pocket money is not enough to cover expenditures related to travel by public transport, which leads the asylum seekers to travel without a ticket and exposes them to fines and penalties. Also, the benefits for accommodation outside the centre are very low and insufficient to rent a flat on the market. For those staying outside the centres, the financial support depends on the number of members of the family. The amounts are rather modest (see Table 5). Therefore, for those who have no financial support from family and/or friends, work—documented or undocumented—seems to be the only solution. As mentioned by the NGO expert, 'people either earn some extra money in the grey zone or live in substandard conditions' (PLMZSO1). Among our micro-level respondents, several did not comment on their situation on the labour market, so it is possible that especially those living outside the centre for foreigners performed undocumented work during the asylum procedure.

Some of our meso-level respondents expressed the opinion that some groups of asylum seekers in Poland are not willing to work and they prefer to rely on social assistance provided by the state. This opinion most often concerned Chechens and was explained either by 'cultural' factors or lack of willingness to stay longer in Poland:

It's probably culturally conditioned. Ukraine—great. Whether it is [about Ukrainians] in the [asylum] procedure, or those who entered on the basis of a visa, I think you can see around you that they are everywhere. Find a man from Chechnya who works; you'll find a woman sooner. But the man [Chechnya] is in a comfortable position, because he has money for himself, for his wife, for six children, and that's enough (PLMZOF1).

'I think that their motivation is that they treat Poland only temporarily. All this time they have in mind Western [European] countries. Perhaps they have some information that social assistance and salaries are different there (PLMZLG1).

The second argument finds confirmation in the testimony of our micro-level interviewees. The majority (17 persons) admitted that they had been transferred from Western European countries under the Dublin procedure where they were trying to join their families. Usually they tried to reach Germany. Out of 15 interviewed Chechens, 12 admitted to this. This situation did not change much over time and was described in earlier reports and in the press concerning Poland (Sienkiewicz, 2016) (Stummer, 2016) (Ząbek & Łodziński, 2008).

All of the aforementioned issues influence not only the work possibilities for asylum seekers but also the sectors in which they work in practice. Although access to employment is not limited to certain sectors, most common is agriculture (mostly undocumented), security services, construction, small gastronomy, light work at the reception centre for the centre inhabitants (as manicurists or hairdressers, mostly undocumented), 'handyman' works and car

⁵⁶ For further information about allowances and housing, see the section '2.1. Housing and Allowances' of this report.

repair. Due to the relatively high demand on the Polish market for seasonal employment in agriculture and horticulture, as well as the fact that some centres for foreigners are located outside large cities and in rural areas, this is conducive to employing asylum seekers. This was mentioned in many earlier research reports (Abdoulvakchabova, 2012) (Ząbek & Łodziński, 2008) (Klaus, 2017a) (Pawlak, 2019) and confirmed by meso-level interviewees under the RESPOND project:

Generally, foreigners are eager to take up seasonal work. For example, such as [in] the season for strawberries, apples, i.e., collecting fruits, vegetables (PLMZOF3/4).

This is conditioned by the location of reception centres. The whole centre in Linin near Góra Kalwaria collects apples and strawberries depending on the season (PLMZSO1).

Although some interviewees on both the meso- and micro-levels admitted that the number of asylum seekers who are undocumented workers is high in Poland, some of the interviewed migrants declared that they were not willing to join the informal workforce and were waiting for the certificate, often simply called a 'work permit'. This can be illustrated by the statement of one of our Ukrainian interviewees, who, asked if he worked illegally, replied:

What sense is in that. (...) That is why sometimes I don't like our [Ukrainian] mentality, because it is not done as it must be, and then there is complaining. That it is not so good with us. And yet he goes with red lights. That's why I didn't do that. In general, I worked legally in all my work (PLMIUK18).

During the asylum procedure, even if asylum seekers are allowed to work (if the procedure is prolonged over six months, as mentioned above), no recognition of competences or professional training are offered to them. Moreover, the staff of the centres for foreigners is not supposed to assist in contacts between interested employers and potential employees among asylum seekers. However, practice shows that in some centres the employers put their job offers on the information board to reach potential employees. A respondent from the Office for Foreigners mentioned that some employers contact the centres with a request to help with recruitment among asylum seekers:

(...) I know that a very large proportion of foreigners want to work, and they work because it is only a matter of willingness, because they are able to find a job. And as I said, sometimes employers call [the centres] and ask (PLMZOF2).

An important role in finding a job is played by social networks, especially among larger groups of asylum seekers such as Chechens:

(...) foreigners (...) know where to look for [jobs] because this information is usually circulated by networks and it works quite well. Here, it seems to me that there is no such problem with the process of finding a job or employee, but more formal issues (PLMZOF2).

Some of the inhabitants of the centre may gain additional pocket money from occasional work inside the centre commissioned by centre staff. This was the case of the husband of one interviewee from Chechnya:

The camp is big. There are a lot of leaves here. This job is legal. There are no problems. It is an additional source of income to the allowance. He [*the husband*] cleans the area, rakes leaves (PLMICH05).

The offer of such jobs, however, is limited and they are not well paid. If some additional payments are offered, then, again, it can be, e.g., 50 PLN (about 12 EUR) per month⁵⁷. This payment is offered to foreigners who, for example, help with cleaning the centre or help with translations. Probably because the payment is low, only 5-10 people in a given centre (so fewer than 10% of the inhabitants) engage in this type of work and receive this financial supplement. From the experience of other EU countries, our interviewees could observe that this kind of activity prevented acts of vandalism and violence within the centres, which are more often reported in Poland (PLMZOF1).

As already mentioned, the staff of the centres for foreigners is not supposed to facilitate early access to the labour market for asylum seekers in any way. The only facilitation linked with prospective activity in the labour market they can offer is access to the kindergarten, which operates during precise hours within the centre, giving parents limited time for potential work or other activities. In this context, the activities provided by the NGOs are useful, even if they are ad hoc. For example, in previous years, NGOs within their projects co-financed from different sources, e.g., EU funds, carried out various training such as language, cultural and various types of job training. Along with the change of government policy and access to AMIF funds for NGOs since 2016, however, many NGOs supporting asylum seekers in the centres have been forced to limit their activities. This can be shown in the example of the room for hairdressing and sewing training at one of the centres which was not used at the time of the interview by one of the practitioners because there were no projects implemented by NGOs that time (PLMZP3).

Early access to the labour market plays a crucial role in the creation of a sense of economic security. It is important for improving the mental health of asylum seekers and allows for better integration if the decision on their asylum application is positive. As one official from the Office for Foreigners stated:

(...) foreigners are really looking for something to do and are looking for a job. Not everyone, of course, because there are also those who are not looking for it and probably will not look for. But there is also a group of people who really want to (PLMZOF2).

Many of our meso-level interviewees admitted that the six-month period before receiving a certificate allowing them to legally work in Poland is too long, even if it is in line with EU law. A three-month period might be a good solution. This change in early access to labour market would not make huge difference to the state as the number of asylum seekers is low, however, it would be important for the pre-integration of asylum seekers (MGN2).

2.5. Encounter with Officials, Civil Actors, and the Receiving Society

Asylum seekers meet and interact with various people and institutions from the moment they cross the state border, through the submission of an application for international protection,

⁵⁷ For comparison since 1 January 2020 the lowest hourly rate in Poland is minimum 14.75 PLN (about 3.42 EUR).

and during the asylum procedure, until they receive the final decision on their case. Of course, among them are those who have been transferred to Poland under the Dublin system. Forced migrants whose application is being examined in Poland are encountering representatives of state actors, including intergovernmental international organisations (UNHCR, IOM, EU), and institutions of national public administration (Border Guard, Office for Foreigners, public schools, public healthcare providers), and non-state actors (NGOs supporting migrants, religious associations, employers, private healthcare providers). They also have contact with other migrants (e.g., in the centres for foreigners) as well as the host society (especially if they live outside the centres). The experiences of asylum seekers in this respect are different. Much has been said about these interactions in the above sections regarding specific areas of reception practices, be it housing, access to education, the labour market, or healthcare services. Therefore, below we recall only some of the voices of our micro-level respondents to broaden this picture.

One of the Ukrainian migrants (PLMIUk18) assessed very positively the first accidental interactions with some Poles after entering into the territory of Poland. He was surprised by the scope of help he received on his way to the centre for foreigners in Biała Podlaska—from the purchase of train tickets to refreshments offered at the railway station.

Also, one of the Chechen men is definitely positive about contacts with people in Poland both NGOs, neighbours and others, even if rare unpleasant incidents happened:

We have some Polish friends who are helping us in everything. Also, there is the Ocalenie Foundation. It's the Polish organisation—they are helping us. I can't list all the people helping us who give material and moral support, even helping us to appeal negative decisions. They worried about us. Talking about negative moments, for example, when you drive a car, they don't want to let you go first, offending you, or let's say you are in line in the shop, some drunk person will say something. Anyways we can't complain. We don't have any problems with the local population in the place we live. Our neighbours are very good, they behaved very gentle (PLMICH13).

Another Chechen asylum seeker, a woman, in general is satisfied with the interactions with Polish society:

I like Poles very much and they treat me well too. I have never had any incidents so far (...). Usually people help me. Once I was doing shopping on crutches and a lady who was passing by stopped and gave me a lift home. Then, she helped me with the bags. Generally speaking, people always help me. Maybe if I was wearing a hijab, they wouldn't (PLMICH04).

However, she recalled one unpleasant situation with a doctor:

The only incident I had was with a doctor, a paediatrician. She asked me, if I was a Muslim. I said that I was. She told me that in the old times Arabs kidnapped Polish women and raped them. I told her that Hitler was Catholic. She didn't like my reply and in the end she showed me an indecent gesture with her finger. She told me that she would treat my child only after I learnt Polish. That was the only unpleasant incident during these two years. The nurse suggested that I should write a complaint, but I didn't want that (PLMICH04).

One of the Chechen migrant women declared that her husband had never met with a negative attitude towards him outside the centre:

(...) he [husband] didn't experience any negative incidents. Such things never happened. He looks different than Poles. He has a dark complexion. You can see at once that he is not Polish, not a Slav, but there wasn't a single case of negative attitude (PLMICH05).

Unfortunately, some migrants have experienced verbal harassment/violence and unpleasant situations in the form of insults or inappropriate behaviour in a public place. Sometimes it was enough not to pay attention to it and leave, but sometimes police or third-party intervention was needed:

Sometimes somebody starts to shout 'bitch', starts to swear at me in the street, in the bus, but I don't pay attention to them. (...) What can I do? I am afraid, that somebody can hit me. It is dangerous. I am afraid of people who are drunk. There are a lot of drunk people here. I don't want contact with such people. I don't want to draw attention to myself. I just run away (PLMICH08).

My wife wears a head scarf and when she is by herself, sometimes she hears not pleasing words (PLMICH11).

When we lived in a camp there was a cyclist, a Pole. When he saw us, he always started to swear, he took off his pants and showed us his bottom. He wanted to frighten with a knife another woman who also covers all her body in a traditional way, like me. Chechen women were afraid to go out, but they had to take their children to school and I had to go to the kindergarten. The police came (PLMICH08).

(...) we were looking for a flat in winter, somewhere towards Bemowo or Wola. We were waiting on the staircase. A guy and a woman with a suitcase came out. And the guy taller than me, wider, maybe weighed a hundred kilos. And so he bumps into me, I do not know if he was under the influence of alcohol and says 'Fuck, what are you looking at me for?'. And I just wrote an SMS, my mother talked on the phone. And I say that I was looking at the door because I wanted to enter the staircase. And he was already pulling me. And I think that he heard the accent and says, 'Oh, I think you're from Ukraine'. We switch with my mother to English, she is scared, he waves his hands. It was so terrible (PLMIUk18).

Asylum seekers during the asylum procedure often interact with various NGOs and religious or religious-inspired organisations/communities. This often happens in centres for foreigners where organisations offer different activities but also involves support outside the centres. Our respondents received help from various NGOs, including legal assistance⁵⁸. They mentioned, among other things, the Ocalenie Foundation, the Association for Legal Intervention, the Polish Migration Forum, Caritas Polska, the Community of Sant'Egidio, and the Rule of Law Institute Foundation.

An Iraqi male asylum seeker gave an example of sports activities that allowed him to meet friends of different origin:

⁵⁸ For further information about legal assistance, see (Pachocka & Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

R: (...) here there is an organisation that comes, they asked us to play, they sign up our names and I agreed to go with him, for one month I was playing football. (...) I: Do you have friends from football? R: Yes, for the first time. I went to play football I did not have friends, but now, I mean, there are friends who play, there's someone from Turkey, someone from Poland, there are Arabs, I mean that is good (PLMIr27).

A Kazakh female living with her children in the centre for foreigners can count on material support from various organisations:

There are a lot of foundations and organisations to which I can appeal when I need clothes for my son or for my daughter. They bring them quickly. Everything is very well organised here (PLMIKa30).

Another positive example is the assistance provided by the Community of Sant'Egidio to the Syrian married couple who was offered affordable housing outside the centre for foreigners:

(...) the positive thing, and beautiful thing that I found, that we got to know the foundation of Sant'Egidio, and this is something very, very nice that is rare, even in our country it is rare to happen. They took us from the camp and they managed a place for us to live and they furnished it with acceptable furniture...(...) And they are paying its rent; we are staying and they're taking something very symbolic, so, this is something that is very, very nice. In addition to that, they always remember about us on holidays, they visit us at home...(...) And they take us to church, we pray at church, whenever they have a celebration they send the car after us so they take us... (PLMISy24).

The Community of Sant'Egidio was established in 1968 in Rome and it has been operating in Poland since the 2000s. Its branches are located in Warsaw, Chojna, and Poznań. This community of lay Catholics combines help for different people in need of support—the poor, the elderly, the homeless, the disabled, the prisoners, children living on the street or the periphery, as well as asylum seekers and refugees (Fundacja Sant'Egidio Polska, n.d.).

Temporary housing support was also provided by the Ocalenie Foundation to one of the asylum-seeking Chechen families:

The organization 'Ocalenie', are psychologists. They found shelter, a guest house for the family, which was together with us before they could stay in the camp. My husband through some people found the Chechen family, which gave shelter to us. But the organisation gave a shelter and food to another family that was with us (PLMICh05).

For people who live in the centres for foreigners, the centre is their closest neighbourhood and place for potential socialisation, mostly with other asylum seekers and centre staff, and sometimes with visiting experts from NGOs. Considering that most centres are located outside large urban areas and poorly connected (if at all) by public transport, the opportunities to establish contacts with the host society are very limited. In addition, there are other barriers such as travel costs (e.g., bus tickets) or lack of sufficient childcare provided within the centre for families. The latter is illustrated by the statement of a Kazakh mother with children living in one of the centres:

Sometimes, [I] leave the camp, but not very often as I don't know what to do with the children. When I leave the camp with the children, I need money. They ask to

buy French fries or ice cream in summer. Now, they ask to buy a toy, if I take them to the shop. If I go shopping, I can't take too many things at once. It is difficult to move all together and I can't leave them with someone for too long either (PLMIKa30).

A Yemeni male asylum seeker tries to socialise in the centre for foreigners, also with the security personnel:

Thank God I know all the people here, I mean I usually sit outside because of the internet, because there is not...(…) A [wi-fi] network to catch, outside there is better [wi-fi] reception; because of me sitting outside, I got to know people, at the beginning no one knew me, they used to see me and nothing, and through my hanging out there I got to know them all, even the security, I started a relation with them as friends, I started with all, with anyone who would see me who would recognise me...(PLMIJe29).

One female Ukrainian was also positive about the management and security staff of the centre where she was staying:

The management of the centre—there was no problem with the management. The same with the security men, they were very polite. There was only one young security man, the rest were elderly. I don't know, there were no problems. Everything was nice. All the time they said hello. One could ask them a question anytime, they directed him/her (PLMIUK19).

There was also a critical voice regarding the situation in the centre for mothers with children in Targówek in Warsaw:

There are very poor conditions in this camp. The guards treat people very bad. They shout at the women (...). In Targowek, women argue very often because of the kids. Their kids start to fight and they start to quarrel with each other (PLMICh08).

Some asylum seekers experience the lack of close relatives and family in Poland, which also limits their socialisation:

The only thing is that I miss my relatives very much and they miss me too. My children miss their grandmother very much (PLMIKa30).

Knowledge of Polish and age also seem to have an impact on establishing everyday contacts with the receiving society:

I am an old person in the first place and my life is on the margin, and I am not socialising so much with people because I don't know the language and I am old (...) here in Poland there are no social relations for us since we are strangers and we have no relatives or friends (PLMISy24).

Conclusions: Challenges, Prospects, and Policy Recommendations

In Poland, reception in legal and institutional terms means assistance for foreigners applying for international protection. Its basic scope is governed by the national provisions of the Law on Protection and two ordinances regarding the amount of financial assistance for asylum seekers and rules of stay in centres for foreigners. The most important public body responsible for reception policy is the Office for Foreigners (OF, supervised by the Ministry of Interior and Administration, MIA) and its Department for Social Assistance (DSA). The medical services provider for asylum seekers—selected in a public tender run by the Office for Foreigners—also plays an important role. Since 2015, this entity has been the private provider Petra Medica. Key actors in the area of public education for children include the Ministry of National Education, local public schools, and local self-government authorities in the vicinity of the centres for foreigners. To this end, NGOs also provide various forms of support to foreigners both in and outside the centres.

The findings of our research indicate that the OF has relatively adequate infrastructure to receive asylum seekers. Considering the information provided by the Office of the Commissioner for Human Rights and some NGOs supporting migrants about violations of the right to apply for asylum in Poland and, as a result, the decrease in the number of applicants for international protection in recent years, the number of places for foreigners in the centres seems sufficient. This is also linked to the increasing number of asylum seekers who often decide to live outside the centres for foreigners, relying on housing financial benefits paid by the state. The Office applies a mixed approach to manage the centres. In 2019, four centres were operated by the OF and the remaining seven were run by private entities selected through a tender procedure. The OF-run centres are the core of accommodation infrastructure, while the others can be opened or closed depending on the need. This is important in the event that the number of migrants increases in a short period of time. According to some meso-level respondents interviewed within the RESPOND project, the situation in the Office's centres is better because they are being modernised and more money is invested into them. In general, the standard of the centres has changed for the better in terms of cleanliness and equipment. Actions are also taken to provide pre-school care, places for prayer, and food that includes special dietary requirements. A different issue is the choice of locations of the centres outside urban areas, especially those run by non-OF entities. As mentioned, it is possible to live outside the centres and receive financial benefits for this purpose; however, the funds are so low that they often do not cover even the basic cost of housing and require additional income (e.g., from undocumented work), living with relatives, or sharing an apartment/house with other migrants.

Overall, the staff of the centres for foreigners were assessed rather positively during our micro-level interviews. It should be noted that while living in a centre, the asylum seekers deal with Office employees, not social workers *per se* (there are no legal requirements regarding the education of the staff who work in the centres, e.g., that they have a social work degree or related). What matters in practice is a communicative knowledge of a foreign language, especially Russian (because most of the people who seek protection in Poland are Russian speaking), and ideally both Russian and English. People working in the centres mainly deal with office work, which does not leave them much time for social work with the residents, even if they would like to focus on it. Our meso-level respondents from various institutions/sectors

spoke positively about mutual cooperation between NGOs and the Department for Social Assistance of the Office for Foreigners. In recent years, several NGOs have specialised in helping asylum seekers and refugees but their activity has been limited since 2015/2016 by the Ministry of the Interior and Administration, which significantly changed the rules for financing projects from EU money through AMIF. That resulted in limiting the activities of many NGOs. The situation may improve gradually in 2020 because in 2019, the Ministry settled the competition for AMIF funds.

From the point of view of forced migrants, it is important to note that the centres meet their basic living and social needs. However, staying in the centres is not conducive to pre-integration due to their location outside urban areas, the inability to work legally during the first six months of the asylum procedure, and the limited offer of Polish language courses or other activities. The scope of needs that can be met depends on the regulations and the availability of financial resources. Some migrants do not invest in pre-integration themselves. There are some reasons for this. First, they may not engage in Polish language courses because they do not know whether they will receive a positive decision in their case and be allowed to remain in Poland. Second, they often have other duties, like mothers who must care for children, which precludes them from attending courses. It is also difficult to socialise on a daily basis with the host society because the centres for foreigners are often outside a town or city. The situation is different for those living outside the centres; for them, the low financial assistance is the main challenge.

The meso-level actors we interviewed did not observe any special impact of the 2015 migration crisis on the functioning of the reception system in Poland, and especially on the centres, as their everyday operation is governed by specific rules and procedures. However, the change of government in 2015 and the Ministry's policy influenced the conditions for financing NGOs from AMIF funds, which limited the activities and projects implemented in the centres.

Criticism expressed during the micro- and meso-level interviews concerned the provision of medical services by Petra Medica since 2015—the quality of healthcare services (especially access to specialists) was rated as lower compared to the services provided by the Central Clinical Hospital of the Ministry of Interior and Administration up until 2015. In addition, a deficiency was identified in terms of access to psychologists who provide support free of charge—either as part of guaranteed medical services or NGO assistance. This is connected to the shortage of specialists who know foreign languages and are prepared to work with asylum seekers, who may be affected by various trauma.

Below, we present detailed conclusions for the specific reception areas analysed in this report.

Housing is provided to asylum seekers in Poland in the centres run by the Office for Foreigners as well as in the form of very modest financial support to asylum seekers by the state with the objective of covering the cost of housing outside the centres. The quality of this provision, both in the centres as well as outside them, is frequently substandard. Thus, there is a significant gap between the regulations and policy documents guaranteeing housing for persons seeking asylum and the actual provision of it or the provision of a cash allowance that should be sufficient to rent a room or a flat/house on the open market. The poor quality of housing results in the slow processes of adaptation of the foreigners to their new socio-cultural conditions in the host country and may have a negative impact on their physical and mental health. This report lists numerous issues linked with the provision of housing for people seeking asylum in the existing centres for foreigners as well as outside of them as pointed out, in the course of

the research, by the asylum seekers, practitioners, NGO actors, and members of the state administration.

The provision of basic healthcare to asylum seekers in Poland is relatively, adequately assured. In some ways, this type of provision might be even superior to what is available in other EU countries. The main issues linked with healthcare assistance to persons in reception concern psychological support and specialised medical support. According to the fieldwork material we collected, these types of provisions are seriously underdeveloped and, in view of some of our interviewees, they have been deteriorating rather than improving recently.

As our micro- and meso-level fieldwork material has shown, there are many challenges related to the education of asylum-seeking children. From the perspective of asylum seekers, the biggest obstacles are language and cultural differences. Although children do not know Polish, their parents are obliged to register them to schools immediately after arriving in Poland. The children attend classes in Polish often without understanding what the lesson is about. All available means of supporting children in learning and teachers in teaching, namely additional hours of Polish language, compensatory classes, cultural assistants and preparatory classes are insufficient for adapting both the asylum-seeking and Polish school community (comprising of school administrators, parents, and children) to the new situation. In conclusion, the actual effectiveness of pre-integration in education depends on the implementation of individual treatment of pupils with special needs (namely foreign children) and currently the whole responsibility for this action rests with teachers, school headmasters, and local governments.

With respect to education for adult asylum seekers, there are two important areas: language education and vocational training. Analysis of micro-level data proved that Polish classes are evaluated well by those asylum seekers who now attend or have attended them. However, whereas the main problem with Polish language courses is the demotivation of asylum seekers in class attendance, vocational education for this group almost does not exist. Due to the lack of a systemic solution to this matter, vocational trainings offered to asylum seekers are always part of a particular, single project and are limited in time and space, and by target group.

According to the Polish regulations, asylum seekers are allowed to access the labour market after six months from the date of submission of an asylum application if a first-instance decision has not been taken within this time and if the delay is not attributed to any fault of the asylum seeker. Although this inclusion into the labour market is possible in Poland earlier than stipulated in EU Directive 2013/33/EU, that is, six months instead of nine months, it is perceived as too long. After that time, employment is not limited but asylum seekers face many obstacles to joining the labour market. Among them, the most crucial are the lack of or poor knowledge of the Polish language, lack of or poor awareness of the legal conditions, which affects both asylum seekers' job opportunities and the relationship between an asylum seeker and the potential employer, who may not be aware of whether or for how long they can employ an asylum seeker, as well as the lack of recognition of competences or professional training, which pushes asylum seekers to work far below their qualifications, and, finally, the location of centres far from big cities, which makes it difficult to find a job. Therefore, the limited possibilities for work often push asylum seekers to perform undocumented jobs, which are continued even after the six months and after a final positive decision.

Based on the collected material and analysis carried out, several recommendations can be proposed, including those submitted by our respondents, in the fields of housing and allowances, healthcare (medical) services, early access to education for children and adult asylum seekers, and early access to labour market.

Policy Recommendations

Housing and allowances:

- Increase the financial allowance for those living outside the centres for foreigners.
- Increase the kinds of financial support for asylum seekers living outside the centres for foreigners depending on their family situations and place of living.
- Increase the 'pocket money' for foreigners who live in the centres for foreigners.
- Locate centres for foreigners in cities or near them (and to well-connected public transport).
- Pay more attention to the spatial dispersion of asylum seekers in cities.
- Introduce more pre-integration activities for asylum seekers located in the centres for foreigners and outside them.

Healthcare (medical) services:

- Move away from the model of providing medical care to asylum seekers by a specially selected service provider (currently, the private medical company Petra Medica) and put asylum seekers under the general public national healthcare system. As one of the interviewees put it straightforwardly: 'these people should be treated like citizens' (PLMZSO1). Some of the benefits of such a change would be financial and organisational. At present, the cost of medical care for persons in reception can be either overestimated or underestimated. If the healthcare provisions were public and under the supervision of the National Health Fund, such a situation would not take place. Another benefit of such a change could be the smooth transition of healthcare provision from the reception phase to the integration phase, which at present remains highly problematic.
- Change public tender criteria for the provision of healthcare assistance to persons in reception so that they take greater accountability for the quality of medical services and access to specialists.
- Increase the availability of specialised medical support for people who need such help and interpretation during medical appointments when appropriate.
- Increase the availability of medical care outside of where the Office for Foreigners' service centres are located.
- Increase access to psychological help in a language other than Polish.

Early access to education for children:

- The weighting of the education subsidy for teaching foreign children should be increased so local governments and schools can afford to hire cultural assistants and organise preparatory classes if needed.
- The Ministry of National Education should provide training for teachers working with foreign children so they have skills to educate non-native Polish pupils.

Early access to education for adults:

- Polish language classes during the asylum procedure should be designed to answer the specific needs of asylum seekers, including mothers of young children, reluctant men, women not willing to participate in the same class with men (because of religious and/or cultural reasons), and generally people trying to navigate the Polish bureaucracy. Incentives to participate in Polish classes should be linked with the overall offer of Poland as a country where they can settle, work, and live.
- The Office for Foreigners should provide vocational courses for asylum seekers in order to, first, prepare them to eventually enter the Polish labour market and, second, not to exacerbate their feeling of isolation by exclusion from working activity.

Early access to the labour market:

- Having in mind Polish labour market conditions as well as the migration situation in Poland, it might be a good solution to provide asylum seekers with earlier access to the labour market, so, instead of the current six months, it would be three months from the date of submission of their asylum application. This is important for the pre-integration of asylum seekers because it can improve their mental health and increase their sense of economic security.
- Asylum seekers should be offered simple but paid activities to be performed in the centres for foreigners. This may include not only simple work such as raking leaves or snow removal but also roles using their potential, knowledge, and skills to support other residents of the centres. For instance, if someone is a judo trainer, he/she could run paid classes for those living in the centre.
- It is recommended that job training that does not demand high-level language skills be provided, for example, confectionery or carpentry.
- More actions should be taken to spur both asylum seekers and potential employees towards asylum seekers' work possibilities and streamlining procedures. Also important is the possibility to facilitate contact between employers and residents of the centres for foreigners, either by the staff of the centres or by other bodies, such as NGOs.
- Centres for foreigners should be established closer to cities to facilitate access to a more developed labour market.
- Public authorities as well as NGOs should work together to create a welcoming political and social climate for forced migrants.

Appendices

Table 10 Main legislative acts relevant to asylum procedures, reception conditions and detention in Poland

The original title in Polish with full references (<i>in italics</i>)	The simplified title in English (translation)	Abbreviation in English
<i>Konstytucja Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej z dnia 2 kwietnia 1997 r. uchwalona przez Zgromadzenie Narodowe w dniu 2 kwietnia 1997 r., przyjęta przez Naród w referendum konstytucyjnym w dniu 25 maja 1997 r., podpisana przez Prezydenta Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej w dniu 16 lipca 1997 r. (Dz.U. 1997 Nr 78, poz. 483 z późn. zm.)</i>	Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 2 April 1997 (Journal of Laws 1997 No. 78, item 483 with amendments)	Constitution
<i>Ustawa z dnia 13 czerwca 2003 r. o udzielaniu cudzoziemcom ochrony na terytorium Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej (t.j. Dz.U. z 2019 r. poz. 1666 z późn. zm.)</i>	Law of 13 June 2003 on granting protection to foreigners within the territory of the Republic of Poland (consolidated text, Journal of Laws 2019, item 1666 with amendments)	Law on Protection
<i>Ustawa z dnia 12 grudnia 2013 r. o cudzoziemcach (t.j. Dz.U. z 2018 r. poz. 2094 z późn. zm.)</i>	Law of 12 December 2013 on foreigners (consolidated text, Journal of Laws 2018, item 2094 with amendments)	Law on Foreigners
<i>Ustawa z dnia 14 czerwca 1960 r. Kodeks postępowania administracyjnego (t.j. Dz.U. z 2018 r. poz. 2096 z późn. zm.)</i>	Law of 14 June 1960 Code of administrative procedure (consolidated text, Journal of Laws 2018, item 2096 with amendments)	Code of Administrative Procedure
<i>Ustawa z dnia 6 czerwca 1997 r. Kodeks postępowania karnego (t.j. Dz.U. z 2018 r. poz. 1987 z późn. zm.)</i>	Law of 6 June 1997 Code of Criminal Procedure (consolidated text, Journal of Laws 2018, item 1987 with amendments)	Code of Criminal Procedure
<i>Ustawa z dnia 30 sierpnia 2002 r. Prawo o postępowaniu przed sądami administracyjnymi (t.j. Dz.U. z 2019 r. poz. 2325)</i>	Law of 30 August 2002 Law on proceedings before administrative courts (consolidated text, Journal of Laws 2019, item 2325)	Law on Proceedings Before Administrative Courts

Source: own elaboration based on (Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d.); (Szulecka, et al., 2018b, pp. 67-69); (C.H.Beck, n.d.); (Sejm RP, n.d.).

Table 11 Main implementing decrees and administrative guidelines and regulations relevant to asylum procedures, reception conditions and detention in Poland

Original title in Polish with full references (<i>in italics</i>)	Simplified title in English (translation)
<i>Rozporządzenie Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych i Administracji z dnia 19 lutego 2016 r. w sprawie wysokości pomocy dla cudzoziemców ubiegających się o udzielenie ochrony międzynarodowej (Dz.U. 2016 poz. 311)</i>	Ordinance of the Minister of Interior and Administration of 19 February 2016 on the amount of assistance for foreigners seeking international protection (Journal of Laws 2016, item 311)
<i>Rozporządzenie Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych z dnia 23 października 2015 r. w sprawie regulaminu pobytu w ośrodku dla cudzoziemców (Dz. U. 2015 poz. 1828)</i>	Ordinance of the Ministry of Interior of 23 October 2015 on the rules of stay in the centre for foreigners (Journal of Laws 2015, item 1828)
<i>Rozporządzenie Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych i Administracji z dnia 24 kwietnia 2015 r. w sprawie strzeżonych ośrodków i aresztów dla cudzoziemców (Dz.U. 2015 poz. 596)</i>	Ordinance of the Ministry of Interior and Administration of 24 April 2015 on the guarded centres and detention centres for foreigners (Journal of Laws 2015, item 596)
<i>Rozporządzenie Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych z dnia 4 listopada 2015 r. w sprawie wzoru formularza wniosku o udzielenie ochrony międzynarodowej (Dz.U. z 2015 r. poz. 1859)</i>	Ordinance of the Ministry of Interior of 4 November 2015 on the form of application for international protection (Journal of Laws 2015, item 1859)

Source: own elaboration based on (Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d.); (Szulecka, et al., 2018b, pp. 67-69); (C.H.Beck, n.d.); (Sejm RP, n.d.).

Table 12 Directives and other CEAS measures transposed into national legislation in Poland

Title of the Directive/ Regulation at the EU level (English name)	Abbreviation	Deadline for transposition	Date of transposition	Title of the corresponding legal act at the national level (English name, Polish name <i>in italics</i>)
Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection, and for the content of the protection granted (OJ L 337, 20.12.2011)	Recast Qualification Directive	21 December 2013	30 August 2014	Law of 26 June 2014 amending the law on granting protection to foreigners within the territory of the Republic of Poland and some other laws (Journal of Laws 2014, item 1004) <i>Ustawa z dnia 26 czerwca 2014 r. o zmianie ustawy o udzielaniu cudzoziemcom ochrony na terytorium Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej oraz niektórych innych ustaw (Dz.U. 2014, poz. 1004)</i>
Directive 2013/32/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection (OJ L 180, 29.6.2013)	Recast Asylum Procedures Directive	20 July 2015; Article 31(3)-(5) to be transposed by 20 July 2018	13 November 2015	Law of 10 September 2015 amending the law on granting protection to foreigners within the territory of the Republic of Poland and some other laws (Journal of Laws 2015, item 1607) <i>Ustawa z dnia 10 września 2015 r. o zmianie ustawy o udzielaniu cudzoziemcom ochrony na terytorium Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej oraz niektórych innych ustaw (Dz.U. z 2015 r. poz. 1607)</i>

Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (OJ L 180, 29.6.2013)	Recast Reception Conditions Directive	20 July 2015	13 November 2015	Law of 10 September 2015 amending the law on granting protection to foreigners within the territory of the Republic of Poland and some other laws (Journal of Laws 2015, item 1607) <i>Ustawa z dnia 10 września 2015 r. o zmianie ustawy o udzielaniu cudzoziemcom ochrony na terytorium Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej oraz niektórych innych ustaw (Dz.U. z 2015 r. poz. 1607)</i>
Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 establishing the criteria and mechanisms for determining the Member State responsible for examining an application for international protection lodged in one of the Member States by a third-country national or a stateless person (OJ L 180, 29.6.2013)	Dublin III Regulation	Directly applicable 20 July 2013	13 November 2015	Law of 10 September 2015 amending the law on granting protection to foreigners within the territory of the Republic of Poland and some other laws (Journal of Laws 2015, item 1607) <i>Ustawa z dnia 10 września 2015 r. o zmianie ustawy o udzielaniu cudzoziemcom ochrony na terytorium Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej oraz niektórych innych ustaw (Dz.U. z 2015 r. poz. 1607)</i>

Source: own elaboration based on (Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d.); (Szulecka, et al., 2018b, pp. 67-69); (C.H.Beck, n.d.); (Sejm RP, n.d.); (Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d.); (EUR-lex, n.d.).

References and Sources

- Abdouvakchabova, M., 2012. Problemy cudzoziemców w Polsce w świetle funkcjonowania Fundacji Ocalenie. In: M. Duszczyk & P. Dąbrowski, eds. *Przestrzeganie praw cudzoziemców w Polsce. Biuletyn RPO. Źródła*. Warszawa: Biuro Rzecznika Praw Obywatelskich, pp. 43-52.
- Association for Legal Intervention, 2019. *Lokalizacja ośrodków strzeżonych dla cudzoziemców*. [Online] Available at: <https://interwencjaprawna.pl/detencja/detencja-informator/lokalizacja-osrodkow-strzezonych-dla-cudzoziemcow/> [Accessed 30 December 2019].
- Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d. *Access to the labour market. Poland*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/poland/reception-conditions/employment-and-education/access-labour-market> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d. *Poland. Health Care*. [Online] Available at: http://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/poland/reception-conditions/health-care#footnote10_yh9ynlw [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d. *Poland: ANNEX I - TRANSPOSITION OF THE CEAS IN NATIONAL LEGISLATION*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/poland/annex-i-transposition-ceas-national-legislation> [Accessed 30 December 2019].
- Asylum Information Database (AIDA), n.d. *Poland: overview of the legal framework*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/poland/overview-legal-framework> [Accessed 30 December 2019].
- Baczyński-Sielaczek, R., 2016. *Język polski w ośrodkach. Wyniki badania ewaluacyjnego*, Warszawa: Instytut Spraw Publicznych.
- Białas, J., Fagasiński, M., Górczyńska, M., Jaźwińska, M., Łysienia, M., Ostaszewska-Żuk, E., Rusiłowicz, K. & Witko, D., 2014. *W poszukiwaniu ochrony. Wybrane problemy dotyczące realizacji praw cudzoziemców ubiegających się o nadanie statusu uchodźcy i objętych ochroną międzynarodową w latach 2012-2014. Obserwacje Programu Pomocy Prawnej dla Uchodźców i Migrantów HFPC*, Warszawa: Helsińska Fundacja Praw Człowieka.
- C.H.Beck, n.d. *System Informacji Prawnej Legalis*. [Online] Available at: <https://legalis.pl/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Central Statistical Office, n.d. *Podział administracyjny Polski*. [Online] Available at: <https://stat.gov.pl/statystyka-regionalna/jednostki-terytorialne/podzial-administracyjny-polski/> [Accessed 30 December 2019].

- Centrum Wolontariatu w Lublinie, n.d. *Centrum Wolontariatu w Lublinie*. [Online] Available at: wolontariat.lublin.pl [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Chrzanowska, A. & Czerniejewska, I., 2015. *"Mieszkamy tutaj, bo nie mamy innego wyjścia..." Raport z monitoringu warunków mieszkaniowych uchodźców w Polsce*, Warszawa: Stowarzyszenie Interwencji Prawnej.
- Commissioner for Human Rights, 2016. *Obecność uchodźców w małych gminach. Doświadczenia Góry Kalwarii i Podkopy Leśnej w integracji uchodźców i edukacji ich dzieci*, Warszawa: Commissioner for Human Rights.
- Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (OJ L 180, 29.6.2013).
- Dziennik Gazeta Prawna, 2018. *MSWiA: nie będzie gett edukacyjnych*. [Online] Available at: <https://edgp.gazetaprawna.pl/e-wydanie/1269,5-kwietnia-2018/5623,Dziennik-Gazeta-Prawna/663945,MSWiA:-nie-bedzie-gett-edukacyjnych.html> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Encyclopaedia Britannica, n.d. *Chechnya*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Chechnya> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- EUR-lex, n.d. *EUR-lex*. [Online] Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/homepage.html> [Accessed 6 January 2020].
- European Commission (EC) - Eurydice, 2019. *Poland. Organisation of the Education System and of its Structure*. [Online] Available at: https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/content/organisation-education-system-and-its-structure-56_en [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Facebook, n.d. *Chlebem i solą. Polacy dla uchodźców*. [Online] Available at: https://www.facebook.com/pg/polacydlauchodzcow/about/?ref=page_internal [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Florczak, A., 2003. In: *Uchodźcy w Polsce. Między humanitaryzmem a pragmatyzmem*. Toruń: Wydawnictwo Adam Marszałek.
- Fundacja Sant'Egidio Polska, n.d. *Kim jesteśmy?*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.santegidio.pl/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Górak-Sosnowska, K. & Pachocka, M., 2019. Islamophobia and the quest for European identity in Poland. In: A. Zempi, ed. *The Routledge International Handbook of Islamophobia*. London, New York: Routledge, pp. 225-236.
- Hajduk, S., 2018. Edukacja dzieci w procedurze uchodźczej. *Urząd do Spraw Cudzoziemców: Biuletyn informacyjny kwiecień 2018*, Issue 3, p. 6.

- Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights (HFHR), 2019. *AIDA Country Report: Poland. 2018 Update*, European Council on Refugees and Exiles (ECRE).
- Horolets, A., Mica, A., Pawlak, M. & Kubicki, P., 2019. Ignorance as an Outcome of Categorizations: The “Refugees” in the Polish Academic Discourse before and after the 2015 Refugee Crisis. *East European Politics and Societies*.
- Klaus, W., 2017a. Rozwiązania prawne stosowane w odniesieniu do osób starających się o ochronę w Polsce. W: A. Górny, red. *Uchodźcy w Polsce. Sytuacja prawna, skala napływu i integracja w społeczeństwie polskim oraz rekomendacje*. Kraków - Warszawa: Komitet Badań nad Migracjami PAN, pp. 9-35.
- Klaus, W., 2017b. Security First – New Right-Wing Government in Poland and its Policy Towards Immigrants and Refugees. *Surveillance and Society*, vol. 15 (issue 3/4), pp. 523-528.
- Klaus, W., 2018. Karanie za pomoc – jak rządy zniechęcają organizacje społeczne wspierające migrantów i ich aktywistów do działania. *Trzeci Sektor*, pp. 8-18.
- Klaus, W., Lévy, M., Rzeplińska, I. & Scheinost, M., 2018. Refugees and asylum seekers in Central-European Countries – reality, politics and the creation of fear in societies. In: H. Kury & S. Redo, eds. *Refugees and Migrants in Law and Policy Challenges and Opportunities for Global Civic Education*. Springer, pp. 457-494.
- Konstytucja Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej z dnia 2 kwietnia 1997 r. uchwalona przez Zgromadzenie Narodowe w dniu 2 kwietnia 1997 r., przyjęta przez Naród w referendum konstytucyjnym w dniu 25 maja 1997 r., podpisana przez Prezydenta Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej w dniu 16 lipca 1997 r. (Dz.U. 1997 Nr 78, poz. 483 z późn. zm.).
- Legut, A. & Pędziwiatr, K., 2018. Sekurytyzacja migracji w polityce polskiej a zmiana postaw Polaków wobec uchodźców. In: R. Jończy, ed. *Sami swoi? Wielokulturowość we współczesnej Europie*. Gliwice, Opole: Dom Współpracy Polsko-Niemieckiej, pp. 41–51.
- Łodziński, S., 2019. Uchodźcy jako „podejrzana społeczność” (suspect community). Polska opinia publiczna wobec udzielania pomocy uchodźcom w okresie maj 2015 – grudzień 2018. *Studia Socjologiczn-Polityczne*, Volume 1(20), pp. 31–60.
- Ministerstwo Edukacji Narodowej (MEN), 2019. *Informacja o kształceniu w polskim systemie oświaty osób przybywających z zagranicy*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.gov.pl/web/edukacja/informacja-o-ksztalceniu-w-polskim-systemie-oswiaty-osob-przybywajacych-z-zagranicy> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Mołęda-Zdziech, M., Pachocka, M. & Wach, M., 2020. Immigration and integration policies in Poland: institutional, political and social perspectives. In: J. Ruano i J. Franzke, redaktorzy *Local Integration Policy of Migrants. European Experiences and Challenges (in press)*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Nagel, A. K., Korkut, U. & Barthoma, S., 2018. *Guidelines for Sampling Criteria. Task Force II*. RESPOND consortium.
- Nalborczyk, A. & Pędziwiatr, K., 2018. Between Old Traditions and New Diversities – Islamic Religious Education in Poland. In: J. Berglund, ed. *European Perspectives on Islamic Education and Public Schooling*. Sheffield : Equinox, pp. 136–156.

- Office for Foreigners, 2015. *First Steps in Poland. Guidebook for foreigners applying for International Protection*, Warsaw: Office for Foreigners.
- Office for Foreigners, 2017. *Polski na dobry start' – projekt dla cudzoziemców*. [Online] Available at: <https://udsc.gov.pl/polski-na-dobry-start-w-osrodkach-dla-cudzoziemcow/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Office for Foreigners, 2018. *'Filtr epidemiologiczny' rozpoczął działalność*. [Online] Available at: <https://udsc.gov.pl/filtr-epidemiologiczny-rozpoznal-dzialalnosc/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Office for Foreigners, 2019a. *Miesięczny raport z działalności urzędu—Czerwiec 2019*. [Online] Available at: <https://udsc.gov.pl/statystyki/raporty-okresowe/meldunek-miesieczny/2015-2/2019-2/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Office for Foreigners, 2019b. *Guidebook. Department for Social Assistance*, Warsaw: Office for Foreigners.
- Office for Foreigners, 2019c. *Załącznik 1. Specyfikacja istotnych warunków zamówienia na świadczenie usług edukacyjnych na potrzeby Urzędu do Spraw Cudzoziemców*.
- Office for Foreigners, 2019d. *Wsparcie dla cudzoziemców w procedurze uchodźczej*. [Online] Available at: <https://udsc.gov.pl/wsparcie-dla-cudzoziemcow-w-procedurze-uchodzczej/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Office for Foreigners, 2019e. *Nowy rok szkolny dla dzieci w procedurze uchodźczej*. [Online] Available at: <https://udsc.gov.pl/nowy-rok-szkolny-dla-dzieci-w-procedurze-uchodzczej-2/> [Accessed 10 January 2020].
- Office for Foreigners, n.d. *International legal acts*. [Online] Available at: <https://udsc.gov.pl/en/prawo/akty-prawa-miedzynarodowego/> [Accessed 30 December 2019].
- Office for Foreigners, n.d. *Kontakt do ośrodków*. [Online] Available at: <https://udsc.gov.pl/uchodzcy-2/pomoc-socjalna/osrodki-dla-cudzoziemcow/mapka-osrodkow/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Office for Foreigners, n.d. *Statistics*. [Online] Available at: <https://udsc.gov.pl/en/statystyki/> [Accessed 30 December 2019].
- Office for Foreigners, n.d. *Types of assistance*. [Online] Available at: <https://udsc.gov.pl/en/uchodzcy-2/pomoc-socjalna/system-pomocy-socjalnej/rodzaje-pryznawanej-pomocy/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Pachocka, M. & Sobczak-Szelc, K., 2020. *Refugee Protection. Poland – Country Report*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.respondmigration.com/wp-blog>

- Pachocka, M. & Szczerba-Zawada, A., 2019. Migration. In: J. Barcz & Z. Czachór, eds. *Priorities of the new European Commission and the interests of Poland. Team Europe's assessments and conclusions*. Warsaw: European Commission Representation in Poland-Elipsa, pp. 79-84.
- Pachocka, M. & Velez, C. D., 2019. Understanding EU Member State cooperation within the asylum regime during the migration and refugee crisis from an IR perspective. In: A. Adamczyk, M. Dziembała, A. Kłós & M. Pachocka, eds. *Promoting values, stability and economic prosperity in the changing world in the global context. EU facing current challenges, opportunities, crisis and conflicts*. Warsaw: Elipsa, pp. 139-154.
- Pawlak, M., 2019. Zatrudnienie. In: *W stronę krajowego mechanizmu ewaluacji integracji. Diagnoza sytuacji beneficjentów ochrony międzynarodowej w Polsce*. Warszawa: Instytut Spraw Publicznych, pp. 31-35.
- Petra Medica, n.d. *Petra Medica*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.petramedica.pl/o-firmie> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Pędziwiatr, K., 2019. *The new Polish migration policy – false start*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/can-europe-make-it/the-new-polish-migration-policy-false-start/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Polish Border Guard Headquarters, 2019. *Polish Border Guard Headquarters*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.strazgraniczna.pl/> [Accessed 30 December 2019].
- Rozporządzenie Ministra Edukacji Narodowej z dnia 18 grudnia 2018 r. w sprawie sposobu podziału części oświatowej subwencji ogólnej dla jednostek samorządu terytorialnego w roku 2019 (Dz.U. z 2018 r. poz. 2446).
- Rozporządzenie Ministra Edukacji Narodowej z dnia 28 marca 2019 r. zmieniające rozporządzenie w sprawie kształcenia osób niebędących obywatelami polskimi oraz osób będących obywatelami polskimi, które pobierały naukę w szkołach funkcjonujących w systemach oświaty innych państw (Dz.U. z 2019 r. poz. 666).
- Rozporządzenie Ministra Edukacji Narodowej z dnia 9 sierpnia 2017 r. w sprawie warunków organizowania kształcenia, wychowania i opieki dla dzieci i młodzieży niepełnosprawnych, niedostosowanych społecznie i zagrożonych niedostosowaniem społecznym Dz.U. z 2017 r. poz. 1578 z późn. zm.).
- Rozporządzenie Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych i Administracji z dnia 19 lutego 2016 r. w sprawie wysokości pomocy dla cudzoziemców ubiegających się o udzielenie ochrony międzynarodowej (Dz.U. 2016 poz. 311).
- Rozporządzenie Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych z dnia 23 października 2015 r. w sprawie regulaminu pobytu w ośrodku dla cudzoziemców (Dz. U. 2015 poz. 1828).
- Rzeczpospolita, 2018. *RPD: równe szanse małoletnich cudzoziemców w dostępie do edukacji*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.rp.pl/Rodzina/303029941-RPD-rowne-szanse-maloletnich->

[cudzoziemcow-w-dostepie-do-edukacji.html](#)

[Accessed 25 February 2020].

- Sejm RP, n.d. *Internetowy System Aktów Prawnych - ISAP*. [Online] Available at: <http://prawo.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Sienkiewicz, Ł., 2016. *Labour market integration of asylum seekers and refugees - Poland*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. [Online] Available at: <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=2&ved=2ahUKEwiF6K6Cz7DoAhWNY8QBHfRVAkgQFjABegQIAxAB&url=http%3A%2F%2Fec.europa.eu%2Fsocial%2FblobServlet%3FdocId%3D15919%26langId%3Den&usq=AOvVaw1wsyQhu1JWsFkYPRTPMisO> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Sołtan-Kościelecka, K., 2018. Klasy powitalne. Realna szansa na poprawę warunków kształcenia cudzoziemców czy pozorne rozwiązanie?. *Biuletyn Migracyjny*, June, No. 57.
- Stummer, K., 2016. *Forgotten Refugees: Chechen asylum seekers in Poland*. [Online] Available at: <http://politicalcritique.org/cee/poland/2016/forgotten-refugees-chechen-asylum-seekers-in-poland/> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Szczepanik, M., 2017. *Right to Healthcare and Access to Medical Services for Asylum Seekers and Beneficiaries of International Protection in Poland*. [Online] Available at: <https://legal-dialogue.org/right-healthcare-access-medical-services-asylum-seekers-beneficiaries-international-protection-poland> [Accessed 25 February 2020].
- Szef Urzędu do Spraw Cudzoziemców, 2018. *Zarządzenie nr 7 Szefa Urzędu do Spraw Cudzoziemców z dnia 29 października 2018 r. w sprawie ustalenia regulaminu organizacyjnego UdSC*. Warszawa: Urząd do Spraw Cudzoziemców.
- Szulecka, M., 2019. *Border Management and Migration Controls in Poland*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.respondmigration.com/wp-blog>
- Szulecka, M., Pachocka, M. & Sobczak-Szelc, K., 2018a. *CMR University of Warsaw - Country Sampling Criteria*. Warsaw: Centre of Migration Research, University of Warsaw (unpublished document).
- Szulecka, M., Pachocka, M. & Sobczak-Szelc, K., 2018b. *Poland – Country Report: Legal and Policy Framework of Migration Governance*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.respondmigration.com/wp-blog>
- UN General Assembly, 1951. *Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees, 28 July 1951, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 189, p. 137*.
- UN General Assembly, 1967. *Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees, 31 January 1967, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 606, p. 267*.
- Ustawa z dnia 12 grudnia 2013 r. o cudzoziemcach (t.j. Dz.U. z 2018 r. poz. 2094 z późn. zm.).
- Ustawa z dnia 13 czerwca 2003 r. o udzielaniu cudzoziemcom ochrony na terytorium Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej (t.j. Dz.U. z 2019 r. poz. 1666 z późn. zm.).

- Ustawa z dnia 14 grudnia 2016 – Przepisy wprowadzające ustawę – Prawo oświatowe (Dz.U. z 2017 r. poz. 60 z późn. zm).
- Ustawa z dnia 14 grudnia 2016 r. - Prawo oświatowe (t.j. Dz.U. z 2017 r. poz. 59 z późn. zm.).
- Ustawa z dnia 20 kwietnia 2004 r. o promocji zatrudnienia i instytucjach rynku pracy (t.j. Dz.U. z 2019 r. poz. 1482, 1622, 1818, 2473 z późn. zm.).
- Ustawa z dnia 20 lipca 2018 r. - Prawo o szkolnictwie wyższym i nauce (Dz.U. z 2018 r. poz. 1668 z późn. zm.).
- Weiner, A., 2006. *Europeizacja polskiej polityki wobec cudzoziemców: 1990-2003*. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe Scholar.
- Wysieńska, K., 2014. *Niewidzialni i niepoliczalni. Rodzaje i skala bezdomności uchodźców i osób w 'procedurze'*, Warszawa: Instytut Spraw Publicznych.
- Ząbek, M. & Łodziński, S., 2008. *Uchodźcy w Polsce. Próba spojrzenia antropologicznego*. Warszawa: Aspra-Jr.